

Daniel Tavares de Castro

Studies on Retail Payment Instruments

Brasília

2022

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Universidade de Brasília - UnB

Faculdade de Administração, Economia e Contabilidade - FACE

Programa de Pós-Graduação em Administração - PPGA

Supervisor: Ivan Ricardo Gartner

Brasília

2022

Daniel Tavares de Castro

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Thesis approved. Brasília, September 26th 2022.

Ivan Ricardo Gartner
Supervisor

Oswaldo Cândido da Silva Filho
Member 1

Thiago Christiano Silva
Member 2

Paulo Roberto Barbosa Lustosa
Member 3

Carlos Rosano Peña
Alternate

Brasília
2022

Abstract

The thesis is made of four studies about retail payments. With the objective of suggesting a research agenda about retail payments, the thesis also presents a bibliometric analysis of the literature. I analyzed and classified 93 papers published from 1995 to 2021, identified through the keywords "retail payments". A major part of the studies is empirical, quantitative and has determinants of usage or choice of payment instrument, specific attributes of payment instrument or industrial organization as their object. Their scope is mainly only one developed country, their focus is cash and cards and analyze short periods of up to 2 years. They use survey, payment diaries or regulators data, employ statistical, econometric, or multivariate analysis and employ logit and its variations as their technique. There is a lack of studies involving emerging countries or a broader sample of countries, long term analysis, alternative techniques such as the ones of machine learning or simulations, data on real transactions and recent instruments such as mobile or fast payments. Fulfilling some of these gaps, the objective of the second study is to identify determinants of usage of electronic and fast payments, through a dynamic panel data analysis with a wider sample of countries from 2005 to 2020. Countries with a higher proportion of older people in the population tend to use more electronic and fast payments, although the level of past use is the most important determinant of present use. The third study also tries to fulfill some of the gaps, with the objective of identifying determinants of choice of electronic payments employing a multilevel logit regression, using data from a survey with 1,519 Brazilians in 2019. Results show that male payers, with higher age and income, more educated, living in the Southern and South-eastern regions of Brazil, having checking or payment accounts, and with previous experience in mobile purchases, are more likely to choose electronic payment instruments. The probability of choosing these instruments is higher in payments of greater value, made on term or in installments and for the purchase of durable goods. The fourth study explains payment instrument choice with machine learning methods, using the same data employed in the previous study. Payment condition, when it is a term or in installment payment, is the most important variable, followed by the way one receives its source of income (when in an account), past experience with mobile purchases and the value of the transaction. The fifth study uses an agent-based model that found that a theory on cash management explains well the empirical distribution of payments per instrument and value reported in Brazilian payment diaries also employed in the two previous studies. With regulatory changes related to payments and with the implementation of new payment instruments, these results can be of interest to market participants, subsidizing investment decisions in infrastructure, technology, and marketing necessary to stimulate the use of electronic instruments, and to regulators, subsidizing policies aiming at the electronization or implementation of new instruments.

JEL classification: D12, G30, M38, M39.

Key-words: retail payments, electronic payment instruments, bibliometric analysis, fast payments, dynamic panel data analysis, logit regression, machine learning, agent-based model.

Resumo

A tese é composta por quatro estudos sobre pagamentos de varejo. Com o objetivo de sugerir uma agenda de pesquisa sobre o tema, o primeiro estudo apresenta uma análise bibliométrica da literatura. Foram analisados e classificados 93 artigos publicados entre 1995 e 2021, identificados através das palavras-chave "retail payments". A maior parte dos trabalhos é empírica, quantitativa, tem por objeto determinantes de uso dos instrumentos, tem por escopo apenas um país desenvolvido, foca em dinheiro e cartões, analisa períodos curtos, usa dados de *surveys*, diários de pagamentos ou reguladores, usa análise econométrica e emprega logit e suas variações como técnica. Há carência de trabalhos envolvendo países emergentes ou uma amostra mais abrangente, análises de longo prazo, técnicas alternativas, dados de transações reais e instrumentos mais recentes como pagamentos móveis e instantâneos. Suprindo algumas das lacunas identificadas, o segundo estudo tem por objetivo identificar os determinantes do uso de pagamentos eletrônicos e instantâneos, através análise dinâmica de dados em painel de 2005 a 2020, empregando amostra abrangente de países. Países com maior proporção de idosos tendem a usar mais pagamentos eletrônicos e instantâneos, embora o nível de uso passado seja o determinante mais importante para o nível corrente de uso. O terceiro estudo também busca suprir lacunas, ao identificar determinantes da escolha de pagamentos eletrônicos empregando análise de regressão logit multinível, utilizando dados de pesquisa que abrangeu 1.519 brasileiros em 2019. Os resultados indicam que pessoas do gênero masculino, mais velhas, com renda maior, mais escolarizadas, moradoras das regiões Sul e Sudeste, que são titulares de contas e que já usaram celulares para compras são mais propensas a escolher instrumentos eletrônicos. A probabilidade de escolha desses instrumentos é maior em pagamentos de maior valor, a prazo ou parcelados e em compras de bens duráveis. O quarto estudo explica a escolha de instrumentos de pagamento com métodos de aprendizagem de máquina, usando os mesmos dados do estudo três. Condição do pagamento, quando a prazo ou a prestações, é a variável mais importante, seguida da maneira de receber a fonte de renda (quando em conta), experiência prévia com compras em celular e o valor da transação. O quinto estudo constrói um modelo baseado em agentes concluindo que uma teoria de gerenciamento de dinheiro explica bem a distribuição empírica de pagamentos por instrumento e valores reportada nos diários de pagamentos também empregado nos dois estudos anteriores. Após diversas mudanças regulamentares relacionadas a pagamentos implementadas ao redor do mundo e com a entrada em operação de novos instrumentos, os resultados podem ser de interesse tanto dos participantes do mercado, para subsidiar decisões de investimento em instrumentos eletrônicos inovadores, quanto dos reguladores, para subsidiar políticas e regulações visando a eletronização de pagamentos ou a implantação de instrumentos de pagamento mais modernos.

Classificação JEL: D12, G30, M38, M39.

Palavras-chaves: pagamentos de varejo, instrumentos de pagamento eletrônicos, pagamentos rápidos, análise bibliométrica, análise dinâmica de dados em painel, regressão logit, aprendizagem de máquina, modelo baseado em agentes.

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1 Introduction

Retail payment instruments and the systems that settle them are fundamental for the good functioning of the economy, allowing the exchange of resources necessary for the relationship among diverse economic agents (Rysman & Schuh, 2017). Originally based on paper, payment instrument have been subject to a fast electronization due to technological advances seen in the last decades, allowing more efficiency and fluidity to its users, although cash is still the dominant payment instrument in most of the countries (Bech et al., 2018; Bech & Boar, 2019; Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2019).

This migration towards electronic instruments, allowing greater well-being to society as a whole, has been pursued by market participants and stimulated by regulators. To that end, it is fundamental to identify and explain factors that influence the use and choice of these instruments by the population, contributing to their development or hampering their adoption.

Bibliometric analysis conducted in the first study of the thesis (chapter 2) pointed out that the most frequent research objects in retail payments were the determinants of choice by users as a function of their socioeconomic characteristics and of transaction characteristics. Determinants of usage, which focus on aggregate macroeconomic and environmental characteristics that influence the aggregate usage of payment instruments, were the second object most researched.

Among the studies on determinants of usage or choice, I found gaps related to the countries considered in the samples, seldom including emerging markets. The studies generally employ traditional econometric techniques, with limited usage of alternative techniques such as simulations or machine learning. There are also gaps related to the instruments considered, since modern instruments such as fast payments are seldom addressed.

The studies that comprise this thesis aim at contributing to fill some of these gaps, using BIS' Red Book data that include countries from five continents from 2005 to 2020 (Bank for International Settlements, 2018) and considering fast payments (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016) in the second study (chapter 3). Data from a survey with Brazilian payers and merchants is employed in the third (chapter 4), fourth (chapter 5) and fifth studies (chapter 6) on the determinants of choice of payment instruments, using traditional econometric techniques, machine learning techniques and an agent-based model to verify the applicability of a cash management theory to the Brazilian case, respectively.

1.1 Theme

A good retail payments infrastructure is important because it favors commerce and the economic interactions among the many agents in the economy and it also contributes to increase confidence among consumers (Hasan et al., 2014). Rysman & Schuh (2017) mention that payments in general have always been central to the efficient functioning of the markets and have always been subject to public policies.

All over the world, the sector has witnessed deep changes with impacts that still need evaluation. Mobile payments and digital wallets solutions, many of them based on payment card and offered by fintechs or big techs such as PayPal, Apple Pay and Google Pay, are becoming ever more popular and showing that the market can still move forward (Rysman & Schuh, 2017). In the cards market, many countries capped interchange fees, owed by acquirers to issuers, in the attempt to stimulate electronization and reduce payment costs (Górka, 2018). Conveniences have been offered by many market participants, such as bracelets and adhesives, as well as the possibility of contactless and PIN-less payments. Cryptocurrencies also proliferated in the last decade, even though their impact on payments seem to be limited (Bank for International Settlements, 2022). There is now a heated debate around the emission of Central Bank Digital Currencies - CBDCs (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2018; Auer & Böhme, 2020).

But one can argue that the main development in the retail payments infrastructure was the introduction of fast or instant payments solutions (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016; Rysman & Schuh, 2017), such as Pix in Brazil. The best example maybe comes from China, where AliPay and WeChat Pay solutions dominate large portions of the retail payments market.

In Brazil specifically, in line with the electronization of payments pursued by the regulator, besides the capping of debit cards interchange fees in 2018, there was, for example, the end of an exclusivity agreement among card networks and acquirers in 2009, the possibility of price differentiation based on payment instrument in 2016, the increase in competition in the payment cards sector with the entrance of new actors, including new issuers such as Nubank, new acquirers such as Stone and even new networks such as Elo, with impacts still to be determined in full (Bogossian, 2019; Perez & Bruschi, 2018).

In relation to other payment instruments, there were reductions in fees charged by messages in the STR (Sistema de Transferência de Reservas, the Brazilian Real-Time Gross Settlement payment system), contributing to the offering of unlimited and free of charge credit transfers by fintechs such as Nubank and PagSeguro. Boletos (credit transfers settled in D+1) started to be registered one by one, allowing more safety and convenience to users, cheques started to be settled in one day electronically, allowing for more efficiency and convenience to the instrument, with the settlement by photo, for

example.

Thus, the retail payments sector is dynamic and is in constant evolution. Understanding what really influences the usage and choice of instruments is crucial to policies aimed at the adoption of new electronic instruments in line with regulators objectives.

1.2 Research problem

Previous studies identified determinants of usage and choice of payment instruments in different contexts, but the countries considered were generally restricted to certain relatively homogeneous regions and the instruments considered in most of the situations were restricted to cash, payment cards and older instruments.

Thus, my research question is: what are the factors that influence the usage and choice of retail payment instruments, considering different contexts?

1.3 Objectives

The general objective of the thesis is to identify determinants of usage and choice of retail payment instruments. The specific objectives are:

- Identify research gaps on the retail payments theme;
- Identify determinants of usage of electronic payment instruments;
- Identify determinants of usage of instant payments;
- Identify determinants of choice of retail payment instruments.

1.4 Hypotheses systems

The hypotheses of the thesis, developed in study two (chapter 3), are the following, related to electronic payments:

- H3.1a: Better technological infrastructure is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.2a: Better levels of economic and institutional development are associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.3a: Expansionist monetary policy is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.4a: Lower tax burden is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.5a: Lower proportion of elderly in the population is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.6a: The level of usage of electronic payments is persistent.

The hypotheses on fast payments, also developed in study two (chapter 3), are the following:

- H3.1b: Better technological infrastructure is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.2b: Better levels of economic and institutional development are associated with more fast payments.
- H3.3b: Expansionist monetary policy is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.4b: Lower tax burden is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.5b: Lower proportion of elderly in the population is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.6b: The level of usage of fast payments is persistent.

The hypotheses on determinants of choice of electronic payments, developed on study three (chapter 4) and four (chapter 5), are the following:

- H4.1a: Payers' gender is a determinant of their choice of electronic instruments.
- H4.2a: Younger payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.3a: Higher income payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.4a: More educated payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.5a: Payers from more urbanized and developed regions are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.6a: Payers' marital status is a determinant of the choice of electronic instruments.
- H4.7a: The employment status of payers is a determinant of the choice of electronic instruments.
- H4.8a: Payers who receive their main source of income on account are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.9a: Payers who have experienced cell phone shopping are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.10a: Payers who have an account with a financial or payment institution are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.1b: The probability that electronic instruments are chosen is higher for higher value purchases.
- H4.2b: The sector in which the establishment or payee operates is a determinant of instrument choice.
- H4.3b: The type of establishment or payment is the determinant of the choice of instrument.
- H4.4b: The payment condition is a determinant of the choice of payment instrument.

The hypotheses on determinants of choice postulated on study five (chapter 6), are the following:

- H6.1: the cash-first optimal choice theory is applicable to Brazilian payers.
- H6.2: an extension of the the cash-first optimal choice theory that considers a cash-like instrument is applicable to Brazilian payers.

1.5 Justification

The thesis' academic justification rests on its addressing of a topic of growing interest in the literature, although it is not as frequently explored as other themes. The proposition of a research agenda with gaps to be fulfilled can contribute to stimulate new research on the field.

Institutionally, the studies can be of interest both to market participants, that can employ my results as inputs to investment decisions in infrastructure and marketing needed to spur the adoption of innovative electronic instruments, and to regulators, that can make use of the results as inputs to the development of public policies and regulations aimed to stimulate the electronization of payments or the implementation of modern payment instruments.

1.6 Contributions

The thesis identifies, on study one (chapter 2) research gaps on the retail payments field, pointing out a possible research agenda. It also fulfills some of these gaps, employing in the second study (chapter 3) a wide sample of countries that includes emerging markets and countries from five continents. It also considers a recent payment instrument (instant payments). In the third study (chapter 4), I also try to fulfill the gap on emerging countries data, since I employ Brazilian survey data in an econometric analysis on electronic payments' determinants of choice. In study four (chapter 5), I try to fulfill a gap related to alternative techniques, since I employ machine learning methods to explain payment instrument choice. Finally, in the fifth study (chapter 6), I also try to fulfill the gap on alternative techniques, employing an agent-based model to investigate the applicability of a cash management theory to the Brazilian case.

The employment of data on a wide sample of countries, not often used in the context of the second study, together with new payments diaries data of a large emerging country (studies three, four and five) and with the utilization of techniques not commonly used in this field (studies four and five), can contribute with the research on a relevant and important theme, associated with a dynamic and innovative sector, subject to regulators' interest in stimulating developments that favor competition, efficiency and improvement of the population's well-being when it comes to retail payments utilization.

1.7 Limitations

On the bibliometric analysis, the criteria chosen to search the data bases are crucial to the composition of the sample of the articles, and subtle changes in the them can lead to significant changes in the identified articles. The criteria employed to code and classify the articles are also subjective.

In the determinants of usage analysis, payment data employed is consolidated by the Bank for International Settlements, since they come from different countries, but it is possible that differences in interpretation by information supplier may hamper comparison. Other determinants not considered could also be important.

The data employed in studies three to five, comprise only one country and year, what may limit the reach of conclusions. Besides that, some of the information employed in other studies on the same subject are not present in the survey used and that could be important determinants of choice, such as the acceptance of the instruments by payees or the amount of cash a payer had at the moment of the payments recorded.

1.8 Structure and organization

Study one (chapter 2) presents a bibliometric analysis of the literature and research gaps on retail payments. Study two (chapter 3) focuses on determinants of usage of electronic and fast payments, employing data from 2005 to 2020 of a wider sample of countries in a dynamic panel analysis. Study three (chapter 4) investigates with traditional econometric techniques the determinants of choice of electronic payments, employing new payment diaries data from a 2019 Brazilian survey. Study four (chapter 5) explains payment instruments choice using the same data employed in study three, but with machine learning techniques. Finally, study five (chapter 6) investigates if a cash management theory is applicable to the data employed in the two previous studies with the use of an agent-based model. Chapter 7 presents the final considerations of the thesis.

2 Retail Payment Instruments: Bibliometric Analysis from 1995 to 2021

2.1 Introduction

Payments are central to the efficient functioning of markets, and payment instruments (methods for transferring resources) have been the subject of numerous innovations over time (Rysman & Schuh, 2017). While cash is still the most widely used payment instrument virtually everywhere in the world, electronic payment instruments, both existing ones such as payment cards and newer ones such as instant payments and e-wallets, have been gaining ground (Bech et al., 2018). The search for efficiency, in terms of cost, speed, convenience, security, and other attributes, has spurred not only the market to offer new solutions, but also regulators to act (Committee on Payment and Settlement Systems, 2012), trying to mitigate market distortions and encouraging the electronization of payment methods. Thus, understanding what has been the subject of researchers in the past and what aspects still deserve attention can help direct research on the subject in order to inform regulatory or market interventions that make it easier for regulators to achieve their desired goals.

This study presents a review of the literature on payment instruments in order to suggest an academic research agenda on the subject. Researchers on the subject have been trying to identify the determinants of the use of the various instruments, both from a microeconomic perspective (i.e., how payers choose their instrument) and also from a macroeconomic perspective (how environmental and economic variables influence the use of these instruments). Specific attributes of the instruments are also the subject of research, such as acceptance, adoption, efficiency, cost, and security. The history of various instruments is also of interest, as well as regulatory issues. The relationship between retail payments and economic activity, either by attempting to predict activity growth through timely retail payments data or by explaining activity as a function of certain characteristics of the retail payments ecosystem in different countries, is also addressed.

Thus, this study creates a sample of articles related to retail payments in the Scopus and Web of Science databases, classifies and codes characteristics of the articles, summarizes the contribution of each article, and identifies the most relevant gaps in the discussion on the subject. Section 2.2 presents the theoretical framework on the subject; section 2.3 describes the methodology; and section 2.4 presents the classification employed in the paper. Section 2.5 presents an overview of the literature on retail payments. Section 2.6 presents the results of the analysis and section 2.7 presents final considerations.

2.2 Theoretical framework

Retail payments are transactions related to the purchase of goods and services by consumers and businesses (Committee on Payment and Settlement Systems, 2012). The topic is embedded in a broader context of payment systems in general, which includes not only retail payments, but also high-value payments and transactions with securities and financial assets. They differ from high-value, usually interbank, transactions in that they are used in more varied situations (such as for point-of-sale transactions, remotely via the internet, or between people, for example), that they can generally be executed by a wider variety of instruments, and that they are settled in mostly privately operated systems. They constitute the bulk of payments by number, although they are a small fraction of total payments by value.

A good retail payments infrastructure is important because it fosters trade and economic interactions between different agents in the economy and contributes to raising consumer confidence (Hasan et al., 2014). Rysman & Schuh (2017) mention that payments in general have always been central to the efficient functioning of markets and have always been subject to government policies. Another aspect that requires central banks' attention in relation to retail payments is their role in maintaining financial stability and financial system efficiency and their role in preserving currency reliability (Committee on Payment and Settlement Systems, 2012).

Kahn & Roberds (2009) propose a theory in which they define a payment system as any arrangement that allows overcoming frictions of time mismatch and limited enforcement. Payment economics would be the study of such arrangements, with antecedents in monetary theory, since it would be, in part, the study of the techniques that institutions use to raise the speed of transactions, making payments more efficient with the same stock of money.

Theories about specific instruments such as cash and cards have also been proposed in the literature. According to Boeschoten (1992), there are theories of the demand for money from both macroeconomic and microeconomic perspectives. Aspects of these theories could be extrapolated to treat other instruments directly or consider them as the complement of cash transactions. From a microeconomic point of view, the theory on the use and demand for money was originally proposed by Baumol (1952) and Tobin (1956) and refined and expanded over the years. In macroeconomic terms, as mentioned by Kahn & Roberds (2009), Friedman's (1956) Quantitative Theory of the Demand for Money would be most related to the use of money in retail transactions. Applied mainly to cards (Baxter, 1983; Verdier, 2011), there is a vast literature on the two-sided market theory (Rochet, 2003; Rochet & Tirole, 2002, 2006).

2.3 Methodology

A structured literature review characterizes a research field, identifies emerging themes, points out research gaps and thus suggests avenues for future work. On the topic of retail payments, there is a lagging survey by Hancock & Humphrey (1998) and some surveys on specific topics, such as those by Rochet (2003) and Verdier (2011) on interchange fees (fees owed by acquirers to issuers in card payment arrangements) and that by Scholnick et al. (2008) on cards and ATMs. However, to the best of my knowledge, research on retail payments more broadly has not yet been addressed extensively in the past 20 years. Jabbour (2013) and other authors suggest the following steps for a literature review:

1. Conduct a search for articles published in the field in relevant databases;
2. Develop a classification model of the articles identified in the first step;
3. Apply the classification developed in the second step to the articles identified in the first step, developing an overview of the current discussion on the topic;
4. Present the main results concerning the literature on the topic, as well as the characteristics of the articles, taking into account the classification system developed in the second step;
5. Point out the gaps and suggest future research opportunities on the topic.

In order to create the sample of relevant articles, queries were made in the Scopus and Web of Science bases on November 15, 2021, using the keywords *retail payments*, searched in the keywords, title and abstract of the articles. There was no time limitation, but the subjects were restricted to *Economics, Econometrics and Finance, Social sciences, Business, Management and Accounting* and *Decision Sciences*, in the Scopus base, and *Economics, Management, Business Finance, Operations Research Management Science, Public Administration, Business* and *Social Sciences Mathematical Methods* in the Web of Science base. Articles in the final publication stage or in publication were considered, but only from English language journals. I obtained 97 articles from Scopus and 71 articles from the Web of Science. Of the 168 articles, 57 articles were listed in both databases, leaving 111 unique articles. Of these, it was not possible to obtain 8 articles, which were unavailable in full. 4 articles were excluded for being editorials, interviews or comments on other articles, 1 for being a book, 2 for being in a language other than English and 3 actually dealt with a subject unrelated to retail payments (telecommunications, energy or mergers and acquisitions), although the keywords matched the search. Thus, 93 articles remained in the sample.

Of the 93 articles in the sample, 41 were published in only 13 journals, as shown in Table 1. In total, articles were found in 65 journals, and in 52 journals only one article was

Table 1 – Articles per journal

Journal	Impact factor	Number of articles
Journal of Payments Strategy and Systems	0.000	9
Journal of Banking & Finance	2.205	8
Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	3.585	3
Review of Network Economics	0.080	3
Applied Economics	0.968	2
Applied Economics Letters	0.591	2
Business History	1.152	2
Contemporary Economic Policy	0.905	2
Economist-Netherlands	0.237	2
Journal of Business Research	4.028	2
Journal of Financial Services Research	1.667	2
Journal of Money Credit and Banking	1.782	2
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	3.815	2
Other	1.047	52
Total	1.219	93

Note: Author's elaboration. Impact factor, as per Clarivate Analytics (2019), calculated as the weighted average of impact factors by the number of articles for "Other" and "Total" and zero for unlisted journals.

Figure 1 – Articles per year. Source: elaborated by the author.

published, showing that research in the area is dispersed. The articles were published in journals with an average impact factor of 1.219. Conservatively, the impact factor of the 24 journals that do not have *Journal Citation Reports* (Clarivate Analytics, 2019) rankings was taken as zero. This indicates that research on the means of payment industry finds space in journals of reasonable impact.

The distribution by years displayed in Figure 1 shows that most research is relatively recent, following the growth in the use of electronic payment instruments, such as debit and credit cards.

2.4 Classification

As mentioned in section 2.3, the classification structure follows the methodology proposed by Jabbour (2013) and also implemented by Silva et al. (2017), among others. Table 2 presents how each article in the sample is classified according to the criteria scheme proposed below:

1. Type of study: 1A - Theoretical, 1B - Empirical, and 1C - Both. Editorials were not considered.
2. Approach: 2A - Quantitative, 2B - Qualitative, and 2C - Descriptive.
3. Object of study: 3A - Relationship between retail payments and economic activity, 3B - Security/fraud in payment instruments, 3C - Acceptance of payment instruments, 3D - Adoption of payment instruments, 3E - Cost of payment instruments, 3F - Prediction of economic activity, 3G - Micro use determinants, 3H - Macro use determinants, 3I - Financial stability, 3J - Industrial organization, 3K - Technology adoption, 3L - Monetary policy, 3M - Benefits of use, 3N - Convergence, 3O - Regulation, 3P - History, and 3Q - Other. Each article can have more than one object of study.
4. Scope: 4A - Region or block, 4B - One country, 4C - More than one country, 4D - Not applicable or not specified, and 4E - World.
5. Context: 5A - Developed country, 5B - Emerging country, 5C - Both, and 5D - Not applicable or not specified.
6. Focus: 6A - Wire transfers/credit transfers/electronic transfers, 6B Cards/payment cards/electronic payments, 6C - Prepaid cards/value storage cards, 6D - Digital money/electronic cash, 6E - Mobile money/mobile payments, 6F - Digital wallet/Paypal, 6G - Payment systems, 6H - Financial services, 6I - Contactless cards, 6J - Payment accounts, 6K - Fast payments, 6L - Credit cards, 6M - Debit cards, 6N - Direct debit, 6O - ATM networks, 6P - Smart cards, 6Q - Cash, 6R - Fintechs, 6S - RFID/NFC, 6T - Checks, 6U - Invoices, 6V - Other, 6W - Banks, 6X - EFTPOS, and 6Y - CBDC. Each article can have more than one focus.
7. 7A - Not applicable or not specified, 7B - Up to 2 years, 7C - More than 10 years, 7D - 5 to 10 years, and 7E - 2 to 5 years.
8. Type of data: 8A - From regulators, Financial Market Infrastructures (FMIs) or other agencies, 8B - Not applicable or not specified, 8C - Retailer/acquirer/financial institution, 8D - Balance sheets, 8E - Payment diary, 8F - Survey/interview, 8G - Experiment, 8H - Simulations, and 8I - Newspaper.
9. Methods: 9A - Mathematical modeling, 9B - Econometric/statistical/multivariate analysis, 9C - Case study, and 9D - Not applicable or not specified.
10. Techniques: 10A - Factor analysis/Confirmatory factor analysis, 10B - Not appli-

cable or not specified, 10C - Heckman selection model, 10D - Time series analysis, 10E - Panel data analysis, 10F - Sigma or beta convergence, 10G - Multinomial Logit/Probit, 10H - Descriptive statistics, 10I - Ordered Logit/Probit, 10J - Mathematical modeling, 10K - Comparison of means, 10L Logit/probit/cloglog, 10M - Poisson regression, 10N - Cluster analysis, 10O - Network analysis, 10P - Other, 10Q - Principal Component Analysis (PCA), 10R - Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), and 10S - GMM. Each article can employ more than one technique.

Table 2 – Sample articles

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Gomber et al. (2018)	1A	2C	3P, 3K	4E	5C	6R	7C	8B	9D	10H	145	29.00
Szmigin & Foxall (1998)	1B	2B	3D	4B	5A	6M, 6L, 6V, 6T, 6Q	7A	8F	9D	10P	116	4.64
Humphrey, Kim & Vale (2001)	1B	2A, 2C	3G, 3E	4B	5A	6Q, 6T, 6M	7D	8F	9B	10E, 10H	69	3.14
Drehmann, Goodhart & Krueger (2002)	1B	2A	3H	4C	5A	6Q, 6D, 6L, 6M	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10H	57	2.71
Zinman (2009)	1B	2A	3G, 3E	4B	5A	6M, 6L	7C	8F	9B	10L, 10R, 10M	55	3.93
Bolt, Jonker & Van (2010)	1B	2A	3C, 3E, 3J	4B	5A	6Q, 6M	7B	8F	9B	10I, 10H	48	3.69
Jonker (2007)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6M, 6L, 6V	7B	8F	9B	10I, 10H	43	2.69
Simon, Smith & West (2010)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6T, 6V	7B	8F, 8E	9B	10L, 10H, 10R	36	2.77
Arango, Huynh & Sabetti (2015)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6M, 6L	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10G, 10H	35	4.38
Stavins (2001)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6A, 6N, 6T	7B	8F	9B	10L, 10H	35	1.59
Hasan, Schmiedel & Song (2012)	1B	2A	3Q	4A	5A	6W	7D	8A	9B	10E, 10R, 10H	28	2.55
Berentsen (1998)	1A	2A, 2C	3L	4C	5A	6D, 6Q, 6P	7A	8B	9A	10H	21	0.84
Jun & Yeo (2016)	1A	2A	3J	4D	5D	6R	7A	8B	9A	10J, 10H	19	2.71
Chiu (2017)	1A	2C	3O, 3P	4C	5A	6G, 6R	7C	8B	9D	10B	18	3.00
Grueschow, Kemper & Brettel (2016)	1B	2A	3E, 3Q	4D	5B	6U, 6L, 6F, 6V	7B	8C	9B	10R, 10H	18	2.57
Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	1B	2A	3H	4A	5A	6B	7C	8E, 8F	9B	10L, 10E, 10H	17	2.43
Batiz-Lazo (2009)	1A	2C	3P	4B	5A	6O	7C	8B	9D	10H	16	1.14
Milne (2006)	1A	2A, 2C	3J, 3K	4C	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T, 6A, 6N	7B	8A	9A	10J, 10H	15	0.88
Bounie, Francois & Van (2017)	1B	2A	3G, 3H, 3C	4B	5A	6B	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10L, 10H	14	2.33
Arango, Hogg & Lee (2015)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6T, 6C	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10L, 10H	14	1.75
Chakravorti (2010)	1A	2C	3O, 3J	4E	5C	6Q, 6B, 6T	7A	8B	9D	10B	14	1.08
Martikainen, Schmiedel & Takalo (2015)	1B	2A	3N, 3H	4A	5A	6Q, 6M, 6L, 6N, 6A, 6T, 6D	7C	8A	9B	10R, 10H, 10F, 10D, 10S	11	1.38
Trutsch (2016)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6T, 6M, 6L, 6C, 6E	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10L, 10H	10	1.43
Kosse (2013)	1B	2A	3H, 3B	4B	5A	6M	7E	8A, 8I	9B	10D, 10R, 10H	9	0.90
Gulbourg & Segendorff (2007)	1B	2A, 2C	3E	4B	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T, 6A, 6N	7B	8D	9B	10H	9	0.56
Hernandez, Jonker & Kosse (2017)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6M	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10I, 10H	8	1.33
Carbo, Chakravorti & Rodriguez (2016)	1B	2A	3H, 3D, 3C	4B	5A	6L, 6M	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10S, 10H	8	1.14
Krivosheya & Korolev (2016)	1B	2A	3G, 3M	4B	5B	6B	7B	8F, 8H	9B	10K, 10C, 10H	8	1.14
Polasik, Wisniewski & Lightfoot (2012)	1B	2A	3K	4B	5B	6I, 6M, 6S	7A	8F	9B	10I, 10A, 10H	8	0.73
Abdul-Muhmin (2010)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5B	6Q, 6M, 6L	7B	8F	9B	10K, 10H	8	0.62
Krivosheya & Korolev (2018)	1B	2A	3C	4B	5B	6B	7B	8F	9B	10K, 10C, 10H	7	1.40
Chen, Felt & Huynh (2017)	1B	2A	3G, 3D	4B	5A	6Q, 6B, 6I, 6C	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10E, 10L, 10H	7	1.17
Patacchini & Rainone (2017)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6L, 6J, 6H	7C	8F	9B	10R, 10P, 10Q, 10O, 10H	7	1.17

Table 2 – Sample articles (continued)

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Fujiki & Tanaka (2014)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6D	7B	8E, 8F	9B	10R, 10H, 10P	7	0.78
Jonker (2011)	1B	2A	3C, 3J	4B	5A	6M, 6L	7B	8F	9B	10C	7	0.58
Kraenzlin, Meyer & Nellen (2020)	1B	2A	3H	4B	5A	6B, 6Q	7B	8C	9B	10P, 10H	6	2.00
Deufel, Kemper & Brettel (2019)	1B	2A	3G	4A	5A	6L, 6F, 6U, 6A, 6Q	7B	8C	9B	10G, 10H	6	1.50
Lee, Hong & Min (2019)	1B	2A	3D	4B	5B	6V	7B	8F	9B	10P, 10A	6	1.50
Fujiki & Tanaka (2018)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6B	7D	8E, 8F	9B	10G, 10H	6	1.20
Deungoue (2008)	1B	2A	3N, 3H, 3O	4A	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T, 6A, 6N	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10F, 10H, 10S	6	0.40
Bolt (2006)	1A	2A, 2C	3E	4B	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T	7A	8A	9A	10J, 10H	6	0.35
Swiecka, Terefenko & Paprotny (2021)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5B	6Q, 6B, 6I, 6E, 6A, 6F	7B	8F	9B	10P, 10H, 10K	5	2.50
Zhang et al. (2019)	1B	2A	3H, 3A	4A	5A	6Q, 6T, 6B, 6A, 6N	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10H	5	1.25
Karoubi, Chenavaz & Paraschiv (2016)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T	7B	8F	9B	10P, 10H	5	0.71
Consoli (2008)	1A	2C	3P	4B	5A	6O, 6X	7C	8B	9D	10H	5	0.33
Fujiki (2020)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q	7D	8F	9B	10P, 10L, 10K	4	1.33
Camera, Casari & Bortolotti (2016)	1C	2A	3G	4D	5D	6Q, 6B	7A	8G	9B	10P, 10L, 10J, 10H	4	0.57
Silva, Ramalho & Vieira (2016)	1B	2A	3H	4A	5A	6A, 6B, 6T, 6N	7D	8A	9B	10L, 10H	4	0.57
Harasim & Klimontowicz (2013)	1B	2C	3G, 3D	4B	5B	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6C, 6N, 6E, 6I	7B	8F	9D	10H	4	0.40
Krivosheya (2020)	1B	2A, 2B	3G, 3M	4B	5B	6B	7E	8F	9B	10P, 10C	3	1.00
Krivosheya (2020)	1B	2A	3G, 3K, 3D	4B	5B	6B, 6F, 6E, 6I	7B	8F	9B	10L, 10I, 10H, 10Q, 10C	3	1.00
Korau et al. (2019)	1B	2A	3B	4B	5B	6B	7B	8F	9B	10A, 10P, 10H	3	0.75
Yoon & Jun (2019)	1A	2A	3B, 3E	4D	5D	6R	7A	8B	9A	10J	3	0.75
Batiz-Lazo & Del (2018)	1A	2C	3P, 3D	4C	5C	6B	7C	8B	9D	10H	3	0.60
Korella & Li (2018)	1B	2C, 2A	3D, 3G, 3H	4C	5C	6Q, 6B, 6A, 6T, 6N, 6E, 6K	7B	8F, 8A	9B	10H	3	0.60
Sinha & Adhikari (2018)	1A	2A	3D	4D	5D	6C	7A	8B	9A	10J	3	0.60
Iman (2020)	1B	2C	3K, 3D, 3N	4C	5B	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6C, 6T, 6A, 6N	7A	8F, 8A	9C	10H	2	0.67
Semerikova (2020)	1B	2A	3G, 3K, 3B	4B	5B	6B, 6F, 6E, 6I	7B	8F	9B	10C, 10L, 10H	2	0.67
Callado-Munoz, Hromcova & Utrero-Gonzalez (2012)	1B	2A	3G	4A	5A	6Q, 6B	7C	8A	9B	10E	2	0.18
Polasik et al. (2010)	1B	2A	3Q	4B	5B	6Q, 6B, 6E, 6I, 6S, 6E	7B	8C, 8F	9B	10P, 10H	2	0.15
Shabgard (2021)	1A	2A	3E, 3J	4A	5A	6B, 6A, 6N	7A	8B	9A	10J	1	0.50
Fujiki (2020)	1B	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6L, 6M, 6D, 6V	7D	8F	9B	10G, 10H	1	0.33
Maixe-Altes (2020)	1A	2C	3P, 3D	4C	5A	6B	7C	8A	9D	10H	1	0.33
Yawe & Kiwala (2019)	1B	2C	3D	4D	5D	6K, 6G	7A	8B	9D	10B	1	0.25
Callado-Munoz, Hromcova & Utrero-Gonzalez (2018)	1B	2A	3H	4C	5B	6Q, 6B	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10H	1	0.20
Folwarski (2018)	1A	2C	3O, 3P	4B	5B	6G	7D	8B	9D	10H	1	0.20

Table 2 – Sample articles (continued)

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Palm (2018)	1A	2C	3P	4E	5C	6V	7C	8B	9D	10B	1	0.20
Krueger (2017)	1A	2C	3P, 3H	4B	5A	6Q	7C	8B	9D	10H	1	0.17
Silva, Ramalho & Vieira (2017)	1B	2A	3H	4A	5A	6T	7C	8A	9B	10E, 10L, 10H, 10M	1	0.17
Marshall & Coke (2016)	1B	2A	3A	4B	5B	6B	7D	8A	9B	10D, 10H, 10P, 10R	1	0.14
Hromcova, Callado-Munoz & Utrero-Gonzalez (2014)	1C	2A	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6B, 6T	7C	8A	9B	10J, 10H	1	0.11
Lee, Loke & Tan (2013)	1B	2A	3D	4B	5B	6V, 6L, 6M, 6D, 6V, 6V	7B	8F	9B	10P, 10H, 10H	1	0.10
Wright (2002)	1B	2A, 2C	3G	4B	5A	6Q, 6L, 6T, 6X	7A	8F	9B	10R, 10H	1	0.05
Birch (2020)	1B	2C	3P, 3D, 3B	4C	5A	6D, 6Y	7C	8B	9C	10H	0	0.00
Bossone, Srinivas & Banka (2020)	1B	2C	3O, 3P, 3J	4C	5C	6G, 6R, 6Y	7C	8A	9D	10H	0	0.00
Buckley & Balakrishnan (2020)	1B	2C	3D, 3Q	4C	5C	6K, 6G	7B	8F	9B	10H	0	0.00
Kemppainen (2020)	1B	2C	3P, 3O	4A	5A	6B, 6A, 6N, 6T	7A	8A	9D	10H	0	0.00
Kumar et al. (2020)	1B	2C	3P, 3O	4B	5B	6Q, 6B, 6T, 6K, 6G	7C	8B	9D	10B	0	0.00
Liao & Yang (2020)	1B	2A	3G, 3K, 3D	4B	5B	6E	7B	8F	9B	10N, 10P	0	0.00
Natarajan & Balakrishnan (2020)	1B	2C	3D	4D	5D	6K	7A	8B	9D	10B	0	0.00
Sahabat et al. (2019)	1B	2A	3I	4B	5B	6G	7C	8A	9B	10O, 10P, 10H	0	0.00
Scheja & Machielse (2019)	1B	2C	3O, 3J	4A	5A	6H, 6W, 6R	7A	8B	9D	10B	0	0.00
Soukal & Draessler (2019)	1B	2A	3G, 3D	4B	5B	6J	7D	8C	9B	10N, 10H	0	0.00
León & Ortega (2018)	1B	2A	3F	4B	5B	6A, 6T	7C	8A	9B	10P, 10H	0	0.00
Sabetti et al. (2018)	1B	2A	3Q, 3I	4B	5A	6G	7C	8A	9B	10P, 10P, 10H	0	0.00
Repousis (2016)	1A	2C	3Q, 3P, 3O	4B	5A	6G	7A	8B	9D	10H	0	0.00
Conesa et al. (2015)	1B	2A	3F	4B	5A	6L, 6M, 6T, 6C, 6A, 6N	7D	8A	9B	10D, 10H	0	0.00
Kopsakangas-Savolainen & Takalo (2014)	1A	2A, 2C	3O, 3J	4B	5A	6O	7A	8B	9B	10J, 10H	0	0.00
Ariguzo & White (2013)	1B	2A	3D	4B	5B	6E	7B	8F	9B	10K, 10H	0	0.00
Kaur & Kaur (2013)	1B	2A	3K	4B	5B	6P, 6B	7D	8D	9B	10K, 10H	0	0.00
Berentsen (2005)	1A	2A, 2C	3L	4C	5A	6D, 6Q	7A	8B	9A	10J, 10H	0	0.00
Ashton & Boyes (2002)	1B	2C	3O, 3J	4B	5A	6G	7C	8B	9D	10B	0	0.00
Möker & Friederich (1996)	1A	2C	3J, 3O	4A	5A	6G	7A	8B	9D	10B	0	0.00

Note: Prepared by the author. Articles ordered from the most recent to the oldest. Columns 1 to 10 correspond to the 10 criteria presented in section 2.4 (1 - study type, 2 - approach, 3 - study object, 4 - scope, 5 - context, 6 - focus, 7 - period, 8 - data type, 9 - method, 10 - technique); 11 - total number of citations; 12 - citations per year.

2.5 Retail payments research overview

This section presents an overview of retail payments research based on the classification of articles by research object, which will be summarized in section 2.6. This criterion best describes the general literature in the area.

2.5.1 Determinants of choice

In this line of research, which presents the largest number of papers, the studies try to identify the determinants of the use of payment instruments from a microeconomic point of view, i.e., they try to identify the determinants of the choice of payment instruments by payers. The studies generally employ surveys and payment diaries, mostly provided by central banks. Transaction data provided by retailers are also used in some studies.

The studies generally regress the instrument chosen by payers against explanatory variables that characterize the payers, such as demographic variables (age, gender, education, etc.), economic variables (income, type of employment relationship, etc.), purchase characteristics (value, type of establishment, type of good consumed, etc.), perception of instruments (for example, through scores assigned to the instruments for various attributes), etc. The techniques employed are basically logit (or probit) and its extensions and variations, such as the multinomial logit when modeling the choice of several instruments and not just two classes (in general, electronic/non-electronic).

The results generally indicate that demographic variables are important, with older people and people with lower education and income sticking more to cash, while younger people, and those with higher education and income, use electronic payment instruments more often. The choice of electronic instruments generally increases with the value of the transaction, while cash is the preferred medium for lower value payments. Cash is the instrument perceived as the least costly, fastest at the point of sale, easiest to use, and most accepted.

One of the gaps refers to the relative scarcity of work involving emerging countries. Another gap concerns techniques. There are few works that apply alternative techniques such as machine learning, such as Shy (2019) and Świecka et al. (2021), or simulation, such as that employed by Arango et al. (2014). Finally, the difficulty of accessing data of significant volume of real transactions with various instruments, including money, hampers the development of studies in this line of research and is a well-known limitation (Humphrey, 2010; Kahn & Roberds, 2009).

2.5.2 Determinants of usage

This line of research tries to identify the determinants of the use of the various payment instruments from a macroeconomic point of view, that is, what macroeconomic and environmental characteristics determine the composition of the basket of retail payment instruments used by payers. Papers generally employ aggregate data, regressing transaction quantities and values of the various instruments on variables such as interest rates, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, crime index, financial market competition, tax level, and others. Since the quantity and value of transactions with money are not available, proxies such as paper money held by the public or the value of household consumption minus the value of transactions with electronic instruments and cheques, for example, are used. Panel data and logit analysis are the most commonly employed techniques and the results point to a greater use of electronic instruments with higher interest rates (due to the opportunity cost of keeping cash), with a higher level of competition among financial and payment institutions (which stimulates alternative instruments), with lower tax levels (which discourage the shadow economy and tax evasion), with a higher crime rate (which increases the risk of losing money to theft) and with greater technological development (a general prerequisite for electronic payments, proxies are usually the number of ATMs and POS).

The gaps are similar to the previous section: there are few works with emerging countries or with alternative techniques. In addition, there are few works with newer payment instruments, such as cryptocurrencies, instant payments or central bank digital currencies (Central Bank Digital Currency - CBDC), for example.

2.5.3 Specific attributes of retail payment instruments

Papers in this line of research are more heterogeneous but have in common the study of specific aspects of retail payment instruments, such as acceptance, efficiency, cost, adoption and security, for example. In general, the papers use data from consumer interviews, but the techniques are more varied (e.g. chronography in Polasik et al. (2010)) and Kirton's adaptation-innovation inventory in Szmigin & Foxall (1998)). Some works are theoretical. Regarding adoption, whether of instruments or technologies, papers conclude that demographic factors are important, with younger and more educated users among the pioneers. Card acceptance is evaluated as beneficial to consumers and carriers, and cost is identified as an important variable for acceptance and use.

As for gaps, few papers involve emerging countries. Studies on newer instruments such as cryptocurrencies and instant payments are also still uncommon, as is the use of alternative techniques.

2.5.4 History and regulation

Papers in this line of research present the history of aspects related to retail payment instruments and describe how various regulatory interventions have impacted the instruments. Most of the work is descriptive or theoretical, but there is also empirical work on the impacts of regulation.

Market failures make electronic instruments, that regulators aim to encourage, expensive and have led to regulatory interventions aimed at cheapening the cost for merchants and consumers. Incentives for new instruments, such as instant payments, have also been created by the relevant authorities, with central banks even going as far as offering the services to end users, as in Mexico (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016).

The main recent regulatory interventions have focused on payment cards, in particular debit cards, which are considered more efficient and capable of delivering more welfare to society than credit cards, for example. Several countries have set caps on interchange fees, required greater transparency in the setting and reporting of prices and fees, and abolished rules that prevented differentiation in the prices of products and services depending on the payment instrument used to make the purchase. The main gaps also concern the few works on emerging countries and the scarcity of works employing quantitative techniques to analyze the subject.

2.5.5 Economic activity and monetary policy

In this line of research there are papers on timely forecasting (nowcasting) of economic activity using retail payments data and papers on the effect of certain characteristics of retail payments on economic activity. The studies generally use Financial Market Infrastructures operators' data such as the quantity and value of individual retail payment transactions as predictors or determinants of economic activity. The papers conclude that retail payments are related to economic activity and can be employed to predict it.

Here too there are few papers employing alternative techniques, for example machine learning as used by León & Ortega (2018). Newer instruments such as instant payments are also not analyzed.

2.5.6 Industrial organization, two-sided market, and interchange fee

This line of research explores issues in the industrial organization of the retail payments industry, with an emphasis on the two-sided market nature of part of the electronic instruments, mainly payment cards. Studies on interchange fees focus on this aspect of the

pricing structure of card payment arrangements. The main conclusion is that the interchange fee that maximizes the social optimum is different from the market interchange fee, so that without intervention, the social optimum is hardly achieved. Moreover, regulation is necessary to ensure adequate competition.

2.6 Literature review results

This section presents the result of the bibliometric analysis according to the methodology described in section 2.3 and the classification presented in section 2.4. The analysis was conducted with the aid of the Bibliometrix package (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017) of the R tool (R Core Team, 2019).

2.6.1 Results by criterion

Regarding criterion 1 (type of study), most of the papers are empirical (70 studies). 21 are theoretical and 2 are theoretical and empirical. The theoretical works (or both) usually have as object history and regulation or industrial organization.

Regarding criterion 2 (approach), most papers (69 studies) employ a quantitative approach. Only 2 papers present a qualitative approach. Descriptive works (32 studies), in turn, generally have history, regulation, and industrial organization as their object of study. Each study may present more than one approach.

Table 3 – Number of articles per object type

Object	Number of articles
Determinants of choice	32
Payment instrument adoption	19
Determinants of usage	14
History	14
Regulation	12
Industrial organization	11
Technology adoption	8
Payment instrument costs	8
Payment instrument acceptance	5
Security/fraud in payment instruments	5
Convergence in usage	3
Other	6
Total	137

Note: Author's elaboration. Each article can have more than one object.

Table 3 presents the classification of the articles according to criterion 3, object of the study. This was the criterion used to present in section 2.5 the overview of the research on payment instruments. Most of the papers (46) try to identify the determinants of the use of the various payment instruments, either from the perspective of consumer/payer

choice (microeconomic approach, with 32 articles), or from the perspective of the economic and environmental conditions that affect the use of the instruments (macroeconomic approach, with 14 articles). Specific attributes of retail payment instruments, such as adoption of a given instrument (19 articles), cost (8 articles), acceptance (5 articles), security and fraud (5 articles), speed (1 article), and reliability (1 article), are the second most frequent object of study, totaling 39 articles. History (14 articles) and regulation (12 articles) are the next most studied objects. These articles are generally theoretical and descriptive, without employing a quantitative approach. Aspects related to the industrial organization of the sector (11 articles) also have room among the objects. Convergence of instruments use between countries (3 articles), economic activity forecasting (2 articles) based on payment instruments data, relationship between economic activity (2 articles), monetary policy (2 articles) and payment instruments are other prominent objects.

Regarding criterion 4 (scope), most of the studies (57 studies) analyze only one country, since data from several countries are more difficult to obtain and require more work for standardization and alignment. Only 3 studies have as scope countries from several regions of the world. The region or block analyzed (13 studies) is usually the European Union, whose member countries' data are standardized. There are also 13 papers that involve more than one country and 7 papers where the scope is not specified, or the criterion does not apply. Studies involving a broader spectrum of countries is another gap identified.

Regarding criterion 5 (context), most studies (55) address developed countries, with only 25 articles addressing developing countries and only 7 studies addressing both developed and emerging countries. The criterion is not applicable to 6 studies (or the context was not specified). The lack of studies involving emerging countries was one of the gaps already mentioned in section 2.5.

Table 4 presents the classification of articles according to criterion 6, focus. As can be seen, there are few papers on more modern instruments, such as mobile payments. For example, only four papers address fast or instant payments and only two other papers address CDBC. This was also one of the gaps identified in section 2.5.

Regarding criterion 7 (period), most of the papers (35) analyze a short period of up to five years. Of the articles whose period is not specified, or the criterion does not apply (20), most are of the theoretical type. Of those that study longer time frames (27 studies), most are either on the determinants of use or on history and regulation, primarily with data from regulators, FMIs, or other agencies in the case of determinants of use or without data in the case of history and regulation. 11 studies analyze a medium term, between 5 and 10 years.

Table 5 presents the classification of papers according to criterion 8, data type.

Table 4 – Number of articles per focus

Focus	Number of articles
Cash	41
Cards/payment cards/electronic payments	33
Cheques	24
Debit cards	23
Credit cards	22
Credit transfers/electronic transfers	15
Direct debit	13
Payment systems	11
Mobile money/mobile payments	10
Digital cash/electronic cash	8
Prepaid cards/value storage cards	7
Contactless cards	7
Fintechs	6
Digital wallet/Paypal	5
Fast payments	5
Other	29
Total	259

Note: Author's elaboration. Each article can have more than one object.

Most papers employ data from surveys or interviews (40), from payment diaries (10) or from retailers (5), used mainly by studies on determinants of choice. Data from regulators, FMIs, or other agencies (24) are employed primarily by studies on macroeconomic determinants of use. The papers where data are not employed (24) are primarily about history and regulation. It is also possible to identify that, due to the difficulty in obtaining data, there are few works with data from simulations and experiments or even from retailers.

Table 5 – Number of articles by data type

Type of data	Number of articles
Survey/interview	40
From regulators, Financial Market Infrastructures or other bodies	24
Not applicable or not specified	24
Payment diaries	10
Retailer/acquirer/financial institution	5
From balance sheets	2
Experiment	1
Newspapers	1
Simulations	1
Total	108

Note: Author's elaboration. Each article can employ more than one type of data.

Regarding criterion 9 (method), most of the papers (62) use econometric, statistical, or multivariate methods. The works where no methods are applied (21) are mostly descriptive and the 8 that employ mathematical modeling are theoretical.

Table 6 shows the classification of the articles according to criterion 10, technique. Descriptive statistics is the most used technique, although it is ancillary in most papers. Logit and its variations are employed in most of the papers on both microeconomic and

macroeconomic determinants of use and some papers on specific attributes of payment instruments. Mathematical modeling is employed mostly in the quantitative theoretical papers. Panel data analysis is employed in part of the work on macroeconomic determinants, but also on specific attributes. As already mentioned, alternative techniques such as machine learning and simulation are uncommon and constitute identified research gaps.

Table 6 – Number of articles per technique

Number of articles per technique	Number of articles
Descriptive statistics	74
Logit/probit/cloglog	14
Panel data analysis	11
Mathematical modeling	10
Ordinary Least Squares (OLS)	10
Not applicable or not specified	9
Comparison of means	7
Heckman selection model	6
Ordered Logit/Probit	5
Time series analysis	4
Multinomial Logit/Probit	4
Factor analysis/Confirmatory factor analysis	3
GMM	3
Other	19
Total	179

Note: Author's elaboration. Each article can employ more than one technique.

2.6.2 Co-citation networks

Figure 2 presents the co-citation network of the top 30 references, i.e., not necessarily the articles in the sample, but the top references cited by the articles in the sample. The size of the circles corresponds to the number of citations received by the reference among the articles in the sample. The network shows that there are three main clusters. The cluster shown in red, whose most cited articles are Klee (2008) (with 10 citations), Borzekowski et al. (2008) (with 13 citations), Ching & Hayashi (2010) (with 12 citations) and Schuh & Stavins (2010) (with 16 citations), represents articles dealing with determinants of choice. Simon et al. (2010) (part of the sample, with 6 citations) is also one of the papers in the cluster.

Rochet & Tirole (2006) (with 9 citations), Rochet & Tirole (2002) (with 15 citations), Rochet (2003) (with 13 citations) and Rysman (2007) (with 13 citations) are references of the cluster displayed in green, which mainly represents articles on industrial organization, two-sided market, and interchange fee.

Finally, the blue cluster represents articles whose object is the determinants of instrument use (both microeconomic and macroeconomic), represented mainly by Humphrey et al. (1996) (with 15 citations), which provides an extensive descriptive analysis of retail payments in developed countries and presents a model that relates the use of instruments

Reference co-citation network

Figure 2 – Co-citation network of references. Source: prepared by the author using the bibliometrix package (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

other than money to macroeconomic and environmental variables; by Humphrey et al. (2001) (part of the sample, with 14 citations), which attempts to establish the relationship between changes in instrument prices and consumer choice; and by Humphrey (2010) ((identified in the keyword search in the bases, but excluded from the sample because it is an editorial, with 9 citations. The object of study "determinants of use" dominates the analysis, since it concentrates 46 among the 147 object occurrences, considering both microeconomic and macroeconomic approaches.

Figure 3, in turn, shows the co-citation network of journals. Among the references, the most cited journals are the *Journal of Banking and Finance* and the *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, with 44 and 25 citations respectively, and together with the *Journal of Monetary Economics* (19 citations), the *American Economic Review* (23 citations), the *International Journal of Central Banking* (6 citations), the *Journal of Financial Services Research* (14 citations), *Journal of Political Economics* (15 citations) and *Econometrica* (21 citations), form the red cluster. They are mainly references on the determinants of the use of payment instruments, both microeconomic and macroeconomic, and on the attributes of payment instruments.

The blue cluster, represented mainly by the journals *RAND Journal of Economics* (12 citations), *Review of Network Economics* (31 citations), *Journal of Industrial Economics* (8 citations) and *International Journal of Industrial Organization* (12 citations),

Figure 3 – Co-citation network of journals. Source: prepared by the author using the bibliometrix package (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

carries references mainly on industrial organization, two-sided market, interchange fee, history and regulation of payment instruments and system.

2.6.3 Keyword co-occurrences

Figure 4 presents clusters of keywords “plus”, index terms automatically generated from the titles of cited articles (Clarivate Analytics, 2019), i.e., groups of words that tend to appear together as keywords in articles. "Cash" is the most cited keyword in the red cluster related primarily to "electronic payments," but also to "growth," "adoption," and "pay", among others, indicating that studies are devoted to investigating either the growth of economic activity or the growth of the use of cash or other instruments as substitutes for cash. The blue cluster suggests the study of economics related to the demand for credit or debit cards in the context of two-sided markets.

"Cost" is the keyword that occurs most often in the yellow cluster, associated with "economics," indicating that papers are devoted to studying cost as an attribute of payment instruments. A fourth cluster (green) suggests that they study usage by consumers.

Keyword Co-Occurrences

Figure 4 – Network of keyword co-occurrences. Source: prepared by the author using the bibliometric package (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

2.6.4 Most cited articles

Table 2 presents the articles in the sample, sorted by those that received the most total citations and by the number of citations per year. The first 10 articles concentrate 60.2% of the citations, with 20 articles receiving no citations, 12 of which published after 2018. This indicates that quality research on the subject is concentrated, and that there are articles that have sparked little interest from academia.

2.6.5 Collaboration network

Figure 5 shows that there are some collaborations involving more than 3 authors and several between a limited number of authors. Figure 6 shows the collaboration network between countries. USA, UK and Germany are the countries that collaborate the most with each other in research related to retail payments. That is, research is concentrated in developed countries, with few articles in isolated peripheral countries, where authors do not work together with researchers from developed countries.

2.7 Final considerations

This paper conducted a bibliometric analysis of studies on retail payments available in the Scopus and Web of Science databases. Interest in the theme, as measured by the

Authors' collaboration network

Figure 5 – Collaboration network between authors. Source: prepared by the author using the bibliometric package (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

Country collaboration network

Figure 6 – Collaboration network between countries. Source: prepared by the author using the bibliometric package (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

number of published articles, has been growing in recent years, with publications also in high-impact journals. Most of the studies are empirical, quantitative, on the determinants of the use of instruments (with both macroeconomic and microeconomic approaches), specific attributes of the instruments or industrial organization, have as their scope only one developed country, focus on cash and cards, analyze short periods of up to 2 years, use data from interviews or surveys, payment diaries or from FMIs and regulators, use statistical, econometric or multivariate analysis, and employ logit and its variations as a technique, in addition to descriptive statistics in an auxiliary way.

As major gaps, there are relatively few papers involving emerging countries, long-term analysis, alternative techniques such as machine learning and simulation, higher volume real transaction data, newer instruments such as mobile payments, instant payments and CBDC. There are also few works that compare a larger number of countries. With several regulatory changes related to payments having been implemented around the world (Folwarski, 2018) and new instruments coming on stream (Semerikova, 2020), the research agenda in the area could prioritize these topics.

As limitations, the criteria used in the base searches are determinants for the composition of the sample, so subtle changes in the search parameters can significantly alter the articles identified. The criteria used to classify the articles are also subjective.

Future work may expand the keywords searched, including other terms related to retail payments, to cover a larger sample of articles. The sample size, however, may increase considerably, making it difficult to analyze it according to the methodology employed, since each article needs to be classified in relation to each criterion. New criteria can be included, and other bases can also be considered.

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3 Determinants of Payment Instruments Usage: An International Empirical Analysis from 2005 to 2020

3.1 Introduction

Retail payment instruments and the systems that settle them are fundamental to the smooth functioning of the economy, enabling the exchange of resources necessary for the relationship between the various economic agents (Hasan et al., 2014; Rysman & Schuh, 2017). Originally paper-based, the instruments have undergone rapid electronization due to technological advances in recent decades, providing more efficiency and fluidity for their users, although cash is still the dominant payment instrument in most countries (Bech et al., 2018; Bech & Boar, 2019; Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2019).

This migration to electronic instruments, which enable greater welfare for society as a whole, has been pursued by market participants and encouraged by regulators, who may be interested in the factors that influence the use of retail payment instruments by considering macroeconomic and environmental variables.

Bibliometric analysis presented in chapter 2 pointed out as the main objects of research in retail payments the identification of determinants with a microeconomic focus, that is, on the choice of instruments by users as a function of their socioeconomic characteristics and the characteristics of the transactions. The identification of determinants with a macroeconomic focus, i.e. the macroeconomic and environmental characteristics that influence the aggregate use of the instruments in a given region, was the second most researched object. Several works address the subject, such as Khiaonarong & Humphrey (2022), Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018) e Silva et al. (2017). The determinants identified in the literature as most common are the technological infrastructure of the countries, their economic development and monetary policy conditions, the institutional environment, socio-demographic characteristics and tax policy characteristics of the countries analyzed, employed here as the basis for postulating the hypotheses that direct the work.

Among the studies on the determinants of use, gaps were identified regarding the countries considered, rarely covering emerging countries. In addition, the methods employed are generally limited to traditional econometric methods and the payment instruments considered do not generally include more modern instruments such as instant payments. This study aims to address two of these gaps, using data from the BIS Red Book that includes countries on five continents from 2005 to 2020 (Bank for Interna-

tional Settlements, 2020) and specifically considering instant payments (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016). The analysis may be of interest to both market participants, who can use the results to inform investment decisions in infrastructure, technology, or marketing needed to encourage the use of electronic or innovative instruments, and regulators, who can employ the results to inform policy and regulation aimed at the electronization of payments or the deployment of more modern payment instruments.

Section 3.2 presents a brief review of the literature and postulates the hypotheses that guide the paper. Section 3.3 presents the research methodology, encompassing sample and data source, research variables and econometric model. Section 3.4 presents the research results and, finally, section 3.5 presents the paper's concluding remarks.

3.2 Literature review and research hypotheses

3.2.1 Theoretical literature on the use of payment instruments

Generic and comprehensive theories on the use of payment instruments in general have not been identified. There are theories on the use of and demand for money and a vast literature on the two-sided market theory (Rochet, 2003; Rochet & Tirole, 2002), applied mainly to payment cards (Baxter, 1983; Verdier, 2011), although it can be applied to other instruments, such as those based on credit transfer orders. According to Boeschoten (1992), there are theories of the demand for money from both macroeconomic and microeconomic perspectives. Aspects of these theories could be extrapolated to treat other instruments directly or consider them as the complement of money transactions.

Macroeconomic theory would be more associated with what the present paper considers the use of instruments, particularly money. The microeconomic theory on the demand for money, originally proposed by Baumol (1952) and Tobin (1956) and refined and expanded over the years, would apply better to the choice of payment instruments (also dealing particularly with money).

Keynes (1936) mentions three reasons for holding cash: transactions, precaution, and speculation (or store of value). As an instrument of payment, one is primarily interested in the use of money for transactions. However, it is not trivial to dissociate the three mentioned uses and the demand for money eventually encompasses all of them.

The economic theory that best relates to retail payment transactions is Friedman (1956)'s, Quantitative Theory of Money, based on the quantitative theory of Fisher (1909) and Fisher (1911). According to this theory, the stock of money in the economy M is associated with the total value of transactions with the instrument and the velocity of circulation of money V according to equation 3.1.

$$MV = PT \quad (3.1)$$

where P is the average price of each transaction, and T is the total volume (or quantity) of money transactions. Thus, the money stock must be adequate to cope with the transactions in the economy, given the velocity with which money circulates in the economy. Given that the volume of transactions and velocity are relatively stable in the short run, and that the money stock can be taken as given, prices would adjust to this volume of money, rising if there is an excess and falling if there is a shortage of money.

The velocity of money would be associated with the production structure (exchanges necessary between agents for goods and services to be produced and consumed) and, most importantly for this study, the payment system. Thus, innovations, such as the introduction of instantaneous electronic payment instruments, would contribute to increasing the velocity of circulation of money. Thus, velocity would be $V = PT/M$, that is, the number of times the stock of money circulates to allow the execution of economic transactions.

[Pigou \(1917\)](#) in an approach known as the Cambridge approach, given the difficulty of measuring the number of transactions in the economy, modifies the model by replacing the volume of transactions by aggregate income Y . Thus, the relationship changes to [3.2](#).

$$MV = PY \quad (3.2)$$

Thus, the velocity of circulation of money would not be determined by the need to execute a certain number of transactions, but by income, that affects the amount of money that individuals wish to keep, either for transactions or for the other functions of money. This desire would also be determined by the interest rate level (which would influence the opportunity cost of holding cash resources instead of interest-bearing assets) and by individual preferences. As a consequence, velocity could vary significantly even in the short run.

The demand for cash for speculation or store of value may be dominant, as argued by [Bech et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Boeschoten \(1992\)](#) and considering only the demand for transactions may be misleading. In this respect, [Markowitz \(1952\)](#) and its evolutions consider money as just another asset, whose demand depends on its return and risk in the context of individuals' aggregate portfolio, which includes all types of financial and real assets.

Thus, theoretical determinants of the demand for money as a payment instrument would be inflation, income and interest rates, factors that would also affect the demand for electronic instruments in a complementary or direct way.

3.2.2 Empirical studies on the use of electronic payment instruments

Several papers have sought to establish the determinants of the use of electronic instruments in various economies. The most common determinant is the country's technological infrastructure. [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#), for example, argue that better technological infrastructure is associated with more electronic payments, which would become cheaper and more accessible. Electronic payments rely on computer and telecommunications technologies in order to be effectively offered and used by the population in a relatively cheap and secure way. Thus, a good technological infrastructure is a prerequisite for electronic payments to be relevant in a given country. As proxies, the number of ATM (Automated Teller Machines, the traditional ATMs) and POS (Point of Sale, the traditional card machines) ([Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#); [Martikainen et al., 2015](#); [Silva et al., 2016, 2017](#)) are generally used, in most works on a per capita basis. Number of banks and branches ([Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012](#)) or number of establishments providing payment services ([Silva et al., 2017](#)) are also employed.

Economic development would also determine the level of payment electronization. [Bech & Boar \(2019\)](#), [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Silva et al. \(2016\)](#), among others, argue that a higher level of economic development is associated with a higher proportion of electronic payments, as firms would have more resources to invest in electronic solutions and consumers would have more resources to use them. As proxies, GDP per capita or per worker ([Bech et al., 2018](#); [Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#); [Martikainen et al., 2015](#)), market capitalization of exchange listed companies ([Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#)), consumption relative to GDP ([Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#); [Silva et al., 2016, 2017](#)) or consumption per capita ([Martikainen et al., 2015](#)) and GDP growth ([Silva et al., 2016, 2017](#)) are used. Similarly, [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#) argue that the better the institutional environment, the greater the incentive for electronic payments to be used. Proxies are the level of integration with the European Union (ranging from one to three) ([Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018](#)) and indices from the World Bank Governance Indicators ([Kaufmann et al., 2010](#)), such as those for control of corruption and respect for laws or trust from the European Social Survey Database, time and cost to enforce a contract, and credit regulation index ([Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#)). [Bech et al. \(2018\)](#) use an index of economic and financial uncertainty they have calculated.

The state of monetary policy would also be another determinant of the use of electronic payments. [Khiaonarong & Humphrey \(2022\)](#), [Bech et al. \(2018\)](#), [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#), for example, argue that lower interest rates reduce the opportunity cost of holding cash and consequently encourage the use of cash as a payment instrument, to the detriment of electronic payments, which are

necessarily associated with funds held in bank or payment accounts. Proxies are short-term interest rates (Bech et al., 2018; Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018; Goczek & Witkowski, 2016; Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2022; Martikainen et al., 2015), inflation, aggregate M2 relative to GDP, credit relative to GDP (Goczek & Witkowski, 2016) or Euro area membership (Silva et al., 2017).

Demographics are also commonly considered determinants. Goczek & Witkowski (2016) and Silva et al. (2016) argue that countries in which the population receives more formal education, is younger and more urban tend to use more electronic payments, as people with these characteristics would be more likely to adopt new technologies. Proxies are age dependency ratio (ADR) (Goczek & Witkowski, 2016) or average age of the population (Bech et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2016, 2017), proportion of the population living in cities (Goczek & Witkowski, 2016), percentage of secondary and tertiary education enrollment (Goczek & Witkowski, 2016; Silva et al., 2016, 2017) or cumulative sum of birth and death rate (Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2022).

Other study-specific determinants are also considered. Silva et al. (2016), for example, include the percentage of credit transfers made under SEPA (Single European Payments Area, the European standard for interoperability of payment instruments between EU countries) relative to total credit transfers and the possibility of deferring certain conversions required for SEPA. Bounie et al. (2017) include competition among them, arguing that greater competition among merchants leads to greater card acceptance. Bounie et al. (2017) also include tax burden and regime, arguing that tax regimes more easily subject to evasion lead to lower card acceptance. Silva et al. (2017) consider the price or fees for using the instrument, arguing that the existence of such fees (in their case, for the use of checks) leads to its lower use. Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018) argue that higher violent crime would lead to greater use of electronic payments, as cash would be more vulnerable to theft and robbery.

Finally, Goczek & Witkowski (2016) argue that the payment-related behavior of the population is resistant to change and therefore past habits influence the current use of payment instruments. Thus, the level of electronic payments in a given country would be dependent not only on several variables such as those mentioned above, but also on the level of past use of payment instruments itself.

The samples of papers are as follows: countries from various parts of the world (Bech et al., 2018; Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2022), central and eastern European countries (Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018), EU (Goczek & Witkowski, 2016; Martikainen et al., 2015; Silva et al., 2016, 2017) and France (Bounie et al., 2017). There seems to be a gap about the determinants of the use of payment instruments in large emerging economies and in heterogeneous samples, as only two references seem to include them in the sample. Among the determinants mentioned previously, I chose to test them in the

context of a larger set of countries, including emerging countries. Given the above, the following hypotheses are postulated:

- H3.1a: Better technological infrastructure is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.2a: Better levels of economic and institutional development are associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.3a: Expansionist monetary policy is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.4a: Lower tax burden is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.5a: Lower proportion of elderly in the population is associated with more electronic payments.
- H3.6a: The level of usage of electronic payments is persistent.

A summary of the determinants considered in the literature, the basis for the hypotheses listed above, is presented in Table 7. The expected relationships are presented in the last column, inferred based on the papers identified.

Table 7 – Determinants and their proxies

Determinant	Most common proxies	Authors (e.g.)	Reported rel.
Infrastructure	# ATMs	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018),	+
	# POS	Goczek & Witkowski (2016),	+
	# bank branches	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2012)	+
	# cards	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	+
Economic development	GDP per worker	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018),	+
	GDP per capita	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2012), Bech et al. (2018)	+
Monetary policy	Interest Rate	Khiaonarong & Humphrey (2022), Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018), Bech et al. (2018)	- - -
	Inflation	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2012), Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	-
Institutional environment	Integration with the EU	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018), Callado-Muñoz et al. (2012)	+
	WGI and ESSD indices	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	-
Tax burden and tax regime	Merchants' regimes	Bounie et al. (2017)	-
Demography	Age of the population	Silva et al. (2017), Bech et al. (2018)	-
	Urbanization	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	+
	Schooling	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	+
	Births and deaths	Khiaonarong & Humphrey (2022)	-
Price and Fees	Usage rate	Silva et al. (2017)	-
Criminality	Violent crimes p/ inhab.	Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018)	+
Persistence	Lagged dep. variable	Goczek & Witkowski (2016), Callado-Muñoz et al. (2018)	+

Note: Prepared by the author based on the references indicated in column 3.

3.2.3 Empirical studies on the use of fast payment instruments

New payment instruments have also been little covered in the literature, probably because their development is recent. Fast payments (or instant payments), for example, are payments where the final availability of funds to the payee occurs in real (or near real) time and for 24 hours a day and 7 days a week (or as close to that as possible) ([Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016](#)). Technological advances, particularly related to communication, have lowered costs for end users and payment service providers, making such services viable, while raising end users' expectations for the speed and convenience of payment services ([Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016](#)).

Of the 26 jurisdictions that report data to Red Book, only nine (Argentina, Australia, China, Singapore, South Korea, India, Mexico, Russia, and Sweden) have reported transactions with this payment method by 2019, but more and more countries have shown interest and developed plans to implement systems that support instruments with these features ([Bech & Boar, 2019](#)). For example, in Brazil, Pix went live in November 2020 ([Lobo & Brandt, 2021](#)). An interesting analysis for regulators and participants in the payments industry is what determines the use of this instrument. Thus, hypotheses similar to the previous ones are postulated, but now considering fast payments:

- H3.1b: Better technological infrastructure is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.2b: Better levels of economic and institutional development are associated with more fast payments.
- H3.3b: Expansionist monetary policy is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.4b: Lower tax burden is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.5b: Lower proportion of elderly in the population is associated with more fast payments.
- H3.6b: The level of usage of fast payments is persistent.

The instruments considered in the identified works are generally cards ([Bounie et al., 2017](#); [Callado-Muñoz et al., 2012, 2018](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#); [Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2022](#); [Martikainen et al., 2015](#); [Silva et al., 2016](#)), but also checks ([Martikainen et al., 2015](#); [Silva et al., 2016, 2017](#)), credit transfers ([Martikainen et al., 2015](#); [Silva et al., 2016](#)) and direct debit ([Martikainen et al., 2015](#); [Silva et al., 2016](#)) or cash ([Martikainen et al., 2015](#)). Here too there seems to be a gap with respect to newer (such as fast payments) or more comprehensive instruments (such as credit transfers and direct debits, addressed in few papers).

3.3 Methodology

To test the hypotheses postulated above, I employ panel data analyses (one for the determinants of electronic payments and one for the determinants of fast payments), with independent variables associated with each of the hypotheses. The samples include a representative set of countries from around the world, involving both emerging and developed countries. The data employed are from the ([Bank for International Settlements, 2020](#)) and several World Bank series related to demographics, economic development

(World Bank, 2019) and institutional governance (Kaufmann et al., 2010). The following sections describe the sample and sources, the variables, and the econometric model.

3.3.1 Sample and data sources

The sample consists of annual observations from 2005 to 2020 from 25 member countries of the BIS Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures (CPMI) that report Red Book data (Bank for International Settlements, 2020). They are: South Africa, Germany, Saudi Arabia, Argentina, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China, Singapore, South Korea, Spain, United States, France, Netherlands, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, Mexico, Russia, United Kingdom, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey. Hong Kong also provides data for the Red Book, but as there are no independent series for much of the explanatory variables employed, they were disregarded. The consideration of a more heterogeneous set of countries in the sample addresses one of the gaps identified in the bibliometric analysis on the subject (chapter 2), as there is little work on retail payments considering emerging countries or countries from several continents together.

In August 2017, the CPMI modified the Red Book methodology, requesting that reporting countries provide modified series backdated to 2012 (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2017), but the earlier data were harmonized to compose a single series. Thus, the period encompasses the 16 mentioned years, with 2020 being the latest year available at the time of writing. The BIS does not release data more frequently, and for the purposes of this study annual data are sufficient, since the use of payment instruments in a given economy does not vary frequently, but changes relatively smoothly, mainly as a function of long-term trends.

The CPMI Red Book contains data on payments (value and quantity of transactions), broken down by instrument, on payment infrastructure (number of ATMs and POS), on some macroeconomic variables (paper money in circulation, inflation, GDP per capita) and demographic variables (population). From the World Bank, data were used on governance indicators (violence, respect for rules, and control of corruption) (Kaufmann et al., 2010) infrastructure (number of mobile phones per capita), countries' tax burden, demographic (proportion of older people in the population), and economic (consumption share of GDP) (World Bank, 2019). Table 8 presents the sources of the variables used.

Table 8 – Variable sources

Variable	Source	WWW address
Electronic or fast payments	Red Book	stats.bis.org/statx/toc/CPMI.html
Consumption in relation to GDP	BM - WDI	data.worldbank.org/indicator/NE.CON.PRVT.ZS
Number of cell phones lines	BM - WDI	data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.CEL.SETS.P2
Paper money in circulation	Red Book	stats.bis.org/statx/toc/CPMI.html
GDP and GDP per capita	Red Book	stats.bis.org/statx/toc/CPMI.html
Inflation	Red Book	tats.bis.org/statx/toc/CPMI.html
Population	Red Book	stats.bis.org/statx/toc/CPMI.html
Control of corruption	BM - WGI	info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/
Quality of regulation	BM - WGI	info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/
Tax burden	BM - WDI	data.worldbank.org/indicator/GC.TAX.TOTL.GD.ZS
Elderly proportion	BM - WDI	data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.65UP.TO.ZS
Violence	BM - WGI	info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/

Note: Prepared by the author.

3.3.2 Study variables

Table 9 presents the association between the variables and the hypotheses, as well as the mnemonic that identifies each of them in the econometric model presented in section 3.3.3. Table 10 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables. The periodicity of all variables is annual. Additional information on each of them is presented in the next subsections.

Table 9 – Mnemonics of the variables

Variable	Type	Mnemonic	Hypothesis
Number of electronic payments per capita	D	ELEC_QT_POP	H3.1a to H3.6a
Number of fast payments per capita	D	FAST_QT_POP	H3.1b to H3.6b
Number of cell phones lines per 100 inhabitants	I	MOBILE	H3.1a and H3.1b
Inflation	I	INFLATION	H3.2a and H3.2b
Tax burden	I	TAX_REVENUE	H3.3a and H3.3b
Elderly proportion in the population	I	ELDERLY_RATIO	H3.4a and H3.4b
Economic and institutional development	I	WGI_INST_ENV	H3.5a and H3.5b

Note: Prepared by the author. Type D = dependent and I = independent.

Table 10 – Descriptive analysis of the variables

Mnemonic	n	Min.	Mean	Med.	Max.	SD	CV	Kurt.	Ass.
ELECT_QT_POP	373	0.00	197.92	183.88	840.00	174.51	0.88	3.70	0.99
FAST_QT_POP	373	0.00	7.31	0.00	236.57	26.19	3.58	36.19	5.30
MOBILE	375	7.85	111.20	111.56	191.03	29.39	0.26	3.59	-0.31
INFLATION	375	-2.09	3.47	2.21	52.80	5.08	1.46	39.73	5.12
WDI_INST_ENV	375	-0.83	0.66	0.89	1.96	0.85	1.29	1.52	-0.23
TAX_REVENUE	355	2.33	15.96	13.53	28.56	6.46	0.40	1.84	0.34
ELDERLY_RATIO	375	2.94	13.38	13.91	28.40	5.94	0.44	2.02	-0.02

Note: Prepared by the author. Variables with annual periodicity. SD = standard deviation; CV = coefficient of variation; Kurtosis = kurtosis; Ass. = asymmetry; ELECT_QT_POP and FAST_QT_POP = number of electronic and fast payments per capita, respectively; MOBILE = number of cell phone lines per 100 inhabitants; INFLATION in % a year; WDI_INST_ENV = index between -2.5 (best) and 2.5 (worst) related to institutional development; TAX_REVENUE = tax burden on GDP; ELDERLY_RATIO = percentage of the population over 65 years old.

3.3.2.1 Dependent variables

The dependent variables considered in the study are the number of transactions with electronic payments (ELECT_QT_POP) or fast payments (FAST_QT_POP) per capita. The number of transactions, obtained from the Red Book, considers credit transfers, direct debits and payments with credit, debit and prepaid cards (e-money), as well as fast payments. Figures 7 and 8 show, respectively, the evolution of the number of electronic and fast payments per capita by country during the period under consideration.

Figure 7 – Number of electronic payments per capita by year and country. Source: Prepared by the author with data from Red Book.

Figure 8 – Number of fast payments per capita by year and country. Source: Prepared by the author with data from Red Book.

The graphs show that there are countries with a relatively high number of electronic transactions per capita, like Singapore (SG), Korea (KR), Australia (AU) and Sweden (SE), while others have low numbers of transactions per capita, like India (ID), Mexico (MX) and Japan (JP), but the trend is growing in all of them, especially Russia. The growth trend in the number of rapid payments is even more accentuated, with

China (CN), Russia (RU), Korea (KR), Sweden (SE), Holland (NL), and Singapore (SG) standing out.

I consider the number of transactions per capita as the most appropriate variable to analyze the growth in the use of electronic retail instruments since it actually reflects the use of these instruments, regardless of value or the organic growth of the economy. To assess the robustness of the results, the value of payments will be employed, either per capita (deflated and converted to US dollars, `ELECT_VL_POP`) or as a ratio to consumption (`ELECT_CONS`), currency in circulation (`ELECT_CURR`) or GDP (`ELECT_GDP`). In the last three cases, it is not necessary to deflate or convert the values to a common currency. Consumption was calculated as the consumption portion of GDP multiplied by the countries' GDP in current values, with data from the Red Book and the World Bank. Currency in circulation and GDP used were those of the Red Book.

The papers reviewed employ dependent variables in line with those employed here, although with some variation. [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2012\)](#) use per capita card payments over per capita money in circulation. [Silva et al. \(2017\)](#) (in one of their analyses) employ the proportion of checks over the total payments considered. [Silva et al. \(2016\)](#) employ the proportion of each instrument over the total instruments considered (checks, cards, credit transfers or direct debit). [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#) use the annual value of card transactions per capita and [Silva et al. \(2017\)](#) (in another analysis) employ the number of checks per capita.

3.3.2.2 Independent variables

As a proxy for the country's technological infrastructure, I chose to use the number of mobile phone accounts per 100 inhabitants from the WDI. The number of ATMs and POS, also used in the literature, were discarded due to the unavailability of data from several countries. Relevant countries, such as South Korea and the United States, do not report these data to the Red Book, and their use would compromise the breadth of the sample. Better technological infrastructure is expected to be associated with a higher share of electronic or fast payments. The number of phone accounts, while not a variable employed in the identified literature, was included as a proxy because currently large numbers of financial and payment transactions are initiated in the mobile channel ([Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures & World Bank, 2020](#); [Rysman & Schuh, 2017](#)).

The proxies for the economic development and institutional environment of the sample countries are an average of the WGI's Regulation Quality, Control of Corruption, and Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism. Because they are highly correlated (Pearson correlation indices between 0.85 and 0.95), these WGI variables were combined into a single one corresponding to the average of the original variables. The values of each index range from -2.5 (poor level of governance in the aspect considered) to 2.5 (good level of governance in the aspect considered). The quality of regulation allows payment arrangements to operate with little risk to participants and end users, ensuring that transactions are indeed carried out efficiently and safely. Controlling corruption and violence discourages the use of cash in transactions. Thus, a better institutional environment would be associated with a higher share of electronic or fast payments

The tax burden of countries is another variable employed. The proxy for this

variable was obtained from the WDI (central government tax burden as a percentage of GDP). Higher tax burdens would discourage payment with electronic instruments, since both payees and payers would tend to prefer the use of cash. Cash facilitates anonymity and makes control difficult, allowing taxes on sales transactions, which are levied in most countries, to be evaded. Qualitative factors about the prevailing tax regime in the countries would also be an interesting variable, but consolidated information for most countries is not available. Higher tax burdens would therefore be associated with a lower use of electronic or fast payments.

As a proxy for the demographic characteristics of the countries, I chose to use the proportion of older people in the population (percentage of people over 65 in relation to the total population). In general, electronic payments are preferred by younger people, while older people, who are generally more traditional, opt for cash payments. Thus, the higher the proportion of older people, the lower the proportion of electronic or fast payments.

The variables were standardized and centered to equalize their influence on the dependent variable. Table 11 presents the correlation between them. The VIF (variance inflation factor), presented in the last column of the table, shows that there are no issues related to multicollinearity between the independent variables. Other variables, such as proxies for education and income would also be interesting and are employed in several papers, but they are highly correlated with some of the variables included in the study and were discarded.

Table 11 – Correlations between the independent variables and VIF

	MOBILE	INFLATION	WDI_INST_ENV	TAX_REVENUE	ELDERLY_RATIO	VIF
MOBILE	1.000	0.055	0.066	0.096	0.139	1.034
INFLATION	0.055	1.000	-0.467	-0.115	-0.330	1.301
WDI_INST_ENV	0.066	-0.467	1.000	0.322	0.619	1.890
TAX_REVENUE	0.096	-0.115	0.322	1.000	0.369	1.184
ELDERLY_RATIO	0.139	-0.330	0.619	0.369	1.000	1.743

Note: Prepared by the author. Variables with annual periodicity. Pearson Correlation between the independent variables and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). MOBILE = number of cell phone lines per 100 inhabitants; INFLATION in % a year; WDI_INST_ENV = index between -2.5 (worst) and 2.5 (best) related to institutional development; TAX_REVENUE = tax burden on GDP; ELDERLY_RATIO = percentage of the population over 65 years old.

3.3.3 Econometric Model

The econometric model of the panel data analysis employed in the paper is presented in equation 3.3.

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 Y_{it-1} + \beta_2 MOBILE_{it} + \beta_3 INFLATION_{it} + \beta_4 WDI_INST_ENV_{it} + \beta_5 TAX_REVENUE_{it} + \beta_6 ELDERLY_RATIO_{it} + \lambda_i + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3.3)$$

where the variables are as follows:

- i : country;
- t : year;
- Y_{it} : number of transactions with electronic (ELECT_QT_POP) or fast (FAST_QT_POP) instruments per person per country and year;
- $MOBILE_{it}$: number of cell phone lines per 100 inhabitants per country per year;
- $INFLATION_{it}$: consumer inflation rate per country per year;
- $WDI_INST_ENV_{it}$: WGI-based Institutional Development Index per country per year;
- $TAX_REVENUE_{it}$: central government tax burden as a percentage of GDP per country per year;
- $ELDERLY_RATIO_{it}$: percentage of people over 65 in total population per country per year;
- λ_i : country fixed effects;
- ϵ_{it} : error

3.4 Results analysis

Results were obtained with R's plm package for panel data analysis (Croissant & Millo, 2008, 2018; Millo, 2017) and tables were generated with R's stargazer package (Hlavac, 2022).

3.4.1 Electronic payments

Table 12 presents the results of the panel analysis where the dependent variable is the number of electronic payments per person. Column 7 presents the results of the panel in first differences with country fixed effects with robust errors, the panel indicated by the tests highlighted at the end of the table as the best fit for the data.

Table 12 – Determinants of the number of electronic payments

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>						
	ELECT_QT_POP						
	OLS	COUNTRY FE	COUNTRY RE	TIME FE	BOTH FE	RE BOTH FE	FD
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
MOBILE	0.169*** (0.038)	-0.001 (0.034)	0.114*** (0.037)	0.037 (0.035)	-0.027 (0.035)	-0.027 (0.071)	0.020 (0.034)
INFLATION	-0.029 (0.040)	-0.069** (0.029)	-0.068** (0.034)	-0.028 (0.034)	-0.094*** (0.028)	-0.094*** (0.030)	0.006 (0.008)
WDI_INST_ENV	0.802*** (0.049)	0.044 (0.145)	0.016 (0.106)	0.900*** (0.042)	0.316** (0.137)	0.316 (0.209)	-0.036 (0.050)
TAX_REVENUE	0.091** (0.039)	-0.447*** (0.093)	-0.246*** (0.085)	0.112*** (0.033)	-0.351*** (0.089)	-0.351*** (0.116)	-0.004 (0.033)
ELDERLY_RATIO	-0.252*** (0.049)	1.726*** (0.085)	1.179*** (0.085)	-0.339*** (0.042)	0.688*** (0.144)	0.688 (0.622)	0.527 (0.582)
Constant	0.018 (0.036)		-0.029 (0.123)				0.055*** (0.021)
Chow		67.554***					
Hausman		166.082***					
Lagrange mult.			222.705***				
Serial corr.					210.444***		
Stationarity					-5.049***		
Heterocedast.					415.096***		
Observations	355	355	355	355	355	355	330
R ²	0.556	0.647	0.493	0.671	0.152	0.152	0.020
Adjusted R ²	0.550	0.615	0.486	0.651	0.031	0.031	0.005
F Statistic	87.433***	119.089***	339.861***	135.998***	11.095***	11.095***	1.302

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for panel serial correlation

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for stationarity of the dependent variable.

Breusch-Pagan test for homoscedasticity.

Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier for time fixed effects test.

F-test for non-zero coefficients.

The Chow test pointed out that there is structural break in the series and that, therefore, panel data analysis is preferable to a pooled regression (comparison between columns 1 and 2 of the table). The Hausman test rejected the null hypothesis that the random effects estimators are consistent and therefore the fixed effects panel is preferable (comparison between columns 2 and 3 of the table). The Lagrange test indicated that there are time fixed effects (comparison between columns 2 and 4 of the table) and that therefore a panel with time and country fixed effects should be used (column 5). The augmented Dickey-Fuller test indicates stationarity of the dependent variable, while the Breusch-Pagan test indicates heteroscedasticity and the Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test indicates the presence of serial correlation. Thus, column 7 presents results for the panel in first differences (FD) with robust errors, in which only the constant is significant, but the F test for this panel fails to reject the null hypothesis that all of the coefficients are different from zero.

Panel Granger causality tests (Dumitrescu & Hurlin, 2012) presented in Table 13, on their turn, show that WDI_INST_ENV and ELDERLY_RATIO Granger cause the number of electronic payments per capita, but, conservatively, I conclude that none of the proposed determinants are significant.

Table 13 – Panel causality Granger test

Variable	Granger test
MOBILE	0.316
INFLATION	-0.041
WDI_INST_ENV	2.487**
TAX_REVENUE	0.996
ELDERLY_RATIO	8.063***

Note: Prepared by the author.

Results for Granger causality test (Dumitrescu and Hurlin, 2012) in panel for each of the independent variables in relation to the dependent variable.

Significance of the statistic implies Granger causality for at least one country.

Although the augmented Dickey-Fuller test indicated stationarity of the dependent variable, as the residuals present serial correlation and the F test for the FD panel failed to indicate the goodness of fit of the model, I chose to employ dynamic panel data analysis, as was done by Goczek & Witkowski (2016). Table 14 presents the results, employing both Arellano & Bond (1991) and Blundell & Bond (1998) two-stage estimators (one-stage estimators indicate similar results, not shown), with country only or country and time fixed effects, with robust errors. As instrumental variables, the dependent variable with lags greater than 1 collapsed was used to avoid excess instrumental variables. Since the dependent variable series is stationary, the most appropriate model would be that of Arellano & Bond (1991), but results with the Blundell & Bond (1998) estimator are presented for robustness. Sargan's test does not reject the null hypothesis of adequacy of instrumental variables. The Arellano & Bond (1991) test indicates the existence of autocorrelation of the first-order residuals and the absence of autocorrelation of the second-order residuals, as required by the estimators. Wald's test, finally, indicates that the coefficients are different from zero. Taken together, these tests indicate the adequacy of the models presented.

Table 14 – Determinants of the quantity of electronic payments - dynamic models

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>			
	AB COUNTRY	AB BOTH	ELECT_QT_POP BB COUNTRY	BB BOTH
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
lag(ELECT_QT_POP, 1)	0.799*** (0.089)	0.835*** (0.239)	1.127*** (0.071)	0.997*** (0.056)
MOBILE	0.044* (0.026)	0.062 (0.056)	-0.00003 (0.014)	-0.010 (0.011)
INFLATION	0.012** (0.005)	-0.024 (0.020)	0.001 (0.008)	-0.008* (0.005)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.019 (0.070)	-0.095 (0.090)	-0.092 (0.057)	0.033 (0.050)
TAX_REVENUE	0.062** (0.029)	0.155 (0.122)	-0.005 (0.023)	0.004 (0.011)
ELDERLY_RATIO	0.207 (0.250)	-0.202 (0.966)	0.039 (0.027)	-0.011 (0.017)
Sargan	11.784	8.820	19.390	4.817
AR1	-2.263**	-1.676*	-2.398**	-1.888*
AR2	1.361	1.466	1.062	1.211
Stages	2	2	2	2
Fixed effects	Country	Both	Country	Both
Estimator	AB	AB	BB	BB
Instr. var.	2 a 13	2 a 13	2 a 13	2 a 13
Colaps. instr. var.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
Wald	455.517***	127.924***	1667.001***	19418.445***
Observations	355	355	355	355

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Wald test for non-zero coefficients.

AB = Arellano and Bond (1991) estimator; BB = Blundell and Bond (1998) estimator.

Sargan test for adequacy of instrumental variables.

AR1 and AR2 are the Arellano and Bond (1991) test for the existence of autocorrelation of the first-order and second-order residuals, respectively.

Instr. var. and Colaps. instr. var. indicate the number of lags of the dependent variable used as instrumental variables and whether they were collapsed, respectively.

Stages indicate whether the 1- or 2-stage estimator was used.

Results indicate that the lagged dependent variable presents a positive and significant coefficient, indicating that the past behavior of the population is important in determining the present behavior regarding the use of payment instruments. This behavior suggests that the lagged dependent variable ultimately captures the influence of the demographic structure and other variables on the use of payments. Thus, hypothesis H3.6a, that the level of usage of electronic payments is persistent, is not rejected.

The coefficient of the proxy for technological infrastructure (MOBILE) shows an undefined sign (negative in some models and positive in others), significant only in the [Arellano & Bond \(1991\)](#) models. The number of cell phone lines per (MOBILE) does not explain the use of larger shares of electronic payments across countries, contrary to works such as [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) (which find a significant relationship) and [Silva et al. \(2017\)](#) (which did not find a significant relationship, but targets the use of checks rather than electronic instruments). This result suggests that a good technological infrastructure, in particular a good availability of mobile lines, may be a prerequisite for electronization, but not a determinant, with countries with good infrastructure also showing relatively low numbers of electronic transactions, such as Germany. Thus, hypothesis H3.1a is inconclusive.

Monetary policy conditions were not a determinant of the electronization of retail payments, although the relationship found is negative in most models, without significance. The result would indicate that higher inflation rates, usually associated with higher interest rates, discourage the use of electronic payments, contrary to expectations. [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2012\)](#) also found a negative relationship with interest rates, but they explain this apparent contradiction as a function of interest rate convergence of eastern and central European countries with the EU (which were being reduced) at the same time that the use of electronic payments also converged (which were increasing). [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#) find a positive (but also non-significant in most specifications) relationship, indicating that the increased opportunity cost of holding and using cash stimulates migration to electronic payments, where funds are held in bank or payment accounts and can earn remuneration. Thus, as the relationship is not significant in the dynamic panel and causality was not verified, it is not possible to infer on hypothesis H3.2a. As in the case of the variable associated with economic development and institutional environment, possibly the electronization of payments is occurring both in countries that have low inflation and in countries that have high inflation.

The institutional environment is also not a significant determinant of the electronization of retail payments. The trend toward electronization spans all countries, including those whose institutional environment is less conducive to innovation. The relationship between the proxy WDI_INST_ENV (control of corruption, quality of regulation, and political stability and absence of violence) and the dependent variable is negative in most models, contrary to expectations. [Callado-Muñoz et al. \(2018\)](#) find positive and significant relationship (represented by the degree of integration with the EU). [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#) also found negative and non-significant relationship. Again, since the relationship is non-significant, it is not possible to infer on hypothesis H3.3a.

Tax burden shows a positive relationship with electronic payments in most models, contrary to expectations, but not significantly. The result suggests that the higher the tax

burden, the more electronic payments are used. Thus, any encouragement by merchants to use cash to avoid consumption taxes would not be sufficient to curb the growth of electronic payments. The result is at odds with the literature, such as [Bounie et al. \(2017\)](#), which finds a negative relationship. However, since the relationship is not significant, it is not possible to infer on hypothesis H3.4a.

Although there is Granger causality between ELDERLY_RATIO and the dependent variable, it is not possible to infer that demographic characteristics are a determining factor for the electronization of retail payments, as the significance does not hold with robust errors in the static panel and in the dynamic panel. The relationship found between the proxy employed in this work and the number of electronic payments per capita was positive in most models, contrary to expectations. [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#) found a negative (though not significant) relationship between the proportion of dependents (elderly or very young) and electronization. One possibility is that the rate of elderly in the population is associated with economic development and also that electronic payments are more widespread among all age strata than previous studies have found. Thus, it is not possible to conclude on hypothesis H3.5a.

3.4.1.1 Alternative dependent variables

Table 15 presents results from static panels with alternative dependent variables for electronic payments and Table 16 presents results from dynamic panels. Model (1) in Table 15 corresponds to the model in first differences (7) presented in Table 12 and models (1) and (2) from Table 16 correspond to models (2) and (4) in Table 14. As mentioned in section 3.3.2.1, the variable ELECT_VL_POP corresponds to the value of electronic payment transactions (deflated and dollarized) per capita, ELECT_CONS corresponds to the ratio of the value of transactions to consumption, ELECT_CURR to the ratio to currency in circulation, and ELECT_GDP to the ratio to GDP. I conclude that, in fact, there is no way to state about the postulated determinants, with the exception of the lagged dependent variable, significant in all models where alternative variables are used, although not all tests show model fit.

Table 15 – Alternative dependent variables for electronic payments

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	ELECT_QT_POP (1)	ELECT_VL_POP (2)	ELECT_CONS (3)	ELECT_CURR (4)	ELECT_GDP (5)
MOBILE	0.020 (0.034)	0.089 (0.091)	0.011 (0.088)	0.040 (0.065)	0.043 (0.080)
INFLATION	0.006 (0.008)	-0.016 (0.043)	-0.044 (0.041)	-0.006 (0.031)	-0.031 (0.038)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.036 (0.050)	0.383 (0.260)	0.323 (0.250)	0.360* (0.188)	0.231 (0.227)
TAX_REVENUE	-0.004 (0.033)	0.025 (0.185)	-0.055 (0.178)	0.168 (0.133)	-0.055 (0.161)
ELDERLY_RATIO	0.527 (0.582)	0.412 (0.690)	0.148 (0.662)	0.093 (0.493)	0.200 (0.602)
Constant	0.055*** (0.021)	-0.020 (0.036)	0.021 (0.035)	-0.009 (0.026)	0.006 (0.032)
Observations	330	330	330	328	330
R ²	0.020	0.012	0.009	0.019	0.007
Adjusted R ²	0.005	-0.004	-0.006	0.004	-0.008
F Statistic	1.302 (df = 5; 324)	0.765 (df = 5; 324)	0.593 (df = 5; 324)	1.242 (df = 5; 322)	0.454 (df = 5; 324)

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. First-difference models with robust errors and country fixed effects.

ELECT_QT_POP corresponds to the amount of electronic payments per capita presented previously.

ELECT_VL_POP corresponds to the dollarized and depreciated value of electronic payments per capita.

ELECT_CONS corresponds to the value of electronic payments in relation to consumption.

ELECT_CURR corresponds to the value of electronic payments in relation to currency in circulation.

ELECT_GDP corresponds to the value of electronic payments in relation to GDP.

F-test for non-zero coefficients.

Table 16 – Alternative dependent variables for electronic payments - dynamic models

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>									
	ELECT_QT_POP		ELECT_VL_POP		ELECT_CONS		ELECT_CURR		ELECT_GDP	
	AB BOTH	BB BOTH	AB BOTH	BB BOTH	AB BOTH	BB BOTH	AB BOTH	BB BOTH	AB BOTH	BB BOTH
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
lag(ELECT_QT_POP, 1)	0.835*** (0.239)	0.997*** (0.056)								
lag(ELECT_VL_POP, 1)			0.708*** (0.071)	0.808*** (0.027)						
lag(ELECT_CONS, 1)					0.715*** (0.083)	0.730*** (0.070)				
lag(ELECT_CURR, 1)							0.914*** (0.101)	0.889*** (0.053)		
lag(ELECT_GDP, 1)									0.754*** (0.161)	0.925*** (0.013)
MOBILE	0.062 (0.056)	-0.010 (0.011)	0.053 (0.155)	0.015 (0.035)	0.021 (0.392)	0.001 (0.046)	-0.213 (0.422)	0.023 (0.025)	0.027 (0.321)	-0.019 (0.019)
INFLATION	-0.024 (0.020)	-0.008* (0.005)	-0.0004 (0.020)	-0.011 (0.010)	-0.006 (0.026)	-0.038** (0.016)	0.003 (0.020)	-0.010 (0.009)	0.015 (0.017)	-0.014* (0.008)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.095 (0.090)	0.033 (0.050)	0.249 (0.349)	0.018 (0.026)	-0.086 (0.410)	-0.009 (0.045)	0.708 (0.716)	-0.012 (0.012)	0.451 (0.345)	-0.016 (0.018)
TAX_REVENUE	0.155 (0.122)	0.004 (0.011)	-0.322 (0.232)	0.006 (0.022)	-0.243 (0.336)	0.012 (0.037)	-0.168* (0.089)	0.006 (0.008)	-0.184 (0.571)	-0.004 (0.014)
ELDERLY_RATIO	-0.202 (0.966)	-0.011 (0.017)	-0.210 (0.460)	0.008 (0.029)	-0.205 (0.299)	0.022 (0.048)	0.821 (1.594)	-0.011 (0.009)	-0.266 (1.657)	0.004 (0.017)
Sargan	8.820	4.817	5.416	6.576	8.775	3.930	10.056	1.760	16.590	8.241
AR1	-1.676*	-1.888*	-1.229	-1.193	-2.141**	-1.983**	-0.663	-1.284	-1.606	-1.327
AR2	1.466	1.211	1.638	1.148	1.792*	0.581	-0.416	-0.795	1.165	0.848
Stages	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Fixed effects	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both	Both
Estimator	AB	BB	AB	BB	AB	BB	AB	BB	AB	BB
Wald	127.924***	19418.445***	285.857***	6072.610***	98.056***	226.669***	7125.647***	17505.128***	331.353***	5614.644***
Observations	355	355	353	353	353	353	353	353	353	353

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Wald test for non-zero coefficients.

ELECT_QT_POP corresponds to the amount of electronic payments per capita presented previously.

ELECT_VL_POP corresponds to the dollarized and depreciated value of electronic payments per capita.

ELECT_CONS, ELECT_CURR and ELECT_GDP correspond to the value of electronic payments in relation to consumption, currency in circulation and GDP, respectively.

AB = Arellano and Bond (1991) estimator; BB = Blundell and Bond (1998) estimator.

Sargan test for adequacy of instrumental variables.

AR1 and AR2 are the Arellano and Bond (1991) test for the existence of autocorrelation of the first-order and second-order residuals, respectively.

Instr. var. and Colaps. inst. var. indicate the number of lags of the dependent variable used as instrumental variables and whether they were collapsed, respectively.

Stages indicate whether the 1- or 2-stage estimator was used.

3.4.2 Fast payments

In relation to rapid payments, whose results of the static panels are presented in Table 17, the econometric tests also indicated the first differences model as the most appropriate. Results are in line with those presented for the number of electronic payments per capita, but ELDERLY_RATIO is significant in the model for fast payments, with a positive relationship with the dependent variable, suggesting that, contrary to what was expected, fast payments are more widespread among all age strata. Besides that, as this variable is associated with economic development, fast payments may be more common in developed countries.

As there is serial correlation between the residuals, I employed models with the lagged dependent variable as one of the explanatory variables (Table 18). In these models, virtually all of the explanatory power is also captured by the lagged variable, as in the case of electronic payments, indicating that the past behavior of the population is important in determining the present behavior regarding the use of fast payment instruments, although the AB test for autocorrelation of the first-order residuals failed. Comparison with the prior literature is hampered in these models because no papers were identified in which fast payments were analyzed in relation to their determinants of use. It is possible to infer, therefore, that hypothesis H3.6b is not rejected, but it is not possible to infer about hypotheses H3.1b through H3.5b.

Table 17 – Determinants of the number of fast payments

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>						
	FAST_QT_POP						
	OLS	COUNTRY FE	COUNTRY RE	TIME FE	BOTH FE	RE BOTH FE	FD
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
MOBILE	0.183*** (0.055)	0.331*** (0.087)	0.447*** (0.074)	0.144** (0.059)	0.608*** (0.095)	0.608* (0.323)	0.074 (0.080)
INFLATION	-0.142** (0.058)	-0.131* (0.075)	-0.104 (0.071)	-0.154*** (0.057)	-0.169** (0.074)	-0.169 (0.104)	-0.010 (0.017)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.317*** (0.071)	1.381*** (0.369)	-0.236 (0.151)	-0.271*** (0.071)	1.520*** (0.366)	1.520** (0.717)	0.031 (0.104)
TAX_REVENUE	-0.117** (0.057)	-0.948*** (0.236)	-0.383*** (0.126)	-0.112** (0.055)	-1.089*** (0.237)	-1.089** (0.537)	-0.155 (0.147)
ELDERLY_RATIO	0.162** (0.072)	1.364*** (0.217)	0.508*** (0.141)	0.098 (0.071)	0.896** (0.385)	0.896 (1.033)	2.662* (1.487)
Constant	0.004 (0.052)		-0.063 (0.132)				-0.033 (0.043)
Chow		12.878***					
Hausman		245.166***					
Lagrange Mult.				10.403***			
Serial corr.					175.619***		
Stationarity					-7.500***		
Homocedast.					1009.389***		
Observations	355	355	355	355	355	355	330
R ²	0.097	0.318	0.183	0.074	0.271	0.271	0.081
Adjusted R ²	0.084	0.257	0.172	0.019	0.168	0.168	0.067
F Statistic	7.523***	30.309***	78.329***	5.355***	23.059***	23.059***	5.715***

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for panel serial correlation

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for stationarity of the dependent variable.

Breusch-Pagan test for homoscedasticity.

Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier for time fixed effects test.

F-test for non-zero coefficients.

Table 18 – Determinants of the quantity of electronic payments - dynamic models

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>			
	AB COUNTRY (1)	AB BOTH (2)	FAST_QT_POP BB COUNTRY (3)	BB BOTH (4)
lag(FAST_QT_POP, 1)	0.963*** (0.059)	0.876*** (0.168)	1.260*** (0.028)	1.244*** (0.034)
MOBILE	0.002 (0.017)	0.067 (0.076)	0.008 (0.012)	0.017 (0.018)
INFLATION	-0.011 (0.008)	-0.016 (0.023)	-0.001 (0.015)	0.004 (0.005)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.059 (0.135)	-0.028 (0.131)	-0.002 (0.026)	0.002 (0.023)
TAX_REVENUE	0.002 (0.042)	-0.008 (0.106)	-0.006 (0.020)	0.002 (0.012)
ELDERLY_RATIO	0.241 (0.237)	1.133 (1.346)	0.008 (0.016)	-0.004 (0.012)
Sargan	10.070	7.314	14.693	5.028
AR1	-1.365	-0.994	-1.455	-1.518
AR2	-1.041	-0.644	-1.123	-0.696
Stages	2	2	2	2
Fixes effects	Country	Both	Country	Both
Estimator	AB	AB	BB	BB
Instr. var.	2 a 13	2 a 13	2 a 13	2 a 13
Colaps. instr. var.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
Wald	1287.647***	579.705***	4333.724***	2772.596***
Observations	355	355	355	355

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Wald test for non-zero coefficients.

AB = Arellano and Bond (1991) estimator; BB = Blundell and Bond (1998) estimator.

Sargan test for adequacy of instrumental variables.

AR1 and AR2 are the Arellano and Bond (1991) test for the existence of autocorrelation of the first-order and second-order residuals, respectively.

Instr. var. and Colaps. instr. var. indicate the number of lags of the dependent variable used as instrumental variables and whether they were collapsed, respectively.

Stages indicate whether the 1- or 2-stage estimator was used.

3.4.2.1 Alternative dependent variables

Table 19 presents alternative dependent variables for fast payments in level and Table 20 for dynamic models. Model (1) in Table 19 is model (7) shown in Table 17 and models (1) and (2) in Table 20 are models (1) and (3) from Table 18. As mentioned in section 3.3.2.1, variable FAST_VL_POP corresponds to the total value of fast payments per capita in a given country and year, in deflated dollars. Additional alternative variables, such as the values in relation to consumption, currency in circulation and GDP, were not employed because fast payments correspond to negligible shares of these macroeconomic variables.

The lagged dependent variable remains significant when employing the value of payments, although not all assumptions of the estimators are met (especially the AR1 test). In panels in level, the variable related to demographics remains significant.

Table 19 – Determinants of fast payments - alternative dependent variables

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	FAST_QT_POP (1)	FAST_VL_POP (2)
MOBILE	0.074 (0.068)	0.038 (0.082)
INFLATION	-0.010 (0.032)	-0.014 (0.039)
WDI_INST_ENV	0.031 (0.193)	-0.029 (0.235)
TAX_REVENUE	-0.155 (0.137)	-0.078 (0.167)
ELDERLY_RATIO	2.662*** (0.511)	1.277** (0.623)
Constant	-0.033 (0.027)	-0.012 (0.033)
Observations	330	330
R ²	0.081	0.014
Adjusted R ²	0.067	-0.001
F Statistic (df = 5; 324)	5.715***	0.924

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. First-difference models with robust errors and country fixed effects.

FAST_QT_POP is the number of fast payments per person.

FAST_VL_POP is the value of fast payments per person, deflated and dollarized.

F-test for non-zero coefficients.

Table 20 – Determinants of fast payments - alternative dependent variables - dynamic models

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>			
	FAST_QT_POP		FAST_VL_POP	
	AB COUNTRY	AB BOTH	BB COUNTRY	BB BOTH
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
lag(FAST_QT_POP, 1)	0.876*** (0.168)	1.244*** (0.034)		
lag(FAST_VL_POP, 1)			1.401*** (0.411)	1.083*** (0.052)
MOBILE	0.067 (0.076)	0.017 (0.018)	0.059 (0.118)	0.004 (0.019)
INFLATION	-0.016 (0.023)	0.004 (0.005)	0.015 (0.094)	-0.00004 (0.005)
WDI_INST_ENV	-0.028 (0.131)	0.002 (0.023)	0.013 (0.333)	0.014 (0.010)
TAX_REVENUE	-0.008 (0.106)	0.002 (0.012)	0.291 (0.229)	0.007 (0.008)
ELDERLY_RATIO	1.133 (1.346)	-0.004 (0.012)	0.081 (0.619)	0.003 (0.011)
Sargan	7.314	5.028	8.240	2.370
AR1	-0.994	-1.518	-1.304	-1.327
AR2	-0.644	-0.696	-1.256	NaN
Stages	2	2	2	2
Fixed effects	Both	Both	Both	Both
Estimator	AB	BB	AB	BB
Wald	579.705***	2772.596***	157.447***	980.537***
Observations	355	355	355	355

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Prepared by the author. Wald test for non-zero coefficients.

FAST_QT_POP is the number of fast payments per person.

FAST_VL_POP is the value of fast payments per person, deflated and dollarized.

AB = Arellano and Bond (1991) estimator; BB = Blundell and Bond (1998) estimator.

Sargan test for adequacy of instrumental variables.

AR1 and AR2 are the Arellano and Bond (1991) test for the existence of autocorrelation of the first-order and second-order residuals, respectively.

Instr. var. and Colaps. inst. var. indicate the number of lags of the dependent variable used as instrumental variables and whether they were collapsed, respectively.

Stages indicate whether the 1- or 2-stage estimator was used.

Table 28 summarizes the possible inferences about the research hypotheses raised.

Table 21 – Hypotheses results

Hypothesis	Status	Hypothesis	Status
H3.1a	Inconclusive	H3.1b	Inconclusive
H3.2a	Inconclusive	H3.2b	Inconclusive
H3.3a	Inconclusive	H3.3b	Inconclusive
H3.4a	Inconclusive	H3.4b	Inconclusive
H3.5a	Inconclusive	H3.5b	Inconclusive
H3.6a	Non rejected	H3.6b	Non rejected

Note: Prepared by the author.

A possible explanation for the fact that only one hypothesis was not rejected is the fact that the sample encompasses relatively heterogeneous countries that, although they show a tendency towards the electronization of payments in general, still present peculiar behaviors in relation to certain instruments. For example, payment diaries indicate that countries such as Germany, Austria, and Japan have a considerably higher proportion of cash payments than other developed countries (Bagnall et al., 2016; Schmidt, 2016). In China, the popularity of fast payments is higher than in other countries, emerging or developed (Bech et al., 2018; Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures & World Bank, 2020; Frost et al., 2019). In the US and the Netherlands, the proportion of card payments is also higher than the world average, either because of the benefits for them to be used (frequent flyer programs, etc.), the superior ease of access to the instrument compared to other countries, or the low cost for consumers and merchants (Arango-Arango et al., 2018; Bagnall et al., 2016).

3.5 Final considerations

The paper contributes to research on retail payments by employing a broader sample, encompassing both developed countries and emerging countries, few times analyzed in previous papers. The study also contributes to the literature by analyzing the determinants of fast payments, one of the newest payment instruments in use, offered in an increasing number of jurisdictions, but still incipient or non-existent in most countries. Previous work generally looks at electronic or non-cash instruments, also addressed in the study.

Through panel data analysis with data from 2005 to 2020, it is concluded that countries that have a higher proportion of older people in the population tend to use more electronic and fast payments. The level of past usage, however, is the most important determinant of present usage. Even if it was possible to conclude on only one of the hypotheses, the result can serve as a subsidy for policies aimed at the electronization of payments or the implementation of fast payment instruments. It may also be useful for industry participants, guiding investments or improvements in the infrastructure needed to stimulate the use of electronic or innovative instruments.

As limitations, the payments data used, even if consolidated by the BIS, come from several countries and it is possible that there are different interpretations among

information providers, so that the comparison between countries may be hampered. The interval of the series, of only 16 years, may hinder the identification of longer term trends.

As future work, one could try to employ decision trees or clustering, for example, to identify countries with similar characteristics, filling a gap related to the analysis methods. Modeling the choice of instrument, in a logit panel for example, could also be a future work. Another possibility is to focus only on a specific country, identifying peculiar determinants. In Brazil, for example, there was the CPMF (Provisional Contribution on Financial Transactions), a tax whose incidence has the potential to directly discourage electronic payments. Competition among merchants is a variable that is difficult to obtain at a national level and standardized across countries and therefore could not be considered in this analysis, but future work could address this issue, as well as include other variables.

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4 How do Brazilians choose their payment instrument? An empirical analysis of the Brazilian case

4.1 Introduction

Payment instruments have been the subject of rapid innovation in recent decades, and the pandemic caused by Covid-19 seems to have accelerated this trend (Avdjiev et al., 2020; Bank of England, 2021). Physical cash, while still dominant in most countries, has been replaced by electronic forms of payment (Bech et al., 2018), offered by a variety of actors, not just financial ones. Bigtechs such as Google, Apple, and Facebook have started offering payment services through digital wallets, for example (Frost et al., 2019). Incentives and interventions by regulators are also happening. Emblematic cases are the regulations of interchange fees set in debit and credit card arrangements (Górka, 2018), the creation of fast instruments such as Pix in Brazil (Duarte et al., 2022; Lobo & Brandt, 2021) and FedNow in the US, and recently the intense discussion around central bank digital currencies (Bank for International Settlements et al., 2021; Kosse & Mattei, 2022).

Catalysts for these changes include technological innovations, which have reduced adoption costs and increased the mass of users needed to enable the development of new products, and changing user expectations regarding the speed and convenience of payments, increasing demand from users, who require services that are increasingly faster, cheaper, and easier to use, on par with what they have been offered in other technology services (Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016). Thus, understanding how payment instruments are chosen by users can be of interest to both market participants, who can use the results to inform investment decisions in infrastructure, technology, or marketing needed for the adoption of new instruments, and regulators, who can use the results to inform policies and regulations aimed at the electronization of payments or the deployment of payment instruments that better meet public objectives (Arango-Arango et al., 2015; Świecka et al., 2021).

As identified in the bibliometric analysis reported in study one (chapter 2), determinants of choice are the most common object in the literature related to retail payments, but as gaps, there are few papers involving emerging countries and employing alternative techniques. Payment diaries are one way to understand how instruments are chosen, usually commissioned by central banks. Few emerging countries conduct them regularly, but recently the Central Bank of Brazil (2021) released a report and microdata from Brazilian dailies. Thus, by aiming to identify determinants of the choice of payment instruments in a major emerging country and by applying multilevel logit, little employed in this context, the paper contributes to fill mentioned gaps.

Section 4.2 presents a brief literature review and postulates the hypotheses that guide the paper. Section 4.3 presents the research methodology, encompassing sample and data source, research variables and econometric model. Section 5.3 presents the research

results and, finally, section 5.4 presents the paper's final considerations.

4.2 Literature review and research hypotheses

4.2.1 Theoretical literature on the choice of payment instruments

As mentioned earlier, Keynes (1936) lists three reasons for holding cash: transactions, precaution, and speculation (or store of value). As an instrument of payment, one is primarily interested in the use of money for transactions. However, it is not trivial to dissociate the three mentioned uses and the demand for money eventually encompasses all of them.

The standard theory for the demand for money was proposed by Baumol (1952) and Tobin (1956) independently, now known as Baumol-Tobin or BT, better described in study four (chapter 5). The authors proposed that the demand for money depends on the interest rate level, the individual's income, the transaction costs of transferring (or withdrawing) resources from interest-bearing assets into the form of cash, and the average value of resources held in cash. They conclude that the demand for money is directly proportional to income and transaction costs and indirectly proportional to the interest rate.

Electronic instruments aimed at purchases, such as cards, are also addressed in the theoretical literature, since they constitute a two-sided market (Rochet & Tirole, 2002) and allow the establishment of interchange fees in order to encourage their use (Rochet, 2003). The model presented next, initially suggested by Baxter (1983), is based in Rochet (2003), but is also presented by many other authors, with minor modifications.

Considering p^B as the fee charged to consumers by issuers (institutions that issue cards for consumers), p^S as the fee charged to merchants by acquirers (institutions that connect merchants to card networks), c^B the marginal cost of issuers, c^S the marginal cost of acquirers, b^B and b^S the difference in net utility that consumers and merchants get in a card transaction in relation to a cash transaction, assuming perfect competition, $p^B = c^B$, since the unit price to consumers becomes equal to issuers' marginal cost. In a similar manner, assuming perfect competition, $p^S = c^S$, with unit price to merchants becoming equal to marginal cost to acquirers.

The total cost of a card transaction is then given by $c = c^S + c^B$. Assuming that a cash transaction is cost-less to the institutions (supposition that does not hold in practice), this total cost can also be interpreted as the incremental cost of a card transaction in relation to a cash transaction.

Social welfare would be maximized (that is, the usage of card would be socially efficient) whenever (1) $b^B + b^S \geq c$, but a card payment occurs only if (2) $b^B \geq p^B = c^B$ and $b^S \geq p^S = c^S$, which more restricted than (1). Assuming that the merchant earns a comparatively superior benefit from a card transaction in relation to the consumer (as additional sales, more safety against robbery, easier transaction conciliation, etc.), the merchant would be willing to finance part of the transaction cost to the consumer so that the card transaction can occur in more situations. Thus, the inefficiency can be corrected if the acquirer pays an interchange fee to the issuer, given by (3) $a_0 = b^S - c^S$, with

the aim at stimulating the usage of the electronic instrument, decreasing its cost to the consumer.

The net cost to the issuer becomes (4) $c^B + c^S - b^S = c - b^S$. Assuming perfect competition between issuers, this reduction in cost to issuers is totally forwarded to consumers (p^B becomes $c - b^S$) and each card transaction would occur if (5) $b^B \geq c - b^S$, that is equivalent to (1), the socially efficient condition. However, interchange fee a_0 is not always defined by card networks in an optimal level, giving rise to inefficiencies, leading to over or under utilization of the payment instrument and, thus, to need of regulation.

Bolt (2003), Wright (2004), Rochet & Wright (2010), Wang (2010), Mariotto & Verdier (2017) and many other authors relax conditions and assumptions and extend the model in many ways. Verdier (2011) presents a survey on the subject. In general, the conclusion is that the interchange fee is not optimal from the social point of view and consumer end up using more or less cards than would be desirable, depending on the assumptions in which the studies are based upon. Merchants, for example, would also end up accepting cards even though they may be more expensive, or would accept less cards than desirable.

4.2.2 Empirical studies on the choice of electronic payment instruments

As identified in the bibliometric analysis conducted in studies 1 (chapter 2), many studies have as object the determinants of choice. Payers' demographic (such as gender, age and education) and economical (such as income, type of employment relationship, etc.) characteristics, transaction characteristics (such as value of payment and type of merchant or payee) and perception of payers on payment instruments, are among the most frequent determinants considered in the literature.

Świecka et al. (2021) group these factors in seven groups: 1) transaction factors, such as type of product or place of transaction; 2) characteristics of instruments, such as their cost, ease of use and safety; 3) satisfaction with the use of the instrument; 4) demographic factors, such as gender, age and education; 5) knowledge about the instrument; 6) economical factors, such as income, way of receiving one's source of income, etc.; 7) other factors, such as acceptance by merchants, knowledge about finance, etc. Arango et al. (2015), on their turn, group these factors as 1) demographic; 2) perception in relation to payment instruments; 3) transaction factors; 4) characteristics of debit and credit cards; 5) incentives. Other authors make classifications in line with the ones just presented. In my study, I group factors as demographic and financial (groups 4 and 6 of Świecka et al. (2021) and 1 of Arango et al. (2015)) and transaction characteristics (groups 1 of Świecka et al. (2021) and 3 of Arango et al. (2015)).

4.2.2.1 Demographic and financial determinants

Demographic and financial factors are the most common, and have been considered in the work of Świecka et al. (2021), Deufel et al. (2019), Fujiki & Tanaka (2018), Bagnall et al. (2016), Goczek & Witkowski (2016) and Arango-Arango et al. (2015), for example. Table 22 consolidates the demographic and financial determinants found in the literature, as well as the relationships reported.

Table 22 – Demographic and financial determinants

Determinant	Authors (e.g.)	Reported relationship	Dependent variable
Gender	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Fujiki (2020),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Deufel et al. (2019),	Not determined	Inst. in real transact.
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016),	Not determined	Card ownership
	Arango et al. (2015)	Determined	Inst. in diary
Age	Świecka et al. (2021),	Negative	Inst. in survey
	Fujiki (2020),	Negative	Inst. em survey
	Deufel et al. (2019),	Not determined	Inst. in real transact.
	Bagnall et al. (2016),	Negative	Inst. in diary
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016),	Negative	Card ownership
Education	Arango et al. (2015)	Not determined	Inst. in diary
	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Bagnall et al. (2016),	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	Positive	Card ownership
Location	Arango et al. (2015)	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	Positive	Card ownership
Marital status	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
Employment relationship	Arango et al. (2015)	Determined	Inst. in diary
Household members	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	Negative	Card ownership
Income or savings	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
	Fujiki (2020),	Positive	Inst. em survey
	Bagnall et al. (2016)	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	Positive	Card ownership
Indebtedness	Arango et al. (2015)	Not determined	Inst. in diary
	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
Use of financial services	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
Use of internet	Goczek & Witkowski (2016)	Positive	Card ownership

Note. Source: author'ss elaboration.

The authors briefly find that electronic payment instruments are more likely to be employed by payers who are male, younger, more educated, have higher incomes, live in large urban areas, belong to smaller households, are financially savvy, and are users of financial services and the internet. Payers with these characteristics would be more likely to try out new instruments and, realizing their benefits, use them more often than cash. This would be the profile of people more likely to try new products and services. Thus, hypotheses H4.1a to H4.7a are postulated:

- H4.1a: Payers' gender is a determinant of their choice of electronic instruments.
- H4.2a: Younger payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.3a: Higher income payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.4a: More educated payers are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.5a: Payers from more urbanized and developed regions are more likely to choose electronic instruments.

- H4.6a: Payers’ marital status is a determinant of the choice of electronic instruments.
- H4.7a: The employment status of payers is a determinant of the choice of electronic instruments.

Not all determinants listed in table 22 gave rise to hypotheses because not all were considered in the opinion survey whose data is the basis for the empirical tests, as described in section 5.2.1. Thus, based on the available characteristics of the respondents who answered the survey, additional hypotheses H4.8a to H4.10a are postulated:

- H4.8a: Payers who receive their main source of income on account are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.9a: Payers who have experienced cell phone shopping are more likely to choose electronic instruments.
- H4.10a: Payers who have an account with a financial or payment institution are more likely to choose electronic instruments.

In these cases, it could be argued that payers who receive on account would be more likely to use electronic instruments, since in order to use cash in their transactions, they would need to withdraw funds in advance, while those who receive cash, in turn, would need to deposit funds to use electronic instruments. The previous experience with cell phone shopping shows experience with technology and may indicate that the user would find it easier to use and choose an electronic instrument. Finally, having an account is almost a prerequisite for using an electronic instrument, and users who have one would be more likely to choose them.

4.2.2.2 Determinants related to payment characteristics

The second group of factors is less common than the first, as it generally depends on consumers being asked to fill out a payment journal or using granular purchase data provided by retailers. Table 23 consolidates the determinants related to payment characteristics found in the literature, as well as the reported relationships.

Table 23 – Determinants related to payment characteristics

Determinant	Authors (e.g.)	Reported relationship	Dependent variable
Value	Świecka et al. (2021),	Positive	Inst. in survey
	Stavins (2018),	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Bagnall et al. (2016)	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Wang & Wolman (2016),	Positive	Inst. in real transaction
	Arango et al. (2015)	Positive	Inst. in diary
	Klee (2008)	Positive	Inst. in real transaction
Sector of merchant	Świecka et al. (2021),	Determined	Inst. in survey
	Stavins (2018)	Determined	Inst. in diary
	Bagnall et al. (2016)	Not determined	Inst. in diary
	Arango et al. (2015)	Not determined	Inst. in diary
Type of product or service	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey
Place or type of merchant.	Świecka et al. (2021),	Not determined	Inst. in survey

Determinant	Authors (e.g.)	Reported relationship	Dependent variable
Discount	Stavins (2018)	Determined	Inst. in diary
	Stavins (2018)	Negative	Inst. in diary

Source: Author's elaboration.

The value of the payment is the determinant found in most of the papers. In general, it is perceived that the lower the payment amount, the greater the use of cash, and the higher the payment amount, the more likely users are to opt for electronic instruments. Thus, the following hypothesis is postulated:

H4.1b: The probability that electronic instruments are chosen is higher for higher value payments.

The sector of operation of the establishment or the payee for which the payment is made is also a considered determinant. In establishments focused on groceries or for paying transportation costs, for example, cash would be used more. Payments for the purchase of durable goods or to pay for housing, for example, would lead users to choose electronic instruments more often. Świecka et al. (2021), for example, find that electronic instruments are proportionally more used for purchases of clothing and durable goods. These considerations give rise to the following hypothesis:

H4.2b: The sector in which the establishment or payee operates is a determinant of instrument choice.

The type of establishment or payee (whether the payment was made in a physical store, online store, to an individual, to a liberal professional, for payment for a service, to a church, NGO, donation or to the government) would also influence the choice of instrument. This determinant is also associated with where the payment, purchase or transfer is made. Świecka et al. (2021), for example, find that electronic instruments are proportionally used more in gas stations, supermarkets, and shopping malls. Thus, the following hypothesis is postulated:

H4.3b: The type of establishment or payment is the determinant of the choice of instrument.

The payment condition, whether cash or forward, would also influence the choice of instrument. Cash, for example, is hardly suitable for installment payments, which are generally made with electronic instruments. This would be a typically Brazilian determinant, since in most countries financing and terms are not granted by retailers, but by financial institutions (card issuers or banks via personal loans). In Brazil, for historical reasons, commerce has assumed the role of term and credit provider for final consumers, with retailers themselves bearing the cost of money over time and, depending on the payment instrument, the cost of granting credit. Thus, even without direct support from the literature, the following hypothesis is postulated:

H4.4b: The payment condition is a determinant of the choice of payment instrument.

As in the previous section, not all the determinants listed in table 23 gave rise to hypotheses because not all of them were considered in the survey whose data are the basis for the empirical tests, as described in section 5.2.1)

4.3 Methodology

To test the hypotheses listed in section 4.2.2, primarily multilevel logit regressions (Finch et al., 2014; Hox et al., 2017) will be employed, as the same payer can make multiple payments. To check the robustness of the results, logit regressions with pooled data and multinomial logit are employed. The packages lme4 (logit multinomial), nnet (logit multinomial), and margins (marginal effects) were employed.

4.3.1 Sample and data source

The data come from an opinion poll commissioned by the Central Bank of Brazil (with a confidence level of 95% and margin of error of 2.5%) as part of the project to evaluate the instant payment solution, which culminated with the implementation of Pix in November 2020 (Banco Central do Brasil, 2021). 1,519 people (segmented by geographic region, age, gender, marital status, family income, education and employment status) and 615 commercial establishments (segmented by geographic region, industry and number of employees) were interviewed between 04/26/2019 and 05/12/2019 and between 04/27/2019 and 05/15/2019, respectively, with questions about the perception and preference for payment instruments, in addition to questions about the possession or not of an account in a financial or payment institution, whether the person had ever made a purchase via cell phone, among others. The 1,519 respondents were asked to fill out a payment diary for seven days between April 27, 2019 and June 12, 2019, at the respondent's choice. In this diary, the person should record all the payments made in the period, noting the amount, the instrument used, where the payment was made, which sector of the establishment, and the payment condition (whether cash or on credit). 1,379 diaries were filled out and collected, totaling 16,712 payments recorded. The microdata were made available, as were the questionnaires used in the research. No academic papers that have used this data before have been identified.

4.3.2 Study variables

4.3.2.1 Dependent variable

The dependent variable of the study is the payment instrument chosen by journal respondents in each of the 16,712 payments reported. The main instruments listed in the survey were cash, credit cards, debit cards, and prepaid cards. Table 24 shows the amount of payments made with each of the instruments. Most of the payments were made with cash and cards, with considerably fewer payments recorded with other instruments.

As there are 12 types of instruments, cash and check were grouped as non-electronic instruments and the others were grouped as electronic. Thus, the dependent variable considered is a binary variable that assumes the value 1 (one) if the instrument used was electronic and 0 (zero) if cash or check was used. The two penultimate rows of table 24 present the descriptive analysis of the value as a result of aggregation. Payments made with electronic instruments account for 22.61% of the total, while paper payments account for just over 77.39%, with cash representing 76.61% of the total. In other words, cash is still the dominant payment instrument in terms of quantity in the country. Studies such

Table 24 – Number and value of payments per instrument in the diaries

Instrument	N	Mean	Medn.	Min.	Max.	SD	VC	Kurt.	Skew.	% of obs.
Cash	12805	81.05	30.00	0.30	8000.00	165.98	0.49	448.04	12.92	76.62%
Debit card	1963	128.99	65.00	2.00	3000.00	210.94	0.61	53.85	5.79	11.75%
Credit card	1155	187.53	100.00	2.00	5200.00	306.86	0.61	93.55	7.53	6.91%
Prepaid card	235	33.95	9.00	2.00	2050.00	146.46	0.23	155.27	11.58	1.41%
Meal card	125	111.57	30.00	1.00	900.00	181.70	0.61	8.60	2.45	0.75%
Cheque	120	162.02	57.98	1.50	2386.00	327.19	0.50	26.42	4.54	0.72%
Boleto	92	537.21	307.50	13.00	3300.00	671.87	0.80	8.80	2.40	0.55%
Direct debit	77	291.75	150.00	12.88	2000.00	388.58	0.75	9.94	2.58	0.46%
Store card	50	300.98	175.00	20.00	1850.00	323.40	0.93	11.63	2.47	0.30%
Book transfers	40	467.13	335.00	20.00	1525.00	439.69	1.06	3.18	1.17	0.24%
Other	24	225.81	52.75	4.20	1300.00	365.72	0.62	5.73	1.91	0.14%
DOC	10	242.30	100.00	37.00	900.00	327.70	0.74	3.25	1.47	0.06%
TED	10	290.78	100.00	8.00	1100.00	392.25	0.74	3.15	1.37	0.06%
NA	6	158.53	47.89	20.00	700.00	267.66	0.59	4.07	1.72	0.04%
Nonelectronic	12934	81.83	30.00	0.30	8000.00	168.38	0.49	422.69	12.60	77.39%
Electronic	3778	160.92	73.00	1.00	5200.00	282.77	0.57	63.87	6.11	22.61%
Total	16712	99.71	40.00	0.30	8000.00	202.75	2.03	213.02	9.59	100.00%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. Mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV), kurtosis (Kurt.) and skewness (Skew.) were calculated on the value of transactions with each payment instrument.

as Bagnall et al. (2016), Arango-Arango et al. (2018) and Bech et al. (2018) show that in several countries, developed or emerging, this is still the reality.

For the application of multinomial logit as a technique to check the robustness of the results, the instruments were grouped into six categories: 1) cash, 2) checks, 3) debit cards (aggregating also prepaid cards and food vouchers), 4) credit cards (encompassing also store cards and virtual wallets), 5) transfers (encompassing TEDs, DOCs and transfers to the same bank) and 6) boletos (aggregating also automatic debit). As table 24 shows, some instruments are little used and an analysis with all the instruments individually would not be very illuminating.

4.3.2.2 Independent variables

To test the hypotheses listed in sections 4.2.2.1 and 4.2.2.2, the variables considered in the survey mentioned in section 5.2.1, were used, grouped according to section 4.2.2. The first group corresponds to demographic and financial variables, and the second group corresponds to variables related to payment characteristics. Some unrepresentative categories of certain variables were grouped to similar categories to facilitate the description, interpretation and visualization of the results.

The demographic and financial variables considered in the research were as follows: gender (GENDER), age (AGE), income (INCOME), education (EDUCATION), region (REGION), marital status (MARITAL), employment relationship (EMPREL) and means of receipt of the main source of income (SOURCE), all categorical variables, and binary variables indicating whether the respondent has ever made a purchase with a cell phone (CEL) and whether he or she has an account with a financial or payment institution (ACCOUNT). The payment characteristics considered were the TYPE and SECTOR of the establishment, the condition (CONDITION) and the VALUE of the payment. Tables 25 and 26 present, for each independent variable, the percentage of individuals in the sample who fit into each category of each variable and, for each category, the percentage of payments made with electronic and non-electronic instruments. Table 24 presents the

Table 25 – Descriptive statistics of demographic variables

Variable	Categories	Perc. sample (a)	Perc. electronic (b)	Perc. nonelectronic (c)
GENDER	F	50.63%	20.39%	79.61%
	M	49.37%	24.87%	75.13%
AGE	18-25	23.24%	19.17%	80.83%
	26-35	25.02%	24.12%	75.88%
	36-45	26.07%	23.30%	76.70%
	46-60	25.67%	23.57%	76.43%
INCOME	00-02 MW	21.66%	12.57%	87.43%
	02-03 MW	20.74%	16.34%	83.66%
	03-04 MW	21.59%	24.01%	75.99%
	04-05 MW	11.59%	27.45%	72.55%
	05-10 MW	22.45%	31.91%	68.09%
	10+ MW	1.97%	57.73%	42.27%
EDUCATION	no educ.	1.65%	8.79%	91.21%
	complete fundamental	27.58%	13.75%	86.25%
	complete middle	55.30%	22.94%	77.06%
	complete undergraduate	13.43%	36.14%	63.86%
	graduate	2.04%	39.71%	60.29%
REGION	CO	7.97%	19.88%	80.12%
	N	10.60%	15.08%	84.92%
	NE	26.86%	19.63%	80.37%
	S	14.22%	32.38%	67.62%
	SE	40.36%	25.73%	74.27%
MARITAL	married	41.15%	24.41%	75.59%
	divorced	6.52%	27.35%	72.65%
	single	49.90%	20.48%	79.52%
	widow	2.44%	25.74%	74.26%
EMPREL	retired	5.51%	24.71%	75.29%
	autonomous	32.43%	19.90%	80.10%
	unemployed	17.28%	16.01%	83.99%
	employee	30.17%	25.16%	74.84%
	entrepreneur	5.18%	36.26%	63.74%
	intern	1.26%	18.75%	81.25%
	civil servant	6.31%	34.33%	65.67%
	lib. profes.	1.86%	18.11%	81.89%
SOURCE	cheque	0.53%	30.86%	69.14%
	cash	56.81%	16.84%	83.16%
	in an account	40.16%	31.36%	68.64%
	other	2.50%	15.30%	84.70%
CEL	no mobile purchase	70.14%	17.07%	82.93%
	previous mobile purchase	29.86%	35.49%	64.51%
ACCOUNT	no bank account	22.71%	9.68%	90.32%
	has bank account	77.29%	26.01%	73.99%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. a) Distribution in the sample, with $n = 1,519$; b) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with electronic instruments among respondents in each category; c) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with nonelectronic instruments among respondents in each category. MW = minimum wage; CO = Center-West, N = North, NE = North-East, S = South, SE = South-East.

descriptive analysis of the value of payments, the only numeric independent variable (the others are categorical variables).

Although the variables in each of the two groups of determinants (demographic variables and payment characteristics) may present some degree of correlation (for example, it is expected that people with higher education have higher income), it does not prove to be problematic, as evidenced by the VIF (variance inflation factor), less than 2 for all variables, considering the degrees of freedom.

Moreover, as the number of categories in all variables totaled more than 60, the use of principal component analysis followed by logit regression was considered, but no representative components were found (the most representative component explains less than 6% of the total variance). Thus, this approach was discarded.

Table 26 – Descriptive statistics for transaction characteristics variables

Variable	Categories	Perc. sample (a)	Perc. electronic (b)	Perc. nonelectronic (c)
SECTOR	durable goods	1.65%	46.74%	53.26%
	construction	0.11%	31.58%	68.42%
	finance	1.07%	41.01%	58.99%
	groceries	35.46%	21.53%	78.47%
	housing	2.26%	17.51%	82.49%
	other	1.33%	15.77%	84.23%
	people	0.05%	NA	100.00%
	service	26.27%	23.26%	76.74%
	transportation	25.91%	18.34%	81.66%
	taxes	0.90%	30.46%	69.54%
	apparel	4.99%	39.81%	60.19%
TYPE	government	0.62%	40.78%	59.22%
	store	72.73%	25.26%	74.74%
	online	0.47%	53.16%	46.84%
	people	2.45%	12.47%	87.53%
CONDITION	service	23.73%	14.38%	85.62%
	cash purchase	92.93%	17.11%	82.89%
	term or install.	7.07%	95.08%	4.92%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. a) Distribution in the sample, with n = 1,519; b) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with electronic instruments among respondents in each category; c) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with nonelectronic instruments among respondents in each category.

4.3.3 Econometric model

The econometric model of the multilevel logit regression employed in the paper is presented in equation 4.1. The model is structured with two levels: 1) payers and 2) payments, where each payer can record in his diary several payments.

$$\ln\left(\frac{Prob(ELECTRONIC_{ij})}{1 - Prob(ELECTRONIC_{ij})}\right) = \beta_1 GENDER_i + \beta_2 AGE_i + \beta_3 INCOME_i + \beta_4 EDUCATION_i + \beta_5 REGION_i + \beta_6 MARITAL_i + \beta_7 EMPREL_i + \beta_8 SOURCE_i + \beta_9 CEL_i + \beta_{10} ACCOUNT_i + \beta_{11} VALUE_{ij} + \beta_{12} SECTOR_{ij} + \beta_{13} TYPE_{ij} + \beta_{14} CONDITION_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij}$$

(4.1)

where $ELECTRONIC_{ij}$ is a dependent binary variable that takes the value 1 if the ij-th payment recorded in the diaries was made with an electronic instrument and 0 if it was made with a non-electronic one, according to section 5.2.2.1. The independent variables are those presented in section 5.2.2.2, with subscript i corresponding to the characteristics of each payment recorded by each respondent j. The variables where there is only the subscript j, relate only to the respondent and are constant for all payments recorded by a given respondent.

The equation that applies to the pooled and multinomial logit, employed for robustness as described below, is presented in equation :

$$\ln\left(\frac{\text{Prob}(\text{ELECTRONIC}_i)}{1 - \text{Prob}(\text{ELECTRONIC}_i)}\right) = \beta_1\text{GENDER}_i + \beta_2\text{AGE}_i + \beta_3\text{INCOME}_i + \beta_4\text{EDUCATION}_i + \beta_5\text{REGION}_i + \beta_6\text{MARITAL}_i + \beta_7\text{EMPREL}_i + \beta_8\text{SOURCE}_i + \beta_9\text{CEL}_i + \beta_{10}\text{ACCOUNT}_i + \beta_{11}\text{VALUE}_i + \beta_{12}\text{SECTOR}_i + \beta_{13}\text{TYPE}_i + \beta_{14}\text{CONDITION}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4.2)$$

4.3.4 Methods for checking the robustness of the results

To check the robustness of the results, pooled logit, a technique used in most works on the use of payment journal instruments (Arango et al., 2015; Bagnall et al., 2016; Stavins, 2018), and multinomial logit, were employed to check the effect of the variables not only in relation to the classification between electronic instruments or not, but in relation to more granular categories, described in section 5.2.2.1.

4.4 Results analysis

I employed the lme4 R package (Bates et al., 2015) for the multilevel logit approach, base R (R Core Team, 2020) for the pooled approach, and the nnet R package (Venables & Ripley, 2002) for the multinomial approach. Marginal effects were calculated with the margins R package (Leeper, 2021).

4.4.1 Results of the multilevel logit regression

Column 1 of table 27 presents the result of the multilevel logit regression, while column 2 presents the average marginal effects (average effect on the probability of the dependent variable, calculated over all observations, as a function of the change in the value of an independent variable). The intraclass correlation (ICC) of 0.46 shows that considering the tiered structure is important here, since the correlation between the choices of electronic instruments by the same payer is considerable. In other words, the impact of bundling payments is relatively high. The ICC, a measure between 0 and 1, measures the degree of correlation within groups. The higher it is, the greater the proportion of the total variance explained by the intra-group variance.

Table 27 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multilevel and pooled logit

	Dependent variable			
	electronic			
	Multilevel logit (1)	Average marginal effects (multilevel) (2)	Pooled logit (3)	Average marginal effects (pooled) (4)
VALUE	0.002*** (0.0002)	0.0001*** (0.00002)	0.001*** (0.0001)	0.0002*** (0.00002)
SECTOR construction	-1.999** (0.814)	-0.154*** (0.045)	-1.435* (0.792)	-0.139*** (0.053)
SECTOR finance	-0.213 (0.304)	-0.022 (0.031)	0.151 (0.250)	0.021 (0.035)
SECTOR groceries	-0.600*** (0.206)	-0.058*** (0.172)	-0.390** (0.022)	-0.049** (0.023)
SECTOR housing	-1.246*** (0.276)	-0.109*** (0.025)	-0.971*** (0.234)	-0.105*** (0.026)
SECTOR other	-0.382 (0.327)	-0.038 (0.033)	-0.388 (0.272)	-0.049 (0.033)
SECTOR people	-13.410 (428.208)	-0.274*** (0.032)	-11.020 (102.149)	-0.264*** (0.025)
SECTOR service	-0.388* (0.207)	-0.039* (0.022)	-0.195 (0.173)	-0.025 (0.023)
SECTOR transportation	-0.425** (0.213)	-0.042* (0.022)	-0.241 (0.178)	-0.031 (0.024)
SECTOR taxes	-0.951** (0.435)	-0.087** (0.037)	-0.983** (0.384)	-0.106*** (0.036)
SECTOR apparel	-0.045 (0.232)	-0.005 (0.025)	0.050 (0.193)	0.007 (0.027)
TYPE store	-0.671 (0.418)	-0.072 (0.049)	-1.053*** (0.368)	-0.165** (0.067)
TYPE NA	-0.405 (0.728)	-0.045 (0.080)	-0.130 (0.596)	-0.023 (0.107)
TYPE online	0.836 (0.530)	0.108 (0.067)	0.387 (0.458)	0.073 (0.085)
TYPE person	-1.485*** (0.462)	-0.140*** (0.051)	-1.734*** (0.408)	-0.238*** (0.069)
TYPE service	-1.232*** (0.425)	-0.121** (0.049)	-1.524*** (0.373)	-0.218*** (0.067)
CONDITION NA	-0.895 (1.121)	-0.075 (0.077)	-1.612 (1.084)	-0.130*** (0.046)
CONDITION term or in install.	4.933*** (0.169)	0.685*** (0.016)	4.592*** (0.143)	0.740*** (0.010)
GENDER M	0.223** (0.110)	0.022** (0.010)	0.268*** (0.048)	0.032*** (0.006)
AGE 26-35	0.156	0.017	0.182**	0.021**

Table 27 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multilevel and pooled logit

	(0.165)	(0.015)	(0.071)	(0.008)
AGE 36-45	0.265	0.024	0.190**	0.022**
	(0.175)	(0.016)	(0.077)	(0.009)
AGE 46-60	0.292	0.030*	0.282***	0.033***
	(0.186)	(0.017)	(0.081)	(0.009)
INCOME 02-03 SM	-0.096	-0.006	0.047	0.005
	(0.189)	(0.016)	(0.082)	(0.009)
INCOME 03-04 SM	0.370**	0.035**	0.391***	0.045***
	(0.177)	(0.016)	(0.080)	(0.009)
INCOME 04-05 SM	0.354*	0.032*	0.357***	0.040***
	(0.204)	(0.019)	(0.090)	(0.010)
INCOME 05-10 SM	0.551***	0.052***	0.581***	0.070***
	(0.177)	(0.016)	(0.079)	(0.009)
INCOME 10+ SM	1.443***	0.161***	1.420***	0.207***
	(0.348)	(0.046)	(0.158)	(0.028)
EDUCATION comp. fund.	0.360	0.027	0.812***	0.067***
	(0.509)	(0.035)	(0.306)	(0.020)
EDUCATION comp. high	0.791	0.066*	1.131***	0.103***
	(0.504)	(0.035)	(0.304)	(0.020)
EDUCATION comp. under.	1.004*	0.086**	1.322***	0.128***
	(0.523)	(0.038)	(0.309)	(0.021)
EDUCATION comp. grad.	0.939	0.082	1.279***	0.122***
	(0.645)	(0.053)	(0.331)	(0.026)
REGION N	-0.056	-0.004	-0.259**	-0.027**
	(0.238)	(0.020)	(0.107)	(0.011)
REGION NE	-0.060	-0.007	-0.116	-0.013
	(0.196)	(0.017)	(0.088)	(0.010)
REGION S	0.749***	0.075***	0.540***	0.069***
	(0.213)	(0.021)	(0.096)	(0.012)
REGION SE	0.339*	0.038**	0.352***	0.043***
	(0.193)	(0.017)	(0.085)	(0.010)
MARITAL divorced	0.113	0.008	0.003	0.0003
	(0.218)	(0.020)	(0.092)	(0.011)
MARITAL single	0.083	0.009	0.079	0.009
	(0.124)	(0.011)	(0.054)	(0.006)
MARITAL widower	-0.091	-0.008	-0.001	-0.0001
	(0.340)	(0.030)	(0.155)	(0.018)
EMPREL autonomous	0.372	0.032	0.349***	0.038***
	(0.258)	(0.022)	(0.117)	(0.012)
EMPREL unemployed	0.345	0.033	0.459***	0.052***
	(0.288)	(0.025)	(0.129)	(0.014)
EMPREL employee	0.283	0.029	0.395***	0.044***
	(0.255)	(0.021)	(0.113)	(0.012)
EMPREL businessman	0.347	0.027	0.347**	0.038**

Table 27 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multilevel and pooled logit

	(0.321)	(0.029)	(0.142)	(0.016)
EMPREL trainee	-0.224	-0.017	0.004	0.0004
	(0.519)	(0.040)	(0.237)	(0.024)
EMPREL civil servant	0.178	0.014	0.177	0.019
	(0.283)	(0.024)	(0.132)	(0.014)
EMPREL indep. prof.	0.006	0.001	-0.011	-0.001
	(0.476)	(0.040)	(0.203)	(0.020)
SOURCE cash	-0.819	-0.080	-0.570**	-0.069*
	(0.640)	(0.070)	(0.274)	(0.038)
SOURCE in an account	-0.109	-0.011	0.001	0.0001
	(0.640)	(0.071)	(0.275)	(0.038)
SOURCE other	-1.038	-0.097	-0.343	-0.044
	(0.760)	(0.077)	(0.334)	(0.044)
CEL	0.871***	0.086***	0.604***	0.077***
	(0.120)	(0.012)	(0.050)	(0.007)
ACCOUNT	0.639***	0.054***	0.558***	0.060***
	(0.163)	(0.013)	(0.082)	(0.008)
Constant	-3.110***		-2.906***	
	(1.024)		(0.605)	
Observations	16,545	16,545	16,545	16,545
Log Likelihood	-5,399.863	-6,388.059	-6,388.059	

Note. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. Standard error in parentheses.

Source: Author's elaboration. The first and third columns correspond to the results of the multilevel logit regression and with pooled data, respectively, where the dependent variable = 1 if a given payment was made with an electronic instrument.

The second and fourth columns correspond to the average marginal effects of the multilevel logit and the logit with pooled data, respectively.

The first level is payer and the second level corresponds to individual payments, with each payer recording several payments.

Base categories for the independent variables:

GENDER = F; AGE = 18-25; INCOME = 00-02 MW; EDUCATION = unschooled;

REGION = CO; MARITAL = married; EMPREL = retired; SOURCE = Cheque.

SECTOR = durable goods; TYPE = government; CONDITION = cash payment.

Since the "male" category of the variable GENDER is significant, it is possible to infer that males are about 2.2% more likely to make payments with electronic instruments than female respondents. Thus, it is not possible to reject hypothesis H4.1a, that is, it can be inferred that gender is a determinant of the choice of electronic instruments in Brazil. This result is in line with the findings of [Deufel et al. \(2019\)](#), although the authors only consider online purchases. [Świecka et al. \(2021\)](#), on the other hand, find no relationship between gender and instrument choice. [Arango et al. \(2015\)](#) show that men, compared to women, prefer credit cards to debit cards, but are indifferent about cash.

Evaluating the coefficients of the categories of the AGE variable, it is concluded that people who are older are more likely to choose electronic instruments than the base group, 18 to 25 years old, contrary to expectations, although there is significance in the marginal effects only in the 46 to 60 years old category (probability higher by about 3%). Thus, there is no evidence to support hypothesis H4.2a, that younger people would be more likely to try electronic instruments. This result goes against what is reported in most of the considered literature ([Bagnall et al., 2016](#); [Fujiki, 2020](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#); [Świecka et al., 2021](#)). It is possible to speculate that in Brazil, younger people would have more difficulty accessing electronic instruments, as they are beginning their trajectories in the labor market and realize lower income than more experienced groups.

In relation to INCOME, as expected, people with higher income (the base category is 0 to 2 minimum wages), because they have access to a greater variety of instruments, are more likely to choose electronic instruments, except in the stratum immediately following the base category (2 to 3 MW), but not significantly so. In the category of those earning more than 10 MW, the probability that they will opt for electronic instruments is about 16.1% higher than the members of the base category. These people would also tend to make higher value payments, typically conducted on electronic instruments. Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.3a. The result is in line with the results identified in the literature ([Bagnall et al., 2016](#); [Fujiki, 2020](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#)), which also report an increase in the use of electronic instruments as the payer's income rises.

In terms of education (EDUCATION), there is also no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.4a, that more educated people would be more likely to opt for electronic instruments (the base category of the variable is people with no education), although the category of those with primary and post-secondary education does not show significance. Among those with college degrees, they are about 8.6% more likely to opt for electronic instruments than those with no education. Schooling, similarly to income, would reflect the easier access to electronic instruments for the more educated and less favored population, while the less educated and less favored population would stick to traditional instruments, often for lack of choice. The result for the relationship between schooling and instrument choice is also in line with the literature considered ([Arango et al., 2015](#); [Bagnall et al., 2016](#); [Goczek & Witkowski, 2016](#)).

The region of the country (REGION) is also a significant determinant as to the South and Southeast regions, whose residents would have a higher propensity (of around 7.5% and 3.8%, respectively) to choose electronic instruments (relative to the base category Center-West), reflecting higher income and education or greater availability of electronic means. Despite the difficulty in distributing cash, people in the North show less propensity to make electronic payments than those in the Center-West, possibly because

of the difficulty in accessing electronic instruments, which often require access to the Internet, less common in this region of the country (and also in the Center-West). Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.5a. Although the variable considered here does not identify the city size of the respondents, it is known that the Southeast and South regions are the most urbanized in the country. The result is in line with [Goczek & Witkowski \(2016\)](#).

The marital status of the respondent (MARITAL; "married" as the base category) did not prove significant. The result is in line with [Świecka et al. \(2021\)](#), who also find no significant relationship between payer marital status and instrument choice. Employment status (EMPREL), similarly, is also not significant, although virtually all categories are more likely to choose electronic payments than respondents in the base category (retirees), with the exception of interns. The source of receipt of income (SOURCE) was also not significant. Thus, it is not possible to conclude on hypotheses H4.6a to H4.8a.

The past use of a cell phone to make a purchase (CEL), in turn, proved to be a strong determinant in the choice of electronic instruments. Those who already have this experience are about 8.6% more likely to choose electronic instruments than those who have never used a cell phone for this purpose. Thus, this is a strong indication that once people master the technology and realize its benefits, they tend to stick to the habit. There is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.9a.

Finally, the possession of an account with a financial or payment institution (ACCOUNT) also proved to be a significant determinant, with those who had an account being 5.4% more likely to opt for electronic payments, as expected. Since much of the electronic instruments are account-based, the original deposit of funds into these accounts would facilitate the use of these instruments. People who receive money would first need to deposit their money in an account and only then use electronic instruments. Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.10a. Since the last three characteristics were not used in the identified literature, comparison with the literature results is impaired.

Regarding the variables related to payment characteristics, as expected, transaction value is a strong determinant of the choice of electronic instruments. For every extra real in the payment amount, the propensity of users to opt for electronic instruments increases by 0.01%. Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.1b. This result is also in line with the literature ([Arango et al., 2015](#); [Bagnall et al., 2016](#); [Klee, 2008](#); [Stavins, 2018](#); [Świecka et al., 2021](#); [Wang & Wolman, 2016](#)), with all identified studies reporting increased use of electronic instruments as a function of purchase value.

Several categories related to the sector in which the commercial establishment operates, in turn, present a significant coefficient, indicating that there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.2b. In all sectors, the probability of using cash payments is higher than in the base category (durable goods). Notably, when payment is made between people, there is a 27.4% higher probability of using traditional instruments than when payment involves the base category, probably because several of the instruments are not accepted by people, such as cards and bills of exchange. Similarly, payments related to spending on construction (15.4%), housing (10.9%), services (3.9%), transportation (4.2%) and groceries (5.8%) also favor the choice of traditional instruments, possibly because several of these categories relate to everyday expenses, while the base category (durable goods) would be associated with less frequent expenses, usually paid on credit, an attribute

in which electronic instruments are considerably better evaluated than traditional ones. The result is in line with [Świecka et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Stavins \(2018\)](#), who identify that the sector in which the establishment operates is one of the factors that determine the type of instrument chosen.

The TYPE of outlet also proved to be a significant determinant of the choice of electronic instruments. When payments are made in all categories except online stores, there is less propensity to choose electronic instruments than in the base category (government). Only when purchases are online is there a higher propensity (10.8%) to use electronic instruments, as expected, but the coefficient is not significant. Payments to persons (14.0%) and services (12.1%) stand out. Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.3b. [Świecka et al. \(2021\)](#), in turn, finds no significant relationship between the type of the establishment or the good or service and the choice of instrument.

CONDITION is also a significant determinant for the choice of electronic instruments. Users tend to choose electronic instruments 68.5% more likely when payments are made in installments or installments, compared to cash payments (base category). In fact, non-electronic instruments such as cash are poorly suited for installment or term payments and would be better suited to everyday spending paid in cash. Thus, there is no evidence to reject hypothesis H4.4b. As mentioned, no studies were found in the literature that have considered this purchase variable, possibly because it is a peculiar characteristic of the Brazilian market. In Brazil, the payment condition is negotiated with the establishment, while in other countries eventual financing is obtained through financial institutions, such as credit card issuers or personal loan providers, for example.

Table 28 summarizes the possible inferences on the postulated hypotheses.

Table 28 – Results of hypotheses

Hypothesis	Status	Hypothesis	Status
H4.1a	Not rejected	H4.1b	Not rejected
H4.2a	Inconclusive	H4.2b	Not rejected
H4.3a	Not rejected	H4.3b	Not rejected
H4.4a	Not rejected	H4.4b	Not rejected
H4.5a	Not rejected		
H4.6a	Inconclusive		
H4.7a	Inconclusive		
H4.8a	Inconclusive		
H4.9a	Not rejected		
H4.10a	Not rejected		

Note: Author's elaboration.

4.4.2 Results using methods for robustness

Column 3 of table 27 presents the results for the pooled logit (with marginal effects in column 4), as per equation 4.2. The results corroborate the findings reported in section 4.4.1. In the simple stacking, there are more significant variables, as expected. The demographic variables age, income, education, region, attachment, and source, especially, are significant when all payments are pooled, but lose significance when the level structure of observations (multiple payments from the same individual) is taken into account. That

is, the proportion of the variance of the chosen instrument that is due to characteristics of the individual is high.

Table 29 presents the results of the multinomial logit. The results show that not all variables are important for the choice of all instruments. Value is an important variable for choosing all the instruments considered over cash (base category), especially for bills of exchange and transfers. Regarding the other characteristics of payments, SECTOR and type of establishment show specific behaviors. For example, the probability of payments via transfers or checks increases in the construction, finance, housing, and services SECTOR. The likelihood that cards are used for payments at online establishments increases considerably, while that of checks decreases. The likelihood of using bills of exchange and transfers in physical stores decreases. Checks are the only instrument that is more likely to be used than cash for payments to people. All instruments are more likely to be used for installment purchases than cash.

Among the demographic and financial variables, gender is an important determinant for credit card and check use, but not for the other instruments. Age is important for cards, but not for the other instruments. Income is important for bills and cards and education for all. Account ownership is important only for cards and cell phone use only for boletos, debit cards and transfers. Thus, in relation to the results presented in section 4.4.1 using the multilevel logit, it is possible to conclude that, although the aggregation of the electronic instruments into a single category is valid, there are considerable differences among them.

Table 29 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multinomial logit

	Dependent variable				
	Boleto	Credit card	Debit card	Cheque	Transfers
	Multinomial logit				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
GENDER M	0.032 (0.174)	0.164 (0.161)	0.291*** (0.052)	0.353* (0.194)	0.264 (0.255)
AGE 26-35	0.248 (0.265)	0.722*** (0.246)	0.191** (0.077)	0.100 (0.270)	-0.413 (0.346)
AGE 36-45	-0.085 (0.291)	0.632** (0.257)	0.189** (0.082)	-0.260 (0.296)	-0.150 (0.366)
AGE 46-60	0.167 (0.283)	0.605** (0.267)	0.301*** (0.087)	-0.391 (0.311)	-0.756* (0.414)
INCOME 02-03 SM	0.956*** (0.245)	-0.289 (0.284)	0.048 (0.089)	-0.085 (0.266)	0.454 (0.374)
INCOME 03-04 SM	0.956*** (0.240)	0.663** (0.268)	0.396*** (0.086)	-0.133 (0.273)	0.125 (0.407)
INCOME 04-05 SM	0.797*** (0.255)	0.282 (0.300)	0.370*** (0.097)	-0.102 (0.307)	0.689* (0.398)
INCOME 05-10 SM	1.609*** (0.210)	0.476* (0.271)	0.536*** (0.085)	-0.106 (0.277)	0.802** (0.354)
INCOME 10+ SM	0.649 (0.396)	1.530*** (0.452)	1.536*** (0.165)	0.082 (0.297)	0.008 (0.358)
EDUCATION comp. fund.	-0.151 (0.234)	0.592*** (0.212)	0.863*** (0.326)	1.002*** (0.235)	0.717** (0.321)
EDUCATION comp. high	0.224 (0.183)	1.350*** (0.158)	1.115*** (0.324)	0.732*** (0.217)	1.225*** (0.246)
EDUCATION comp. under.	0.763*** (0.201)	2.241*** (0.181)	1.259*** (0.329)	1.399*** (0.254)	1.694*** (0.288)
EDUCATION comp. grad.	-0.236 (0.419)	3.138*** (0.279)	1.189*** (0.353)	0.783 (0.505)	1.866*** (0.521)
REGION N	-0.818** (0.402)	0.852** (0.345)	-0.321*** (0.116)	0.788*** (0.256)	1.020*** (0.284)
REGION NE	-0.216 (0.278)	0.910*** (0.295)	-0.208** (0.095)	0.314 (0.217)	0.866*** (0.226)
REGION S	-0.620* (0.368)	-0.024 (0.355)	0.619*** (0.101)	1.025*** (0.234)	0.455 (0.319)
REGION SE	-0.050 (0.269)	0.577* (0.296)	0.369*** (0.090)	0.635*** (0.208)	0.426* (0.246)
MARITAL divorced	-0.508 (0.361)	0.029 (0.318)	-0.027 (0.099)	-0.263 (0.449)	0.840* (0.484)
MARITAL single	0.033 (0.193)	-0.090 (0.180)	0.074 (0.057)	-0.444** (0.213)	0.677** (0.308)
MARITAL widower	-0.112	0.763	-0.012	1.260***	-0.798***

Table 29 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multinomial logit

	(0.479)	(0.469)	(0.168)	(0.414)	(0.026)
EMPREL autonomous	-0.535**	0.476**	0.388***	0.447**	0.070
	(0.259)	(0.216)	(0.125)	(0.218)	(0.268)
EMPREL unemployed	-0.186	0.576**	0.505***	0.358	-0.068
	(0.286)	(0.263)	(0.138)	(0.265)	(0.342)
EMPREL employee	-0.750***	0.803***	0.476***	0.427**	0.020
	(0.247)	(0.201)	(0.121)	(0.209)	(0.243)
EMPREL businessman	-0.087	0.567*	0.357**	0.228	0.393
	(0.307)	(0.313)	(0.151)	(0.417)	(0.394)
EMPREL trainee	-1.165***	0.518	0.137	1.136**	-0.077
	(0.142)	(0.544)	(0.249)	(0.478)	(0.115)
EMPREL civil servant	-0.754**	0.238	0.277**	0.445	-0.831*
	(0.321)	(0.294)	(0.140)	(0.331)	(0.427)
EMPREL indep. prof.	-0.831**	-0.432	0.152	0.803*	-1.796***
	(0.396)	(0.485)	(0.214)	(0.429)	(0.050)
SOURCE cash	-2.055***	-0.088	-0.529*	-0.483**	-1.044***
	(0.244)	(0.221)	(0.282)	(0.222)	(0.195)
SOURCE in an account	-1.520***	0.122	0.068	-0.128	-0.438**
	(0.259)	(0.240)	(0.283)	(0.249)	(0.207)
SOURCE other	-1.665***	-1.433***	-0.137	-0.182	-1.682***
	(0.396)	(0.403)	(0.342)	(0.404)	(0.026)
CEL	0.751**	0.238	0.625***	0.342	0.882***
	(0.176)	(0.171)	(0.053)	(0.212)	(0.261)
ACCOUNT	0.378	0.657**	0.574***	-0.176	0.218
	(0.314)	(0.268)	(0.090)	(0.261)	(0.423)
VALUE	0.002***	0.001***	0.001***	0.001***	0.002***
	(0.0002)	(0.0003)	(0.0001)	(0.0004)	(0.0003)
SECTOR construction	-0.590***	-2.076***	-1.553***	1.652***	1.850***
	(0.085)	(0.330)	(0.055)	(0.497)	(0.149)
SECTOR finance	0.780***	-1.259**	-0.059	1.470***	1.208***
	(0.278)	(0.556)	(0.273)	(0.475)	(0.452)
SECTOR groceries	-2.963***	-0.077	-0.263	0.477**	-0.984***
	(0.344)	(0.227)	(0.176)	(0.228)	(0.372)
SECTOR housing	-0.783**	-2.486***	-1.245***	0.238	1.114***
	(0.334)	(0.526)	(0.265)	(0.466)	(0.352)
SECTOR other	-1.201***	-0.152	-0.525*	-8.184***	1.034**
	(0.453)	(0.201)	(0.304)	(0.00002)	(0.474)
SECTOR people	-1.888***	-0.889***	-4.984***	-0.923***	-1.869***
	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.0004)	(0.003)	(0.003)
SECTOR service	-0.892***	-0.224	-0.155	0.737**	0.164
	(0.176)	(0.227)	(0.177)	(0.224)	(0.238)
SECTOR transportation	-4.169***	-0.520*	-0.013	0.566**	-1.954***
	(0.440)	(0.270)	(0.182)	(0.267)	(0.498)
SECTOR taxes	-1.654***	-1.908***	-0.676**	0.517***	-1.161**

Table 29 – Determinants of choice of electronic instruments - multinomial logit

	(0.353)	(0.537)	(0.285)	(0.173)	(0.560)
SECTOR apparel	-1.338***	0.366	0.118	0.082	0.217
	(0.417)	(0.309)	(0.200)	(0.445)	(0.498)
TYPE store	-2.361***	0.385*	-0.496***	2.200***	-2.956***
	(0.212)	(0.224)	(0.166)	(0.186)	(0.249)
TYPE NA	-3.467***	1.425***	0.677	-1.448***	-3.395***
	(0.002)	(0.056)	(0.427)	(0.0002)	(0.003)
TYPE online	-0.259	2.651***	0.543*	-4.089***	0.170
	(0.506)	(0.470)	(0.325)	(0.0001)	(0.507)
TYPE person	-3.304***	-0.818*	-1.472***	2.315***	-1.622***
	(0.483)	(0.477)	(0.253)	(0.341)	(0.340)
TYPE service	-1.281***	-1.386***	-1.122***	1.666***	-2.375***
	(0.236)	(0.303)	(0.176)	(0.242)	(0.298)
CONDITION NA	-0.766***	2.790***	-5.993***	-1.310***	-0.469***
	(0.001)	(0.050)	(0.0002)	(0.001)	(0.001)
CONDITION term or in install.	4.048***	8.990***	1.889***	5.014***	2.755***
	(0.362)	(0.264)	(0.296)	(0.309)	(0.681)
Constant	-0.575**	-9.009***	-3.779***	-8.890***	-4.897***
	(0.241)	(0.255)	(0.367)	(0.173)	(0.221)
Observations	16,545	16,545	16,545	16,545	16,545

Note.

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. Standard error in parentheses.

Source: Author's elaboration. Columns 1 to 5 correspond to the result of the multinomial logit regression with money as the base category for the dependent variable.

Base categories for the independent variables:

GENDER = F; AGE = 18-25; INCOME = 00-02 MW; EDUCATION = unschooled;

REGION = CO; MARITAL = married; EMPREL = retired; SOURCE = Cheque.

SECTOR = durable goods; TYPE = government; CONDITION = cash payment.

4.5 Final considerations

The paper contributes to the literature on the choice of retail payment instruments by analyzing the Brazilian case through new data collected in a survey conducted by the country's central bank in 2019 with over 1,500 respondents, responsible for recording over 16,000 payments in a seven-day diary. Addressing emerging countries is a gap identified in the literature that the paper helps fill.

Employing multilevel logit regressions (with one level for payers and another level for payments reported by each payer), it was identified that people of the male gender, older age, higher income, higher education, living in the South and Southeast regions of the country, holding an account at a financial or payment institution, and who have already used a cell phone for purchases are more likely to opt for electronic instruments in their payments. Among the characteristics of the transaction, the probability of choosing electronic instruments is higher for payments of greater value, for purchases of durable goods, and for payments in installments or in installments. Results are robust, being confirmed by pooled logit and multinomial regressions.

These results can contribute as a subsidy to policies aimed at the electronization of payments or to the implementation of new instruments. They may also be useful for industry participants, guiding investments or improvements in the infrastructure necessary for the adoption of new instruments.

As limitations, the data are for only one specific year and only one country, which may limit the scope of the conclusions. In addition, there is no information in the diaries about a number of variables present in other works and that may be important, such as the acceptance of the instruments by the payees, the amount of cash the respondent had at the time of payment, or the number of withdrawals made.

As future work, the database can also be explored in additional analyses, such as analysis of usage compared to preferences (Stavins, 2018), analysis on the compatibility of Alvarez & Lippi (2017) model of cash inventory or data on merchants, not employed in the present work. Users' perceptions of each instrument can also be explored. The explanatory variables and the observations themselves can also be grouped through cluster analysis to aid in the interpretation of the results.

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5 Explaining payment instruments choice with machine learning methods

5.1 Introduction

Retail payment instruments have been the subject of much attention, innovation and change in recent years, a trend exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic (Avdjiev et al., 2020; Bank of England, 2021), with new players entering the market (fintechs and BigTechs such as Google, Apple and Facebook) (Carstens et al., 2021; Frost et al., 2019), and the introduction of new technologies (contactless cards and payment wallets) and new instruments (cryptocurrencies, instant payments and Central Bank Digital Currencies) (Bank for International Settlements et al., 2021; Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2016; Lobo & Brandt, 2021), for example. Regulators have also been intervening in the market, either to correct market failures (such as interventions on debit and credit card interchange fees (Górka, 2018)), stimulate competition, foster innovation or encourage the use of new instruments (Bank for International Settlements, 2022; Carstens et al., 2021; Juan Carlos et al., 2021). Cash is still the dominant instrument, but this reality may soon change (Bech et al., 2018), with electronic instruments gaining even more popularity (Arango-Arango & Suárez-Ariza, 2020; Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, 2021; Duarte et al., 2022).

Understanding how payers choose their payment instruments has been of interest to market participants, regulators and academia for many years (Humphrey et al., 2001). Market participants typically produce market reports such as McKinsey & Company (2021) and FIS (2022). Central banks in developed countries regularly conduct surveys that include payment diaries (Caddy et al., 2020; Cubides & O'Brien, 2022). Academia uses data from these payment diaries, retailers, and aggregate financial market infrastructures data to produce studies mainly on determinants of choice and usage of retail payment instruments (Bagnall et al., 2016; Shy, 2021; Stavins, 2018). These studies generally employ traditional econometric techniques such as logit regression and its variations. They also generally consider developed countries, for which detailed data are more abundant and readily available, as shown in study 1.

Analyzing this topic with machine learning (ML) techniques (Shy, 2018) and explaining retail payment choice predictions with Explainable AI (XAI) techniques can provide new insights into the importance of each of these determinants and how they are interconnected. Considering emerging countries may also provide new information on the subject. Our study attempts to fill these gaps with an analysis of the Brazilian case with a new payment diaries database published by the country's central bank in 2021 (Banco Central do Brasil, 2021) and with the use of Shapley Additive Explanation (SHAP) values, a relatively new approach to explain the importance of features in ML predictions. Classification trees are also constructed for better visualization purposes, not often used in this context (Shy, 2018, 2019).

Our findings on what is most important in the choice of payment instruments may

be of interest to market participants, who can use them as inputs in investment decisions in infrastructure, technology, or marketing needed for the adoption of new instruments. Regulators may also be interested in my findings, employing them as inputs for regulations aimed at the electronization of payments or the implementation of new instruments that better help achieve public goals (Arango-Arango et al., 2015; Świecka et al., 2021).

Section 5.2 presents the methodology, comprising a description of my sample and the data sources, variables, and algorithms. Section 5.3 presents results of the study, and finally, section 5.4 presents my concluding remarks.

5.2 Methodology

I employ some of the most common ML algorithms traditionally used for classification problems. The algorithm that provides the best results in predicting payment instrument choice is the one considered in my attempt to explain the most important characteristics that influence this choice. I also construct classification trees to facilitate and visually improve the understanding of the results.

5.2.1 Sample and data source

The data comes from a survey commissioned by the Central Bank of Brazil, with 95% confidence level and margin of error of 2.5% (Banco Central do Brasil, 2021), part of the project to evaluate an instant payment solution that culminated with the launch of Pix in November 2020 (Lobo & Brandt, 2021). 1,519 people (segmented by geographic region, age, gender, marital status, household income, education and employment relationship) and 615 merchants (segmented by geographic region, industry sector and number of employees) were surveyed between 04/26/2019 and 05/15/2019 with questions about perception and preferences about payment instruments, ownership of checking or payment accounts, previous experience with mobile purchases, among others.

The 1,519 respondents were asked to fill out a payment diary between 04/27 and 06/12/2019, comprising seven days of their choice. In this diary, each person had to record all payments made in the period, including information on value, payment instrument used, where the payment was made, what the sector of the merchant or payee was, and what the payment condition (whether it was a cash or term payment or one made in installments) was, for example. In total, 1,379 diaries were returned, making a total of 16,712 payments recorded. Questions and microdata are available from the Central Bank of Brazil (2021).

5.2.2 Study variables

5.2.2.1 Target variable

The dependent or target variable is the payment instrument chosen by respondents in each of the 16,712 payments recorded in the reported payment diaries. Table 30 shows that the main instruments listed in the survey were cash and credit, debit and prepaid card. Other instruments account for a considerably smaller share of the payments.

As there are 12 payment instruments, cash and cheques were grouped as nonelectronic instruments and the rest were grouped as electronic instruments. The dependent variable is then a binary variable that assumes the value of 1 (one) when the chosen instrument was electronic and 0 (zero) if it was cash or cheque. Table 30 presents the descriptive analysis of all 12 instruments (first rows) and the result of this aggregation (bottom rows). Payment with electronic instruments account for 22.61%, while paper based payments account for 77.39% of the total, with cash totaling 76.61%. Cash is still the dominant instrument in terms of volume, in line with studies such as Bagnall et al. (2016), Arango-Arango et al. (2018) and Bech et al. (2018), which show that this is still the reality in many countries.

Table 30 – Quantity and value of payments per instrument

Instrument	N	Mean	Medn.	Min.	Max.	SD	CV	Kurt.	Skew.	% of obs.
Cash	12805	81.05	30.00	0.30	8000.00	165.98	0.49	448.04	12.92	76.62%
Debit card	1963	128.99	65.00	2.00	3000.00	210.94	0.61	53.85	5.79	11.75%
Credit card	1155	187.53	100.00	2.00	5200.00	306.86	0.61	93.55	7.53	6.91%
Prepaid card	235	33.95	9.00	2.00	2050.00	146.46	0.23	155.27	11.58	1.41%
Meal card	125	111.57	30.00	1.00	900.00	181.70	0.61	8.60	2.45	0.75%
Cheque	120	162.02	57.98	1.50	2386.00	327.19	0.50	26.42	4.54	0.72%
Boleto	92	537.21	307.50	13.00	3300.00	671.87	0.80	8.80	2.40	0.55%
Direct debit	77	291.75	150.00	12.88	2000.00	388.58	0.75	9.94	2.58	0.46%
Store card	50	300.98	175.00	20.00	1850.00	323.40	0.93	11.63	2.47	0.30%
Book transfers	40	467.13	335.00	20.00	1525.00	439.69	1.06	3.18	1.17	0.24%
Other	24	225.81	52.75	4.20	1300.00	365.72	0.62	5.73	1.91	0.14%
DOC	10	242.30	100.00	37.00	900.00	327.70	0.74	3.25	1.47	0.06%
TED	10	290.78	100.00	8.00	1100.00	392.25	0.74	3.15	1.37	0.06%
Unspecified	6	158.53	47.89	20.00	700.00	267.66	0.59	4.07	1.72	0.04%
Nonelectronic	12934	81.83	30.00	0.30	8000.00	168.38	0.49	422.69	12.60	77.39%
Electronic	3778	160.92	73.00	1.00	5200.00	282.77	0.57	63.87	6.11	22.61%
Total	16712	99.71	40.00	0.30	8000.00	202.75	2.03	213.02	9.59	100.00%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. Mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV), kurtosis (Kurt.) and skewness (Skew.) were calculated on the value of transactions with each payment instrument. Boleto, DOC and TED are credit transfers settled in D+1, D+1 and D+0, respectively.

5.2.2.2 Features

Independent variables, or features, are the variables present in the payment diaries mentioned in section 5.2.1. As is common in payment diaries I divide the independent variables into two main groups: demographic and payment characteristics variables (Świecka et al., 2021). Poorly representative categories of certain categorical variables were grouped with similar categories to facilitate data description, and results interpretation and visualization, without loss of information.

The demographic and financial variables considered in the study where: categorical variables describing GENDER, AGE, INCOME, EDUCATION, REGION, MARITAL status, employment relationship (EMPREL) and the way in which the main SOURCE of income is received, and dummy variables to indicate whether the respondent has ever made a purchase with a cell (CEL) phone and to indicate whether someone has a bank or payment ACCOUNT. Payment characteristics considered were the TYPE and SECTOR of the merchant or payee, as well as the CONDITION (indicating whether it was a cash, term or in installments payment) and VALUE of the payment. Tables 31 and 32 present, for each independent variable, the percentage of individuals or payments that belongs to each category and, for each category, the percentage of electronic and nonelectronic

Table 31 – Descriptive statistics of demographic variables

Variable	Categories	Perc. sample (a)	Perc. electronic (b)	Perc. nonelectronic (c)
GENDER	F	50.63%	20.39%	79.61%
	M	49.37%	24.87%	75.13%
AGE	18-25	23.24%	19.17%	80.83%
	26-35	25.02%	24.12%	75.88%
	36-45	26.07%	23.30%	76.70%
	46-60	25.67%	23.57%	76.43%
INCOME	00-02 MW	21.66%	12.57%	87.43%
	02-03 MW	20.74%	16.34%	83.66%
	03-04 MW	21.59%	24.01%	75.99%
	04-05 MW	11.59%	27.45%	72.55%
	05-10 MW	22.45%	31.91%	68.09%
	10+ MW	1.97%	57.73%	42.27%
EDUCATION	no educ.	1.65%	8.79%	91.21%
	complete fundamental	27.58%	13.75%	86.25%
	complete high	55.30%	22.94%	77.06%
	complete undergraduate	13.43%	36.14%	63.86%
	graduate	2.04%	39.71%	60.29%
REGION	CO	7.97%	19.88%	80.12%
	N	10.60%	15.08%	84.92%
	NE	26.86%	19.63%	80.37%
	S	14.22%	32.38%	67.62%
	SE	40.36%	25.73%	74.27%
MARITAL	married	41.15%	24.41%	75.59%
	divorced	6.52%	27.35%	72.65%
	single	49.90%	20.48%	79.52%
	widow	2.44%	25.74%	74.26%
EMPREL	retired	5.51%	24.71%	75.29%
	autonomous	32.43%	19.90%	80.10%
	unemployed	17.28%	16.01%	83.99%
	employee	30.17%	25.16%	74.84%
	entrepreneur	5.18%	36.26%	63.74%
	intern	1.26%	18.75%	81.25%
	civil servant	6.31%	34.33%	65.67%
	indep. profes.	1.86%	18.11%	81.89%
	cheque	0.53%	30.86%	69.14%
SOURCE	cash	56.81%	16.84%	83.16%
	in an account	40.16%	31.36%	68.64%
	other	2.50%	15.30%	84.70%
	no mobile purchase	70.14%	17.07%	82.93%
CEL	previous mobile purchase	29.86%	35.49%	64.51%
	no bank account	22.71%	9.68%	90.32%
ACCOUNT	has bank account	77.29%	26.01%	73.99%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. a) Distribution in the sample, with $n = 1,519$; b) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with electronic instruments among respondents in each category; c) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with nonelectronic instruments among respondents in each category. MW = minimum wage; CO = Center-West, N = North, NE = North-East, S = South, SE = South-East.

payments reported in the diaries. Table 30 presents descriptive statistics for the VALUE of payments, the only numeric independent variable.

5.2.3 Machine learning techniques for prediction and visualization

I will employ six commonly used classification algorithms to predict the choice of payment instrument based on the features previously described: 1) logit regression, 2) classification trees, 3) random forests, 4) gradient boosted trees (GBT) or gradient boosted machines (GBM), 5) artificial neural networks (ANN) and 6) k-nearest neighbors (KNN) (Athey & Imbens, 2019; Géron, 2019; Murphy, 2022; Shy, 2018; Varian, 2014). I will evaluate the performance of each model using four traditional measures: 1) accuracy, 2) precision, 3) recall, 4) F1 score and 5) Kappa. The predictions of the best model will be analyzed to determine the most important features using the random forest approach and

Table 32 – Descriptive statistics for transaction characteristics variables

Variable	Categories	Perc. sample (a)	Perc. electronic (b)	Perc. nonelectronic (c)
SECTOR	durable goods	1.65%	46.74%	53.26%
	construction	0.11%	31.58%	68.42%
	finance	1.07%	41.01%	58.99%
	groceries	35.46%	21.53%	78.47%
	housing	2.26%	17.51%	82.49%
	other	1.33%	15.77%	84.23%
	people	0.05%	NA	100.00%
	service	26.27%	23.26%	76.74%
	transportation	25.91%	18.34%	81.66%
	taxes	0.90%	30.46%	69.54%
	apparel	4.99%	39.81%	60.19%
TYPE	government	0.62%	40.78%	59.22%
	store	72.73%	25.26%	74.74%
	online	0.47%	53.16%	46.84%
	people	2.45%	12.47%	87.53%
	service	23.73%	14.38%	85.62%
CONDITION	cash purchase	92.93%	17.11%	82.89%
	term or install.	7.07%	95.08%	4.92%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. a) Distribution in the sample, with $n = 1,519$; b) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with electronic instruments among respondents in each category; c) Percentage of payments reported in the diary paid with nonelectronic instruments among respondents in each category.

the SHAP values approach. Classification trees will be constructed to visually improve the interpretability of how the most important features influence the payment instrument decision choice.

The hyperparameters of the models were tuned using a grid search with a 5-fold cross-validation and 3 repetitions. The goal was to maximize accuracy. The variables described in 5.2.2.2 were preprocessed by removing missing values, scaling and centering, so that they all had the same influence on the predictions. The data was split into a training and test sample in the ratio 80:20. The training and test data are the same for all of the models. The random seed was the same in all of the evaluations.

I now give an overview of each of the aforementioned algorithms, as implemented by the caret R package (Kuhn, 2022) and the packages it depends on: base R for logit and KNN (R Core Team, 2022), rpart for classification trees (Therneau & Atkinson, 2022), ranger for random forests (Wright & Ziegler, 2017), xgboost for XGBoost (Chen et al., 2022) and nnet for ANN (Venables & Ripley, 2002). SHAP values were implemented by Greenwell (2021) and Mayer (2022).

5.2.3.1 Classification trees

Classification or decision trees are flexible algorithms capable of fitting complex data, by iteratively dividing the sample into smaller and smaller groups according to simple decisions rules based on certain features (Breiman et al., 1984). The R package rpart (Therneau & Atkinson, 2022) employs the CART algorithm. This algorithm splits the given dataset into two groups according to a specific feature k and an associated threshold t_k . The best feature for splitting and its associated threshold are determined by the algorithm, attempting to produce the purest groups. The cost function the algorithm tries to minimize is given by equation 5.1.

$$J(k, t_k) = \frac{m_{left}}{m} G_{left} + \frac{m_{right}}{m} G_{right} \quad (5.1)$$

where $G_{left/right}$ measures impurity of each subset and $m_{left/right}$ is the number of observations in each subset.

After this first split, the algorithm splits each of the two groups formed into new subgroups, following the same procedure, and so on, recursively, until it reaches a predefined maximum depth hyperparameter or if a new split will increase the impurity instead of improving it.

The impurity can be calculated by the Gini measure or by entropy. I use the Gini measure, defined by equation 5.2.

$$G_i = 1 - \sum_{c=1}^n p_{i,c}^2 \quad (5.2)$$

where $p_{i,c}$ is the ratio of observations (or instances) of class c among all considered observations in the i^{th} node and n is the number of classes. It ranges from 0 (pure node) to 0.5 (impure node).

An important hyperparameter is the complexity parameter, cp , which prevents the tree from overfitting the data. Its value ranges between 0 and 1. If it is small, the tree will overfit and if it is 1, the tree will have no splits. This value is usually set by hyperparameter tuning. In my case, the cross-validation process employed for parameter tuning achieved a value of 0.002, the value that maximizes accuracy for the training data set. It is also possible to determine other hyperparameters to control when to stop, such as the minimum number of observations a node should have, the maximum number of leaf nodes and the maximum number of features considered for splitting each node.

5.2.3.2 Random forests

A random forest (Breiman, 2001) is an ensemble of decision trees, mostly built via bagging, in which each tree is built with a bootstrap sample (or sample with replacement) or subsample of the data available for training. In each split, the algorithm searches for the best feature among a randomly chosen subset of the features rather than among all of the features. These characteristics of the algorithm result in higher diversity of trees and in better predictive power. The algorithm has as hyperparameters the number of trees, in addition to the hyperparameters of the decision trees, as described in section 5.2.3.1. Random forests generally perform reasonably well without the need for complex tuning of the hyperparameters (Athey & Imbens, 2019; Geron, 2019).

In my application, the forest was built with a predefined number of 500 trees and the number of features to be possibly split at each node and the minimum node size were set by the cross-validation process to be, respectively 26 and 1. The splitting rule selected was extra-trees (and not Gini as in the case of section 5.2.3.1). With this splitting rule, which makes the trees even more random, the thresholds for the splitting features are set randomly, rather than optimized. All training data was used in each tree, with replacement.

5.2.3.3 Logistic regression

Logistic regression is another common algorithm used for binary classification purposes. It estimates the probability that an instance belongs to a certain class and if this value is greater than a certain threshold (usually 50%), the instance is predicted to belong to this class.

The algorithm estimates probabilities in a similar way to linear models, but transforms the weighted sum of the input features according to the sigmoid function, given by equation 5.3.

$$S(t) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-t}} \quad (5.3)$$

Thus, the probability that a dependent variable (or output variable) y is 1 given a set of independent variables (or input variables or features) \mathbf{x} is given by equation 5.4 (in vectorized form).

$$Prob(y = 1|\mathbf{x}) = \hat{p} = S(\mathbf{x}^T \beta) \quad (5.4)$$

where β is a vector of coefficients. The classification is given by equation 5.5, with a threshold of 50%.

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \hat{p} < 0.5 \\ 1 & \text{if } \hat{p} \geq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

5.2.3.4 Artificial neural networks

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are inspired by natural neural networks, in which a set of neurons interact to process information. They are composed of processing elements, called nodes or neurons, an interconnection topology and a learning scheme. One of its main characteristics is that it can adapt as input is processed. The nodes (or neurons) are usually organized in layers, with an output layer, an input layer and one or more hidden intermediate layers (in my application, there is only one hidden layer). Each neuron has an activation function and a combination function. The combination function computes the net input of the neuron, usually a weighted sum of inputs. The activation function produced the output, given the net input computed by the combination function. There are many possibilities for these functions and typical forms are the sigmoid (equation 5.3) for the activation function and linear for the combination function, as in equation 5.6 (Kendrick et al., 2005).

$$y_t = \theta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j a_{tj} \quad (5.6)$$

where y_t is the output in period t , a_{tj} is the output value of node j in the period t , θ_j are parameters to be determined and q is the set of hidden nodes.

a_{tj} , the values for each hidden node j in period t , are given by equation 5.7.

$$a_{tj} = S \left(\sum_{i=1}^{q_j} w_{ji} x_{it} \right) \quad (5.7)$$

where x_{it} is the value of input i in period t , w_{ji} is the weight of input i at node j and q_j is the set of inputs at the hidden node j . $S()$ can be, for example, the sigmoid function given in equation 5.3).

Weights w_{ji} are also parameters to be determined. In the implementation used in my application (Venables & Ripley, 2002), they are updated at each period t , according to a gradient descent decay parameter with a value of 0.1, as determined by the cross-validation procedure. It also has a hyperparameter batch size that controls the number of observations to be processed before the parameters are updated, determined to be 1 by the cross-validation procedure in my application.

5.2.3.5 k-nearest neighbors

K-nearest neighbors (KNN) is a simple algorithm commonly used for classification (Cover & Hart, 1967; Fix & Hodges, 1951, 1989). It is based on how similar an observation is from other observations. Practically, it tries to find the class to which an observation belongs based on its distance to other observations, for which the classification is known. This distance is generally the Euclidian distance, calculated according to equation 5.8, but it can also be the Malahanobis, Manhattan, Minkowski, or any other distance.

$$d(x, y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^F (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (5.8)$$

where F is the set of features, x_i is the value of feature i for observation x and y_i is the value of feature i for observation y .

The algorithm calculates this distance between a given observation in the testing data and all of the observations in the training data. It then assigns to this test observation the most prevalent class in the k observations that are nearest to it. This algorithm has k as its hyperparameter, controlling the number of instances to which a given test observation is compared. In my application, k was determined to be 9 by the cross-validation procedure and the Euclidian distance was used.

5.2.3.6 Gradient Boosted Trees

The XGBoost algorithm used in this work is an efficient implementation of the Gradient Boosted Tree (or Gradient Tree Boosting or Gradient Boosted Regression Trees) algorithm, also known as Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) (Chen et al., 2022; Chen & Guestrin, 2016). It is built on the CART algorithm described earlier (section 5.2.3.1) and is known for its speed and accuracy, although tuning its hyperparameters can be non-trivial (Müller & Guido, 2017).

Boosting attempts to combine several weak predictors into a strong one by training them sequentially, with each one attempting to correct its predecessor. The most common methods for this are AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting. AdaBoost trains the predictors

sequentially, changing the weights of each predictor according to its accuracy for classification problems (or any chosen measure, including those applicable for regression problems). The more accurate the predictor, the higher its weight in the final ensemble. Gradient Boosting, in turn, fits each new predictor to the residual errors of its predecessor, trying to minimize a given loss function. Mathematically, the algorithm tries, at each step t , to minimize the regularized objective given by equation 5.9

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)} + f_t(\mathbf{x}_i)) + \Omega(f_t) \quad (5.9)$$

where l is a loss function (differentiable convex), \mathbf{x}_i is the vector of all features for observation i , y_i is the actual value for the target or dependent variable for observation i , $\hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}$ is the prediction given by the previous model for instance i , f_t is the model built on the residuals, and Ω is a regularization term, also known as the learning rate, which penalizes complexity and prevents over-fitting. According to Chen & Guestrin (2016), this "cannot be optimized using traditional optimization methods in Euclidean space" and thus, a second-order Taylor approximation can be employed, as in equation 5.10.

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)} \simeq \sum_{i=1}^n [l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}) + g_i f_t(\mathbf{x}_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_t^2(\mathbf{x}_i)] + \Omega(f_t) \quad (5.10)$$

where $\hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}$ is the mean prediction of the target variable in step t , g_i and h_i are the first and second order gradients on the loss function, respectively, given by equations 5.11 and 5.12.

$$g_i = \frac{\partial l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)})}{\partial \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}} \quad (5.11)$$

$$h_i = \frac{\partial^2 l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)})}{\partial (\hat{y}_i^{(t-1)})^2} \quad (5.12)$$

The loss function can take many forms, such as the root mean squared error (RMSE) for regression problems and the logistic form for classification problems such as ours. The logistic log loss function is given by equation 5.13.

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)} = - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ln(p) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - p) \quad (5.13)$$

where y_i is the actual class of instance i and p is its associated probability (or pseudo-probability) score, given by the same sigmoid/logistic equation described earlier in equation 5.3. The final prediction is the sum of the predictions from each tree in the model.

In my application, the learning rate (eta in the implementation of Chen et al. (2022)) was determined to be 0.3 by the cross-validation procedure I employed. The maximum depth of each tree was determined to be 3, the subsample ratio of features considered in the construction of each tree was determined to be 60% and the subsample ratio of the training instances to be considered was determined to be 75%. The number of steps for boosting was set to 150.

5.2.4 Evaluation measures

The algorithms were evaluated according to five measures commonly used for results appraisal of classification problems (Naser & Alavi, 2020): 1) accuracy, 2) precision, 3) *recall*, 4) *F1 score* and 5) Kappa, defined according to equations 5.14, 5.15, 5.16, 5.17 and 5.18, respectively:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (5.14)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5.15)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5.16)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{precision} + \frac{1}{recall}} = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + \frac{FN+FP}{2}} \quad (5.17)$$

$$Kappa = \frac{Accuracy - p_e}{1 - p_e} \quad (5.18)$$

where TP = true positives, or positive observations correctly classified as such, FP = false positives, or negative observations incorrectly classified as positive, TN = true negatives, or negative observations correctly classified as such, FN = false negatives, or positive observations incorrectly classified as negatives and p_e defined according to equation 5.19.

$$p_e = \frac{[(TP + FP)(TP + FN)] + [(TN + FP)(TN + FN)]}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)^2} \quad (5.19)$$

p_e represents the probability that the algorithm makes a correct prediction, either negative or positive, simply by chance. In my application, positive predictions are those where the predicted instrument is electronic and negative predictions are those where the predicted instrument is nonelectronic.

Accuracy measures the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions. Precision, on its turn, measures, among those payments predicted as electronic, those that were actually paid with electronic instruments, that is, the percentage of true positives relative to all those predicted as positive. This metric penalizes false positives (type I error), i.e., payments predicted as electronic but actually paid with cash or cheques. Recall evaluates how many of the positives were correctly identified, penalizing false negatives (payments made with electronic instruments, but predicted as non-electronic), i.e., this measure penalizes type II error. The F1 measure is a harmonic means of precision and recall. It is more comprehensive, as it penalizes both type I and II errors. Finally, Kappa measures the possibility of making correct predictions by chance.

5.2.5 Feature importance

5.2.5.1 Random forest approach

Determining which features are the most important is crucial to understanding the model and trusting its predictions. In a decision tree, one way to measure the importance of a feature is to determine which feature contributes to the creation of better decision rules, that is, decision rules capable of reducing node impurity in a sharper way (Breiman et al., 1984). In a random forest, the same principle applies, but I measure how a given feature reduces impurity by considering a weighted average across all trees in the forest. The weights are the number of training samples that are associated with each node (Breiman, 2001).

According to Breiman (2001), the importance of the i -th feature at the t -th tree is calculated according to equation 5.20.

$$FI_{i_t} = \frac{\sum_{j \in J} N_j}{\sum_{l=1}^{\Omega} N_l} \quad (5.20)$$

where J is the set of nodes split by the i -th feature, Ω is the number of nodes of the t -th tree and N_j is the importance of the j -th node given by equation 5.21.

$$N_j = \omega_j \xi_j - \sum_{k \in j^-} \omega_k \xi_k \quad (5.21)$$

where ω_j is the number of observations (weighted) in the j -th node, ξ_j is the impurity of the j -th node and j^- is the set of all nodes below the j -th node.

Given this, the importance of a specific feature i is the average importance considering all trees in the forest, according to equation 5.22.

$$FI_i = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{FI_{i_t}}{T} \quad (5.22)$$

where T is the set of all trees in the forest.

5.2.5.2 Shapley Additive Explanation

Shapley Additive Explanation (SHAP) is a method proposed by Lundberg & Lee (2017), based on Shapley's (1953) work on cooperative game theory, that attempts to explain feature importance in artificial intelligence models.

Intuitively, the importance of the i -th feature is the effect on model predictions caused by the inclusion of this particular feature. It is computationally intensive because it requires computing and comparing predictions of models built with and without this particular feature. This procedure is repeated for all possible subsets S of the set of all features F ($S \subseteq F$) without the i -th feature, since a prediction depends on the other features included in the model. The weighted average of all possible differences is then calculated, as in equation 5.23.

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|!(|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f_{S \cup \{i\}}(x_{S \cup \{i\}}) - f_S(x_S)] \quad (5.23)$$

where $f_{S \cup \{i\}}$ is the prediction of the model with the i -th feature present and $f_S(x_S)$ is the prediction of this model without the i -th feature. $x_{S \cup \{i\}}$ is the sample with the i -th feature and x_S is the sample without this i -th feature.

Although SHAP values are considerably expensive to calculate, it is a model-agnostic method (it builds on and unifies several previous methods of explaining variable importance), and is able to assign an importance value for each feature in the prediction for each specific observation. Thus, it can provide both local (there is a set of SHAP values, and thus feature importance metrics, for each observation) and global interpretability (the SHAP values for each observation can be aggregated to provide a feature importance metric for the entire sample).

5.3 Results analysis

5.3.1 Comparison of payment instrument choice prediction models

Table 33 presents the performance of each algorithm in predicting which payment instrument is chosen in each payment according to each of the measures described in section 5.2.3. Results show that the random forest algorithm performed the best overall. Predictions of this algorithm were superior according to all measures, except for precision. It shows that this algorithm was not the best at dealing with type I errors (false positives). Logit, on the other hand, performed the worst on all measures except for precision, under which it was the best. This algorithm, therefore, focused on precision, making many type II errors (false negatives), compromising its overall performance.

Table 33 – Algorithms performance comparison

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	Kappa
Random forest	0.869	0.755	0.624	0.683	0.602
Gradient boosting trees	0.851	0.817	0.437	0.569	0.489
Artificial neural network	0.837	0.781	0.385	0.516	0.432
Logit	0.837	0.835	0.346	0.489	0.411
Classification tree	0.842	0.812	0.387	0.524	0.443
K-nearest neighbors	0.838	0.733	0.443	0.552	0.460

Note. Source: Author's elaboration.

This result is in agreement with that presented by Shy (2018), who does a similar analysis with American payment diaries, even though the author does not employ GBT. This algorithm shows superior performance in many situations, even though it was worse in my application, but Müller & Guido (2017) mention that, while they may be better than random forests, their hyperparameters are generally harder to calibrate, which may have happened in my application. They also tend to overfit the training data more often than random forests (Müller & Guido, 2017). Another explanation for the superiority of random forests may be due to their better handling of situations in which there is high correlation between independent variables, a situation that may have occurred here.

It is also worth noting that all algorithms are highly accurate, with 83.7% as the floor in the ANN and logit cases, and 86.9% as the best measure in the random forest

Figure 9 – Classification tree with demographic, financial and transaction characteristics variables. Source: author’s elaboration with R package rpart. Each node presents the predicted class, the probability that the instrument is electronic and the percentage of observations that fall into it. Positive result of the condition evaluation for each node on the left.

case. The largest discrepancies were in the recall measure, in which logit did worst, with 0.346, while the random forest algorithm achieved an nearly double measure of 0.624. This is because of the aforementioned high level of FN predicted by the logit.

5.3.2 Variable importance

5.3.2.1 Visualization through classification trees

A useful way to convey the variable importance information is through a visual decision tree. While not as accurate as other prediction methods, when it comes to communication and explanation, they are important tools for presenting results and facilitating understanding of how payment instruments are chosen (Shy, 2018, 2019).

Figure 9 shows a classification tree considering all features. In this case, the CART algorithm considers that only `CONDITION` is sufficient to determine the choice. If it is a cash payment, the model predicts that the probability of choosing electronic payments is 17%, with 93% of payments classified as nonelectronic. If it is not a cash payment, the model assigns a probability of choosing electronic instruments of 95%, with 7% of observations classified as such. Intuitively, `CONDITION` is the variable capable of dividing the sample in the purest way, as can be seen in Table 32, because when the payment is made at term or in installments, it was paid with an electronic instrument in 95% of the reported payments, even if they account for only 7% of all payments. In fact, these are exactly the probabilities reported in figure 9.

If I omit the `CONDITION` variable, Figure 10 shows the new classification tree. In this case, `VALUE` is the top-level variable, separating payments above and below R\$31. Payments below R\$31 have an 87% chance of being made with nonelectronic instruments (with 45% of observations classified as such). For payments above R\$31, the model considers the payer’s previous experience with mobile purchasing. If the user has never made a purchase using his/her cell phone, the model considers that there is a 76% chance of the payment being made with a nonelectronic instrument (with 38% of observations classified

Figure 10 – Classification tree with demographic, financial and transaction characteristics variables, except CONDITION. Source: Author’s elaboration with the R package rpart. Each node shows the predicted class, the probability that the instrument is electronic and the percentage of observations that fall into it. Positive result of the condition evaluation for each node on the left.

as such). If the user has this kind of previous experience, the third variable considered is the INCOME. If it is less than 10 minimum wages, with 76% of probability, the payment will be made with a nonelectronic instrument, although only 1% of observations are classified as such by the model. REGION, TYPE of merchant, VALUE (again, but with R\$94 as threshold) and SECTOR are the other variables considered to build the tree. In agreement with the SHAP values (section 5.3.2.3) and the random forest variable importance approaches (section 5.3.2.2) discussed below, the CONDITION, VALUE, CEL and INCOME variables are the most important features, although not in the same order.

5.3.2.2 Random forest approach

Figure 11 shows the features considered most important by the random forest approach described in section 5.2.5.2. Payment CONDITION is the most important variable (when it indicates a term or in installments payment), followed by how one receives his/her main SOURCE of income (when it is in an account) and the previous experience with online purchasing (CEL). CONDITION is twice as important as the second and third most important features. VALUE is also important, but is less than half as important as CEL.

As already mentioned in section 5.3.2.1, CONDITION is the variable that best reduces node impurity, but now considering the ensemble of trees built by the random forest algorithm. The importance of SOURCE (on an account) is less obvious, but it comprises 40% of the respondents, and when one’s income is received this way, 31% of the payments are made with an electronic instrument, up from 17% when received in cash. The same is true for CEL. When one had a previous experience with a mobile purchase (30% of respondents), 35% of the payments were reported on an electronic instrument, compared to 17% for those who had no previous experience with a mobile purchase. The importance of REGION SE, the fourth most important feature, is even less obvious, but it also reduces impurity, as 26% of the reported payments from this region are made with

Figure 11 – Most important variables according to the random forest approach. Source: Author’s elaboration with the R package caret.

electronic instruments, up from 23% overall.

5.3.2.3 SHAP values

Since the random forest algorithm was the most accurate, as shown in Table 33, it was chosen to be used for description by the SHAP values approach. Figure 12 shows the global importance of the features in this model, confirming the results of the random forest feature importance approach presented in section 5.3.2.2. *CONDITION* (either term or in installments payments and cash payments), *SOURCE* (either in an account or in cash), *CEL* (both previous or no previous experience with a mobile purchase) and *VALUE* are the most important features, although the order is not exactly the same in the two approaches. The case of the *VALUE* feature is the most remarkable, as it is the fourth most important variable in the SHAP values approach (figure 12), but only the ninth in the traditional random forest importance approach (figure 11).

It is worth noting that in the SHAP values approach it is clear that the other variables are still very important in the aggregate, being twice as important as the most important individual feature (*CONDITION*). Therefore, they still play an important role in characterizing the choice of payment instruments. It is possible to see this in the classification tree shown in figure 9, for example. *CONDITION*, the most important variable, divides the sample into 93% nonelectronic and 7% electronic, while the true classes comprise respectively 77% and 23% of the payments.

The swarm plot presented in Figure 13 shows that the aggregate of the 49 least important variables, even though they are quite heterogeneous, tends to pull predictions towards the nonelectronic class, as expected, since they comprise most of the observations. It also shows the correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable. For example, when *CONDITION* indicates a payment made in installments or at

Figure 12 – Global features importance for the random forest model. Source: Author’s elaboration with R’s shapviz package.

Figure 13 – Beeswarm global features importance for the random forest model. Source: Author’s elaboration with R’s shapviz package.

term (high values for the dummy variable, shown in yellow), the SHAP values are positive and high, indicating that the probability of the dependent value assuming the value of electronic is high. This feature is then positively correlated with the dependent variable.

As for the VALUE feature, most payments are of low value, but when this variable is higher, it tends to pull the prediction to the electronic side. Another example is the way the SOURCE of income is received. When income is received in cash (SOURCE cash), it tends to pull predictions towards nonelectronic instruments (high values of the variable in yellow and low values of the dependent variable indicated by negative SHAP values). This feature is then negatively correlated with the target variable.

Figure 14 shows dependence graphs for four of the most important features. With this type of graph, it is possible to see in more detail how each independent variable influences the dependent variable. For the VALUE variable, it shows that higher value payments are associated with higher probabilities of choosing an electronic payment in-

Figure 14 – Dependence plot for (a) payment condition, (b) way or receiving income, (c) previous experience with mobile purchases and (d) value. Source: author’s elaboration using the R package shapviz.

strument, but this relationship is not linear as the shape of the graph shows. There are fewer higher value payments and are highly associated with electronic payments (higher values for SHAP).

The categorical variables have a more direct interpretation. For the payment `CONDITION` feature (when at term or in installments), because it is a dummy variable, indicating whether it was a term payment or not, SHAP values are higher when the variable takes the value of one. In fact, for term or installment payments, the probability of someone choosing an electronic payment is higher. In the case of the `SOURCE` of receiving the income, the impact on choice is less pronounced, but when income is received in an account, payments are more likely to be made with electronic payments than when it is not received in an account. Previous experience with mobile shopping shows a less clear separation than the `CONDITION` variable, but better than the `SOURCE` account variable. It indicates that a previous experience with this type of purchase tends to increase the probability of choosing an electronic instrument.

A final possibility for interpreting the SHAP values are interaction dependence graphs, such as the ones shown for the `VALUE` variable in Figure 15. The figure on the left shows the interaction between `VALUE` and the way the `SOURCE` of income is received (in cash), chosen automatically by the implementation function. The figure on the right shows the interaction between `VALUE` and `CONDITION` (term or in installments payments), an explicitly chosen variable. It is possible to see that people who receive their `SOURCE` of income in cash make payments of any value, but this information tends to pull predictions towards nonelectronic payments, especially for lower value payments. Installment or term

Figure 15 – Dependence plot for the interaction of VALUE and (a) SOURCE (cash) and (b) CONDITION (installments or term). Source: author’s elaboration with R’s shapviz package.

payments are more associated with higher value payments and, especially for these, pull the choice toward electronic instruments.

I find that the peculiar characteristics of Brazilian payments are more important in the country than other variables traditionally considered. The SECTOR and TYPE of the merchants are of lesser importance in the country. Payments to TYPE of service merchants are only the 13th most important variable in the SHAP values approach, with a concentration of cash payments. Previous studies, which generally use traditional methods such as binary or multinomial logistic regressions (in all their variations, but generally pooled), also find TYPE to be of minor importance (Świecka et al., 2021), but the SECTOR is generally significant (Stavins, 2018; Świecka et al., 2021). VALUE is in line with the previous literature, with Arango-Arango et al. (2015), Bagnall et al. (2016), Klee (2008), Stavins (2018), Świecka et al. (2021) and Wang & Wolman (2016) also finding that the probability of someone choosing an electronic payment instrument increases with value. I also found that this variable is of paramount importance.

SOURCE, ACCOUNT, CEL and CONDITION are not generally considered in other studies. In developed countries, the unbanked proportion of the population is not significant and having a checking or payment ACCOUNT is not of interest when it comes to choice of payment instruments. In my analysis, the absence of an ACCOUNT is the tenth most important variable in the random forest approach. CONDITION is also generally not of interest, since in most countries the decision to defer payment is made later with a financial transaction with the credit card issuer or other financial institution. In Brazil, on the other hand, merchants generally offer the possibility of installment payments, either through credit cards or through “boletos” (credit transfers that can be scheduled for future payments), for example. Previous experience with mobile shopping is also not considered, because in developed countries it is assumed that most people are familiar with the technology needed to make electronic payments. But in Brazil, an emerging country with a significant proportion of the population in lower socio-economic classes, these variables assume maximum importance in determining the choice of payment instrument.

Regarding demographic variables, Arango-Arango et al. (2015), Bagnall et al. (2016), Fujiki & Tanaka (2018), Goczek & Witkowski (2016) and Świecka et al. (2021) find that AGE, INCOME and EDUCATION are important determinants, with the use of

electronic instruments decreasing with the former and increasing with the latter two. I find that INCOME (when in the 05-10 MW category) is of moderate importance, but AGE and EDUCATION do not appear in the top variables, according to the SHAP methodology, although EDUCATION (when complete undergraduate) is the eleventh most important variable in the random forest approach.

As for MARITAL status, I find the married category to be of moderate importance with a slightly positive correlation with the target variable. Świecka et al. (2021), on the other hand, find no significance between marital status and the choice of electronic payments. REGION is found to be significant by Goczek & Witkowski (2016), with residents of more urbanized regions using electronic payments more than residents of predominantly rural areas. This is in line with my findings, which show that REGION has moderate significance when it comes to the Southeast (SE), the most urbanized region in Brazil. It shows a strong correlation with the target variable, indicating that SE residents tend to choose electronic payments more often. Employment relationship (EMPREL) is not considered significant in previous studies (Świecka et al., 2021), but in my case it also shows a moderate importance when the person is self-employed or an employee, both with a positive correlation with the target variable.

5.4 Final considerations

Our study contributes to the literature on retail payment instrument choice by analyzing the Brazilian case employing a new base, with data collected in a survey commissioned by the Central Bank of Brazil in 2019 with more than 1,500 respondents, responsible for recording almost 17,000 payments in a seven-day payment diary. It also innovates by analyzing this subject with SHAP values, an Explainable AI technique capable of highlighting in detail the importance of each variable in predicting the choice of payment instruments. The most common approach to analyzing payment diaries is with logit regression (typically pooled and sometimes the multinomial variation). It is also worth noting that few studies consider emerging countries.

I made predictions of retail payment choice with six of the most common classification algorithms (logit regression, classification trees, random forests, gradient boosted trees, artificial neural networks, and K-nearest neighbors) and, as the model that showed the best overall prediction performance, including being the most accurate, random forest was used as the base model for the variable importance analysis. Features considered were demographic and financial as well as payment transaction characteristics.

The most important features were CONDITION of payment (term, in installments or cash payment), how the main SOURCE of income was received (in an account or in cash), the VALUE of the payment, previous experience with mobile shopping (CEL), REGION, marital status (MARITAL), INCOME, employment relationship (EMPREL) and EDUCATION of the respondent. Variables typical of the Brazilian market, such as the CONDITION of payment and the way of receiving the SOURCE of income, are more important than the determinants generally found in the literature.

The importance of the variables was determined by the SHAP values approach as well as the traditional random forest importance approach. Classification trees were built to help convey information about the most important variables visually. They also

confirmed that payment CONDITION, VALUE, INCOME and previous experience with mobile shopping are among the most important variables.

These results can contribute as inputs to policies aimed at the electronization of payment or to the development of new instruments. They may also be useful for industry participants, guiding investments or improvements in infrastructure and marketing needed to stimulate the adoption of new instruments.

As limitations, my data comprises only a specific country and year. In addition, our payment diaries do not carry certain variables present in other studies and that may also be important, such as the acceptance of the instruments by merchants, the amount of cash with the payer at the time of the payment or the number and value of cash withdrawals made by each respondent.

As future studies, I can use other Explainable AI techniques, such as LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016), even if the SHAP values try to unify them all. As an agnostic approach, SHAPs could be constructed for the other models to study the consistency of the most important variables. Since most of my variables are categorical and there are more than 60 categories in total, they could also be selected with a regularized regression approach (such as the lasso) before fitting the models. Principal Component Analysis could also be employed before fitting the models. The data could be employed in additional analyses, using each payer's perception in relation of each instrument, for example.

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6 Payment instrument choice in Brazil: an agent-based model

6.1 Introduction

Payment instrument choice can be explained with traditional econometric techniques, such as the logit models employed in chapter 4 or even with less traditional approaches such as the machine learning techniques employed in chapter 5, but the proposition and empirical testing of specific theories to explain why people still choose cash when there are plenty of other payments instruments available is still relatively rare. Cash is still the most common payment instrument in many countries, although adoption of electronic instruments such as payment cards and instant payment have been increasing, specially after the COVID-19 pandemic (Khiaonarong & Humphrey, 2022).

Agent-based models are a technique well suited for simulations, allowing for the interaction of agents under predefined rules in complex models (Macal and North, 2010). Their employment in situations where we do not have complete information about a phenomenon, such as the case in my application, can provide insights into the problem under investigation. Payment instrument choice data generally comes from payment diaries, in which records of payments are recorded, but the whole context surrounding a payment is generally missing, such as the availability and specific transaction costs of other instruments, amount of resources available at hand or in a payment account, acceptance of payment instruments by payees, etc. (Bagnall et al., 2016).

The objective of this study is to test the model proposed by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) with Brazilian payment diaries (the same employed in studies three and four), implemented through an agent-based model (ABM), in order to understand the decision process and motivations behind the choice of a payment instrument in each situation. Their model postulates that people choose to pay with cash whenever they have enough of it at hand, since there is a cost associated with cash withdrawals. Even though it is relatively simple, it is able to explain the behavior documented in payment diaries of six different developed countries.

Our findings may be useful to market participants and regulators, providing inputs to better understand why specific instruments are chosen. It can be helpful in financial literacy campaigns or other public policy initiatives on the usage of payment instruments, for example, helping to reduce the costs associated with payments.

I contribute to the literature by testing a recent theory on cash holding and usage in an important emerging market. I also suggest an evolution to this model, considering a policy for minimal payment account holdings, implemented as an ABM. Also, the bibliometric analysis conducted in chapter 2 showed that the usage of simulation techniques to study retail payments is also a gap in the literature that I believe I can help fulfill.

Section 6.2 presents the theoretical model in which I based the construction of the ABM. Section 6.3 presents the methodology, including the description of the models

implemented and the data used to test the model empirically. Section 6.4 presents the results of the simulations and finally section 6.5 presents the final considerations of this study.

6.2 Literature review

6.2.1 Cash management

The standard theory to explain demand for money was proposed by Baumol (1952) and Tobin (1956) independently, now known as Baumol-Tobin or BT. The authors proposed that the demand for money depends on the interest rate level i , the individual's income Y , the transaction costs C of transferring (or withdrawing) resources from interest-bearing assets into the form of cash, and the average value of resources held in cash M .

Assuming that the individual consumes all his income in a given period (no savings from one period to another), that the interest rate is due at the end of this period, and that the transaction cost is independent of the amount withdrawn, the total cost of managing money is given by the number of transactions N multiplied by its unit cost (NC) plus the interest yield given up by keeping money at hand (iM), where M depends on the number of transactions. If one withdrawal is made, M equals $Y/2$. If two withdrawals are made, the average amount of funds held in the period is $Y/4$. The general formula is $M = Y/2N$. Thus, the total cost of money management (TC) is given in equation 6.1:

$$TC = NC + Y_i/2N \quad (6.1)$$

Deriving and setting the above equation equal to zero, the number of transactions N that minimizes this cost is given by equation 6.2:

$$N^* = \sqrt{Y_i/2C} \quad (6.2)$$

Since the average value of resources held in cash is $Y/2N^*$, we have the following relationship, given by equation 6.3:

$$M = Y/2N^* = \sqrt{YC/2i} \quad (6.3)$$

Thus, it follows that the demand for money is directly proportional to income and transaction costs and indirectly proportional to the interest rate. This theory has been extended in various ways over time. For example, Alvarez & Lippi (2009) introduced random no-cost withdrawal opportunities and concluded that it is always advantageous to withdraw at these opportunities, even if one has cash on hand, as a precaution, since there is uncertainty about the cost of future withdrawals. Alvarez & Lippi (2017), meanwhile, extend the model by allowing individuals to spend on cards at a cost proportional to the value of the transaction, in addition to spending cash at a fixed cost per transaction. The conclusion is that the optimal policy is always to spend cash if available ("cash burning policy"). Alvarez & Argente (2021) extend the model considering how the Covid-19 pandemic increased the transaction cost of using cash, explaining why cash transactions

reduced during the pandemic, even though only slightly as shown by their research, with data from Latin America and the US.

6.2.2 Cash-first optimal choice

Under this theory, proposed by Arango-Arango et al. (2018), given the need to make a payment, an agent chooses to fulfill it using cash whenever she has enough cash at hand. If the payment amount is greater than her cash amount at hand, she chooses to pay with another instrument such as a payment card. There are no income restraints.

Their model, following Alvarez & Lippi, (2009) and others, shows that payers hold cash for precautionary reasons, fearing, for example, that fees for making cash withdrawals may be high, that using cards may be expensive, or that cards may not be accepted when needed. People would then try to hold a minimum amount of cash, or a "minimum cash holdings policy" as stated by Arango-Arango et al. (2018).

Finally, their model, following Alvarez & Lippi (2017), considers that payers choose cash whenever they have enough cash to make a specific payment. If the amount of cash they have is not enough, they pay with a card. Alvarez & Lippi (2017) state that cash "burns", while Arango-Arango et al. (2018) mention it as "cash first". It is reasoned that, after paying a (possibly high) fixed cost for getting cash, people consider the marginal cost of using it smaller than that of cards. This is specially true for low payment values.

They test their model with payment diaries data from six developed countries (United States, Austria, Canada, France, Germany and the Netherlands) concluding that their theory is able to explain the payment patterns presented in the surveys, with differences between predictions and observed cash shares of payments (weighted by transaction values) ranging from 3.5% to 7.6% in France and the United States, respectively. In the Netherlands, the fit of the model is worse (12.1%), possibly due to the fact the debit cards are less costly in this country, both for merchants and payers, as the authors state it. In this country, a higher share of payments, specially lower value ones, are paid with debit cards and the minimum cash holdings is smaller than in the other countries. Their results suggest that high Automated Teller Machines (ATM) fees increase the cost of getting cash and consequently, induce payers to hold higher amounts of cash. Having incurred this high fixed cost, they tend to pay with cash even for higher transactions in these circumstances.

A natural extension of this model that I suggest would consider a cash-like instrument, free of user charge as debit cards in the Netherlands (and in Brazil), but that require resources to be in no interest account. The payer would then waiver interest income in order to use this instrument. The updated policy would be to use cash whenever available, withdrawn if it falls below a predefined threshold, to use this cash-like instrument whenever there are resources available in a payment account, replenished from an interest-bearing account or fund whenever its balance falls bellow a second predefined account. Otherwise, a credit card is chosen to fulfill the payment.

Based on the descriptions given above, I then postulate the following hypotheses:

- H6.1: the cash-first optimal choice theory is applicable to Brazilian payers.

- H6.2: an extension of the the cash-first optimal choice theory that considers a cash-like instrument is applicable to Brazilian payers.

6.2.3 Agent-based models

According to Macal and North (2010), agent-based modeling is a simulation approach in which autonomous agents interact in complex systems, allowing the emergence of patterns and behaviors not directly specified in the models. When compared to traditional econometric models, ABMs make it easier to replicate social interactions, adaptive and learning agent behaviors, and patterns of information diffusion (Gilbert & Terna, 2000; Macy & Willer, 2002). As a consequence, they have been used in many knowledge areas that require or benefit from the modeling of interactions among agents, such as biology, ecology, and sociology.

In Finance and Economics, ABMs have been used extensively, including applications to industrial organization (Sanchez-Cartas, 2018), banking (Chan-lau, 2017; Liu et al., 2020) and financial markets (Katahira et al., 2019). In payments, there are some models about the payments system as a whole (Galbiati & Soramäki, 2011), modeling of network topology, contagion and payment flows.

Cards have been addressed in the works of Alexandrova-Kabadjova et al. (2007), that focus not only on the payer, but also on the competition of the institutions involved. They conclude that the market tend to be dominated by a small number of payment schemes. Alexandrova-Kabadjova & Negrín (2009) address the drivers of card network growth, while Alexandrova-Kabadjova et al. (2015) study the adoption of payment cards conditional on the level of the interchange fee (the fee payed by the merchant to the issuer of the card). Kriete-Dodds & Maringer (2016) focus on the behavior of credit cards users, showing that overconfidence leads to more borrowing, in an application closer to my objective, but, to the best of my knowledge, I have not identified any models focusing specifically on payment instrument choice.

There are general innovation diffusion models, such as the one proposed by Johanning et al. (2020), that could potentially be used to model new payment instruments adoption, for example, but as far as I know, they have not been applied to the payments universe. The lack of studies with simulation techniques is a gap identified in my first study (chapter 2) that I help to address.

6.3 Methodology

6.3.1 Model 1

Our first model is the simulation proposed by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) to test empirically the cash first optimal choice theory in six different countries, but here implemented as an agent-based model. I implemented it as an ABM for extensibility reasons, as will be clear when I present model 2 later on.

In this model, as described by Arango-Arango et al. (2018), each period is divided into two sub-periods, a and b. In the first sub-period, the agent makes a cash withdrawal

if she has less cash than a threshold m^{th} . In the second sub-period, the agent can make a payment of amount p . If p is smaller than the amount m of money she has at the moment, the payment is made with cash. If p is greater than m , the payment is made with a payment card. The agent starts with no cash at hand ($m_0 = 0$). The distribution of payments comes from the payments diaries described in section 6.3.3. So, the amount of cash an agent has at the beginning of sub-period b of time t , just before being presented with a payment need and right after making a cash withdrawal of amount w (if she chooses to according to her policy), is given by equation 6.4, adapted from Arango-Arango et al. (2018).

$$m_t^{(b)} = \begin{cases} m_t^{(a)} & \text{if } m > m^{th} \\ m_t^{(a)} + w & \text{if } m \leq m^{th} \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

where w is the value of a cash withdrawal drawn from the withdrawals distribution. She then ends up with the same amount she had at the beginning of sub-period a , if she already had more cash than her desired threshold m^{th} , or with the amount she already had previously plus the amount withdrawn, defined according to the withdrawal distribution.

At the beginning of sub-period a of time $t+1$, just after making a payment of amount p and right before being presented with an withdrawal opportunity of amount w , the amount of cash an agent has is given by equation 6.5, also adapted from Arango-Arango et al. (2018).

$$m_{t+1}^{(a)} = \begin{cases} m_t^{(b)} - p & \text{if } p \leq m_t^{(b)} \\ m_t^{(b)} & \text{if } p > m_t^{(b)} \end{cases} \quad (6.5)$$

where p is the value of the payment made by the agent. So, she ends up with the amount of cash she had previously less the value of the payment, if it is smaller than the value of cash she already had, or she ends up with exactly what she had if the value of the payment is greater than it and she opts to pay with another instrument such as a payment card.

In this model, I have as parameters the number of agents n , the initial cash balance of each agent m_0 , the threshold withdrawal limit m^{th} , the payments distribution P and the withdrawals distribution W . Table 34 summarizes these parameters.

Following Arango-Arango et al. (2018), the best combination of parameters is the one that minimizes the weighted difference between the simulated and observed share of payments made with cash, $G_1(m)$, given by equation 6.6.

$$G_1(m) = \sum_{p \in P} w_p \left| S_{cash}^{sim}(p) - S_{cash}^{obs}(p) \right| \quad (6.6)$$

where w_p is the share of payments of value p in the payments distribution, $S_{cash}^{sim}(p)$ and $S_{cash}^{obs}(p)$ are the simulated and observed, respectively, share of payments of value p made with cash. For implementation reasons, I divided the payments distributions into R\$ 2 intervals.

Table 34 – Parameters in each model

Parameter	Description	Model 1	Model 2
n	number of agents	1519	1519
steps	number of steps in each iteration	11	11
m_0	initial agent's cash balance	0	0
m^{th}	threshold for withdrawal	1 to 9; 10, 12, ..., 18; 20, 25, ..., 45; 50, 60, ..., 90; 100, 120, ... 180; 200, 250, ..., 450; 500, 600, ..., 900	1 to 9; 10, 12, ..., 18; 20, 25, ..., 45; 50, 60, ..., 90; 100, 120, ... 180; 200, 250, ..., 450; 500, 600, ..., 900
$m2^{th}$	threshold for transferring to checking account		100, 200, ..., 900
P	payments distribution	empirical distribution according to section 6.3.3	empirical distribution according to section 6.3.3
W	withdrawals distribution	hypothetical distributions 1 to 5, according to Figure 18	hypothetical distributions 1 to 5, according to Figure 18
A	transfers to payment accounts distribution		hypothetical distributions 1 and 2, according to Figure 19

6.3.2 Model 2

The second model is a straightforward extension of the first model, but I now consider the agent to have the option of a costless electronic payment instrument such as a free debit card or a free instant payment solution. She then establishes a second threshold $m2^{th}$ used to determine when to move funds from a interest-bearing account or fund to a checking or payment account from which a payment can be made. So, I have to keep track not only of the amount of cash the agent has, but also of the amount of resources she has at her checking or payment account ($m2$), which is given, at the beginning of sub-period b, by equation 6.7.

$$m2_t^{(b)} = \begin{cases} m2_t^{(a)} & \text{if } m2 > m2^{th} \\ m2_t^{(a)} + w2 & \text{if } m2 \leq m2^{th} \end{cases} \quad (6.7)$$

where $w2$ is the amount she transfers from the interest-bearing account or fund to her checking or payment account.

The agent's instrument payment choice is also a straightforward extension of model 1. She pays with cash if the payment value is less than the amount of cash m she has, pays with a debit card (or instant payment transfer) if the payment amount is greater than m , but less than the amount $m2$ she has in her payment account, and pays with a credit card if the payment value is greater than $m2$. So, at the beginning of sub-period a, the amount she has in her checking or payment account is given by equation 6.8.

$$m2_{t+1}^{(a)} = \begin{cases} m2_t^{(b)} - p & \text{if } m_t^{(b)} < p \leq m2_t^{(b)} \\ m2_t^{(b)} & \text{if } p > m2_t^{(b)} \end{cases} \quad (6.8)$$

In this model, besides the parameters defined in model 1, I have the threshold for transferring resources to the checking or payment account $m2^{th}$ and the transfers to payment accounts distribution A. Table 34 presents the parameters and the values used in each model.

Model 2 is evaluated in a manner similar to Model 1, but I now consider the share of payments made not only with cash, but also with debit cards (or instant payments), as in equation 6.9.

$$G_2(m) = \sum_{p \in P} w_p \left(\left| S_{cash}^{sim}(p) - S_{cash}^{obs}(p) \right| + \left| S_{debit}^{sim}(p) - S_{debit}^{obs}(p) \right| \right) \quad (6.9)$$

where $S_{debit}^{sim}(p)$ and $S_{debit}^{obs}(p)$ are the simulated and observed, respectively, share of payments of value p made with debit card. As in Model 1, w_p is the share of payments of value p in the payments distribution, $S_{cash}^{sim}(p)$ and $S_{cash}^{obs}(p)$ are the simulated and observed, respectively, share of payments of value p made with cash.

6.3.3 Data

Data comes from the survey commissioned by the Central Bank of Brazil mentioned in studies 3 (chapter 4) and 4 (chapter 5), with confidence level of 95% and margin of error of 2.5% (Banco Central do Brasil, 2021), part of the project for evaluating an instant payment solution that culminated with the implementation of Pix in November 2020 (Lobo & Brandt, 2021). 1,519 people (segmented by geographic region, age, gender, marital status, household income, education and employment relationship) and 615 merchants (segmented by geographic region, sector and number of employees) where survey between 04/26/2019 and 05/15/2019 with questions about perception and preferences on payment instruments, ownership of checking or payment accounts, previous experience with mobile purchases, among others.

The 1,519 respondents were asked to fill out a payment diary between 04/27 and 06/12/2019, comprising seven days of their choice. In this diary, each person had to register all payments made in the period, including information on value, payment instrument used, where the payment was made, what was the sector of the merchant and what was the payment condition (if cash, term or in installments payment), for example. In total, 1,379 diaries were returned, totaling 16,712 registered payments. Questions and microdata are available at Banco Central do Brasil (2021).

Descriptive statistics for payments with the 12 payments instruments recorded is presented in table 35. It shows that the main instruments used by respondents of the survey were cash and credit, debit and prepaid card. Other instruments correspond to a considerably lower share of the payments. Cash is still the dominant instrument in terms of volume, in line with studies such as Bagnall et al. (2016) and Bech et al. (2018), who show that this is still the reality in many countries.

For the purpose of my study, I am concerned with the distribution of payments with each payment instrument per value. Dividing the payments in R\$ 2 intervals, the distribution of payments per value is presented in figure 16. There is a prevalence of low valued payments, with payments up to R\$40 comprising 50% of the total (the median value in Table 35), with round values accounting for the great majority of the payments. Table 36 shows the most frequent values of payments and table 37 shows the frequency distribution for R\$25 intervals.

Figure 17 shows the proportion of payments with each instrument per value of payments range. It can be seen that cash rules in every range, but its proportion falls

Table 35 – Number and value of payments per instrument in the diaries

Instrument	N	Mean	Medn.	Min.	Max.	SD	VC	Kurt.	Skew.	% of obs.
Cash	12805	81.05	30.00	0.30	8000.00	165.98	0.49	448.04	12.92	76.62%
Debit card	1963	128.99	65.00	2.00	3000.00	210.94	0.61	53.85	5.79	11.75%
Credit card	1155	187.53	100.00	2.00	5200.00	306.86	0.61	93.55	7.53	6.91%
Prepaid card	235	33.95	9.00	2.00	2050.00	146.46	0.23	155.27	11.58	1.41%
Meal card	125	111.57	30.00	1.00	900.00	181.70	0.61	8.60	2.45	0.75%
Cheque	120	162.02	57.98	1.50	2386.00	327.19	0.50	26.42	4.54	0.72%
Boleto	92	537.21	307.50	13.00	3300.00	671.87	0.80	8.80	2.40	0.55%
Direct debit	77	291.75	150.00	12.88	2000.00	388.58	0.75	9.94	2.58	0.46%
Store card	50	300.98	175.00	20.00	1850.00	323.40	0.93	11.63	2.47	0.30%
Book transfers	40	467.13	335.00	20.00	1525.00	439.69	1.06	3.18	1.17	0.24%
Other	24	225.81	52.75	4.20	1300.00	365.72	0.62	5.73	1.91	0.14%
DOC	10	242.30	100.00	37.00	900.00	327.70	0.74	3.25	1.47	0.06%
TED	10	290.78	100.00	8.00	1100.00	392.25	0.74	3.15	1.37	0.06%
NA	6	158.53	47.89	20.00	700.00	267.66	0.59	4.07	1.72	0.04%
Nonelectronic	12934	81.83	30.00	0.30	8000.00	168.38	0.49	422.69	12.60	77.39%
Electronic	3778	160.92	73.00	1.00	5200.00	282.77	0.57	63.87	6.11	22.61%
Total	16712	99.71	40.00	0.30	8000.00	202.75	2.03	213.02	9.59	100.00%

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. Mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV), kurtosis (Kurt.) and skewness (Skew.) were calculated on the value of transactions with each payment instrument.

Table 36 – Most frequent payment values in the payment diaries

Value	Count	Percentage	Cumulative count	Cumulative percentage
20	864	5.17%	864	5.17%
50	862	5.16%	1726	10.33%
10	819	4.90%	2545	15.23%
30	740	4.43%	3285	19.66%
100	655	3.92%	3940	23.58%
15	485	2.90%	4425	26.48%
40	413	2.47%	4838	28.95%
60	388	2.32%	5226	31.27%
80	311	1.86%	5537	33.13%
70	306	1.83%	5843	34.96%
25	293	1.75%	6136	36.72%
150	288	1.72%	6424	38.44%
5	285	1.71%	6709	40.14%
8	281	1.68%	6990	41.83%
200	280	1.68%	7270	43.50%

Source: Author's elaboration.

Table 37 – Number of payments per R\$25 value intervals

Value range of the payment	Number of payments
(0,25]	6497
(25,50]	3383
(50,75]	1465
(75,100]	1575
(100,125]	541
(125,150]	609
(150,175]	189
(175,200]	525
(200,225]	150
(225,250]	250
(250,8000]	1528

Note. Source: Author's elaboration. Value range in R\$. Number of absolute payments recorded in the diaries.

slightly with the value of the payment.

Since I neither have the empirical distribution of withdrawals nor the empirical distribution of transfers from interest-bearing accounts to payment accounts, I made up

Figure 16 – Payments distribution (a) total and (b) up to R\$500. Source: Author’s elaboration

Figure 17 – Payments per instrument per value range (a) absolute numbers and (b) percentage. Source: Author’s elaboration

five hypothetical distributions based on other countries distributions. These distributions are shown in figures 18 and 19.

6.4 Results

The models were implemented with Python’s mesa module (Kazil et al., 2020). Source code is available at GitHub (https://github.com/dtcastro/retail_payments_model).

6.4.1 Model 1

For model 1, I ran 10 iterations with 11 steps and 1,519 users each, totaling 16,709 simulated payments in each iteration, close to the number of payments I have in my data.

Figure 20 shows the difference between the simulated and observed distribution ($G(m)$) for each simulated threshold m^{th} , showing the mean and a 95% confidence interval for the 10 iterations.

Figure 21 shows the difference between the simulated and observed cash payments distribution for the value of m^{th} that minimizes the weighted overall difference. The

Figure 18 – Hypothetical withdrawal distributions used in simulations. Source: Author’s elaboration

Figure 19 – Hypothetical transfers to payment accounts distributions used in simulations. Source: Author’s elaboration

Figure 20 – Difference $G(m)$ between the simulated and observed distribution for each simulated m^{th} in Model 1, (a) considering all of the simulated thresholds and (b) only thresholds above R\$100. Source: Author's elaboration

minimal difference was 9.65% when m^{th} was set at R\$500 (considering the mean of the 10 iterations; the absolute minimum was reached when m^{th} was R\$450, with an error of 9.04%). The model overestimates the proportion of cash payments, specially for lower value ones. Possibly, this is due to the existence of cash-like instruments in Brazil, such as debit cards, that have no direct cost to the payer.

Arango-Arango et al. (2018) report that "the average deviation obtained for Austria, Canada, France, Germany, and the US with respect to the observed shares of cash payments ranges from 3.5% to 7.6% and amounts to 12.1% for the Netherlands". The authors suggest that the cause of the relative high value found in the Netherlands is the low cost of debit cards. The same reason may explain in part the Brazilian results, since debit cards are free of charge for payers and the Merchant Discount Rate (MDR) charged to merchants is relatively low (around 1%). Indeed, as shown in table 35, debit cards were the second most used payment instruments reported in the diaries.

Arango-Arango et al. (2018) also suggest that "high ATM withdrawal fees may induce higher average cash holdings, which may explain why Austrians and Germans, for example, use cash for high transaction value purchases more often than consumers in other economies". In Brazil, a certain quantity of cash withdrawals per month are free of charge, but is not universal, since this gratuity is not applicable to payment institutions, now responsible for a considerable portion of the payments. ATMs distribution is irregular and many of them are not shared between institutions. This may contribute to a relative high value of usage of cash, specially for higher value payments, as can be seen in figure 17.

As mentioned earlier, Model 1 overestimates the proportion of cash payments, specially for lower value payments. Model 2 is an attempt to deal with this shortcoming, taking into account the existence of a cash-like instrument such as debit cards. Even though the difference between the observed and simulated payment distribution were relatively high, they are in line with the results found by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) and so were not able to reject hypothesis H6.1 that the cash-first optimal choice is applicable to the Brazilian case.

Figure 21 – Difference $G(m)$ between the simulated and observed share of cash payments per value for the best m^{th} in Model 1. Source: Author's elaboration

Figure 22 – Difference $G(m)$ between the simulated and observed distribution for each simulated m^{th} , (a) considering all thresholds simulated and (b) only those above R\$100 in Model 2. Source: Author's elaboration

6.4.2 Model 2

For Model 2, Figures 22 and 23 show the behavior of the weighted difference between the simulated and observed number of payments with cash and debit for each payment value range. The threshold m^{th} presents the same behavior show in Model 1, but $m2^{th}$ shows that the difference between simulated and observed distributions actually increases with greater values of this threshold.

Figure 24 shows the difference of the combination of both m^{th} and $m2^{th}$. It is the same information that is in figures 22 and 23, with the size of the bullet corresponding to the difference between the observed and simulated distributions. As can be seen, the

Figure 23 – Difference $G(m)$ between the simulated and observed distribution for each simulated $m2^{th}$, (a) considering all thresholds simulated and (b) only values of m^{th} above R\$100 in Model 2. Source: Author's elaboration

Figure 24 – Difference between the simulated and observed share of cash and debit payments per combination of m^{th} and $m2^{th}$. The size of the bullet corresponds to the difference between the observed and simulated distributions. Source: Author's elaboration

difference is higher for lower values of m^{th} and higher values of $m2^{th}$, with m^{th} being the most important factor driving the difference.

Figure 25 shows the difference between the simulated and observed cash payments distribution for the best combination of m^{th} and $m2^{th}$. These values are, respectively, R\$600 and R\$200, showing that the user may still opt for a relatively high level of cash and a relatively low level in her payment account. This may be because the cost of transferring funds between accounts is relatively small, with lost interest being the main cost. The model continues to overestimate the proportion of cash payments, specially for lower valued payments. The weighted difference between the observed and simulated

Figure 25 – Difference $G(m)$ between the simulated and observed share of cash and debit payments per value for the best m^{th} and $m2^{th}$. Source: Author's elaboration

usage was 16.4%, higher than in Model 1 because I now consider two instruments and the differences are added. If I consider that each instrument accounts for half of this error, the difference for the cash share shows that this Model is more precise than Model 1.

Payments between persons, that do not accept all payment instruments, such as cards, may be a challenge to the model, that do not take this fact into account. In the Brazilian case, though, this does not seem to be an issue, since less than 3% of the payments occur between persons.

Since the difference between observed and simulated payment distribution is in the range reported by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) and smaller than the difference reported in Model 1, it suggests that hypothesis H6.2 is not rejected.

6.5 Final considerations

In this study, I implemented an agent-based model based on the cash-first optimal choice proposed by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) in order to test this theory in the Brazilian case, comparing the simulated distribution of payments by instrument and value to the empirical distribution provided by payment diaries survey on behalf of the Central Bank of Brazil in 2019 (the same data used in studies three and four).

Our results suggest that the cash-first optimal choice proposed by Arango-Arango et al. (2018) is applicable to the Brazilian case, with difference between simulated and observed payment distributions in the range reported by the authors for other countries. For the countries studied by Arango-Arango et al. (2018), this difference ranged from

3.5% to 7.6%, with a 12.1% outlier in the Netherlands. In Brazil, I found this difference to be 9.5%.

The model overestimates the share of cash payments, specially for lower value payments, which can be explained by the existence of free of charge (to payers and relatively cheap to merchants) debit cards, as is the case in the Netherlands. The relatively high shares of cash payments, even for higher value payments, may suggest that cash withdrawal costs (including ATM fees, locomotion expenses, etc.) in the country may induce the holding of relative high values of cash (around 100 dollars). In Arango-Arango et al. (2018), this value range between 22 Canadian dollars and 67 euros in Canada and Austria, respectively. Even though the regulation grants some free cash withdrawals to the population, it is not universal, and the number and distribution of ATMs in country is a known problem, since they are concentrated geographically. Besides, a considerable portion of them are not shared, being exclusive to the use of clients of institution owning them. These facts may induce the high cash holdings I simulated. So, the Brazilian case may be explained by a mix of free cash withdrawals with a poor distribution of ATMs and free debit cards for the payers.

Model 2 results may suggest that taking into consideration the existence of some resources in a payment account, transferred at will from an interest-bearing account, may improve lead to a better fit of the simulated distribution to the empirical one. The difference between observed and simulated distributions fell to around 8%, from 9.5% in Model 1. This model takes in account the choice between cash, a free debit card, and a credit card, enhancing Model 1 that only considers cash and card.

Limitations include the absence of empirical data on withdrawal distribution, as well as data on transfers between interest-bearing and payment accounts. Data on the amount of cash available with each respondent is also missing. Simulation was used to supply these information, but the exploration of other data sets providing these information could be used, if available in future releases of the survey or from other sources. Other information available in the survey, on the other hand, such as information on merchants and on the perception of the users in relation to each payment instrument could be explored in further improvements of the models. Instrument acceptance could be modeled, even though Arango-Arango et al. (2018) mentions that it is less important. The distribution of ATMs may also be explored in a spacial ABM, for example.

Development in the payments landscape, such the launching of the Brazilian instant payments scheme (Pix), and the Covid-19 pandemic, as reported by Alvarez & Argente (2021), may have changed the behavior of the payers and payees. The data I employed is from a survey from 2019, before these developments and a new evaluation of the theory could bring further insights into the behavior of the payers, if data becomes available.

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7 Final considerations

In this thesis, I investigated the theme of determinants of retail payments in a broad perspective. Starting from a bibliometric analysis, an overview of the field was presented and research gaps were identified. Some of these gaps were then addressed in the four subsequent empirical studies that compose it.

In the bibliometric analysis, it was found that interest on the theme, measured by the number of studies published, is increasing over the years, with publications in high impact journals. It was also found that most of the studies are empirical, quantitative, have determinants of usage and choice as their object, have only one developed country in their scope, focus on cash and payment cards in short term analysis, employ data from surveys and interviews, including payment diaries, or data from regulators and Financial Market Infrastructures. Techniques most often employed are logit regressions and its variations. Few studies considering emerging countries, analyzing longer terms, employing alternative techniques such as machine learning or simulations, considering recent payment instruments such as instant payments, or employing real transaction data from retailers are the gaps identified.

Study two on the determinants of usage of electronic payments tries to fulfill two of the gaps, employing a wider data base that includes data from many emerging countries, and analyzing specifically the determinants of fast payments, a recent instrument infrequently addressed in the literature. The study employed a dynamic panel data analysis, concluding that the past level of usage is the most important determinant of usage of electronic (and conversely of nonelectronic) payment instruments. Other determinants, such as demographic and environmental variables, are not significant.

Employing data from Brazilian payment diaries surveyed in 2019, the third study identified, with the use of a multilevel logit regression, that male payers, with higher age, income and education, living in more urbanized regions, receiving their source of income in bank or payment accounts, and reporting previous experience with mobile shopping choose electronic payment instruments with higher probabilities. Among payment transaction characteristics, the probability of choosing electronic instruments is higher the higher the value of the payment, and also when the payment corresponds to durable goods purchases or term or in installments payments.

Conclusions of study four, which explains payment instrument choice with machine learning methods, notably Shapley Additive Explanation (SHAP) values, corroborated the findings of study three, as expected, adding information on the importance of the determinants. The condition of payment, when it is a term or in installment payment, is the most important variable, followed by how income is received (when in an account), past experience with mobile shopping and the value of the transaction.

Study five also focus on payment instrument choice employing the same data used in studies three and four. It corroborated to some extent the findings of study two on determinants of usage. Study two concludes that past behavior is the most important determinant of current behavior, being more important than all of the other determinants. With the use of an agent-based model, this study found that a theory on cash management

explains well the empirical distribution of payments per instrument and value reported in Brazilian payment diaries, suggesting that habit is indeed a major factor explaining payment instruments choice.

I consider that the thesis accomplished its main objective, of identifying determinants of usage and choice of retail payment instruments in a broad perspective. Study one accomplished the first specific objective of the thesis, of identifying research gaps. Study two accomplished the second and third specific objectives of the thesis, of identifying determinants of usage of electronic and fast payment instruments, respectively. Studies 3, 4 and 5 accomplished the fourth specific objective of the thesis, of identifying determinants of choice of retail payment instruments with different techniques.

The studies the comprise this thesis contribute to the literature by addressing a new payment instrument (fast payments) in the context of determinants of usage, by employing a wider sample of countries (study two), new data from Brazilian payment diaries (studies three to five), and methodologies seldom employed in the field (multilevel logit in study three, machine learning techniques in study four and an agent-based model in study five).

The thesis contributes to the field of empirical analysis of consumer economics by confirming some previous conclusions, but also with new findings. On the determinants of choice of payment instruments in Brazil, the importance of the payment value was confirmed, for example, but variables specific to the Brazilian reality, such as condition of payment or how income is received, proved to be more important. We also found one more evidence that a cash management policy wherein payers favor cash whenever it is available can explain the choice of payment instruments, testing it in the Brazilian case. On determinants of usage, the past behavior of the population proved to be the most important determinant, not quite in agreement with previous literature, which found other determinants to be important as well. The thesis also contributes to government policy and regulation on payments and marketing, because my finding can be used as inputs to policies aimed at the electronization of payment. They may also be useful for industry participants, guiding investments or improvements in infrastructure and marketing needed to stimulate the adoption of new instruments.

The thesis innovates by employing techniques such as Explainable Artificial Intelligence and multilevel logit to the field. It also suggests an original extension to the cash management policy of Arango-Arango et al. (2018), that proved capable of explaining the choice of payment instruments in the Brazilian case. I also use new data with Brazilian payment diaries not employed before in academia. The thesis is relevant for exploring a dynamic theme in a broad perspective.

Future work can expand the bibliometric analysis, widening search terms and sample articles, to be treated with machine learning methods if the number of articles exceeds what can be manually treated. Alternative methods can also be employed for the study of determinants of usage, such as cluster identification. In the last three studies, more recent data, comprising the period of the COVID-19 pandemic and the period after the introduction of Pix in Brazil, for example, if available in the future, could be used to conduct a dynamic analysis. The usage of other countries data could also be used in an international comparison.

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